

Detection and control of *Infectious spleen and kidney necrosis virus* in aquaculture

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Declaration of Authorship

Apart from the assistance stated in the acknowledgements section, this thesis represents the original work of the author. The results of this study have not been presented for any other degree or diploma at any other university.

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Cahya Kurnia Fusianto

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Summary

Infectious spleen and kidney necrosis virus (ISKNV) is the type species in the genus *Megalocytivirus* (MCV) within the family *Iridoviridae* (Chinchar et al., 2017). The species ISKNV includes three genotypes named red sea bream iridovirus (RSIV), ISKNV (genotype), and turbot reddish body iridovirus (TRBIV) which are sometimes referred to collectively as megalocytiviruses. Mortality due to ISKNV infection has been reported in at least 52 marine fish species (Wang et al., 2007) and 30 species of freshwater fish (Joon et al., 2008; Subramaniam et al., 2014). The infection can cause a disease with up to 100% mortality (Subramaniam et al., 2012). Fish with ISKNV infection exhibit generic clinical signs including a darkened body surface, lethargy and inappetence (He et al., 2000; Kurita et al., 2002). Infection with ISKNV can also be subclinical, which has likely contributed to spread of the virus to new hosts and locations via apparently healthy fish (Rimmer et al., 2015; Jung-Schroers et al., 2016; Girisha et al., 2021). Due to the considerable negative impact on aquaculture production, two genotypes of ISKNV, RSIV and ISKNV are currently included in the OIE list of notifiable diseases for aquatic animals and subjected to strict biosecurity regulation in many countries (OIE, 2021).

Biosecurity for ISKNV in aquaculture facilities is vital to limit local and transboundary spread of the virus (OIE, 2019b). Functional biosecurity requires appropriate diagnostic methods, knowledge of the characteristics of ISKNV and the pathobiology of infection, and effective disinfection measures which are combined to prevent ISKNV incursions into new environments. However, inadequate information regarding these aspects results in knowledge gaps in the design of biosecurity programs. The objective of this thesis was to generate new knowledge about ISKNV to inform improved disease control in aquaculture. This included a thorough veterinary diagnostic investigation at sea cage farms in Indonesia experiencing epidemic mortality events due to ISKNV. Determining the complete viral genome from diverse samples provided insights into diversity of the ISKNV species, resolution of

taxonomic confusion and enabled molecular epidemiologic analyses to guide biosecurity and disease control recommendations. From a practical standpoint, disinfection measures for ISKNV were evaluated to inform biosecurity measures at land-based aquaculture premises.

The literature review (Chapter 1) highlighted the importance of pathogen-specific knowledge as a key to develop effective biosecurity measures. There are gaps in knowledge for ISKNV regarding pathogenesis and understanding of the risks for virus transmission associated with subclinical infections. There is a need for validation of appropriate diagnostic methods, better understanding of the epidemiology of ISKNV infection, the development of appropriate disinfection protocols for ISKNV, and evaluation of the developed vaccines to offer broader options for ISKNV prevention. Chapter 1 also identified that the naming of ISKNV genotypes, clades and isolates based on a fish species, geographic location or environment is no longer applicable and generates confusion for disease control. New information has revealed that ISKNV infections do not have high specificity for host fish species and are not constrained by environmental barriers such as marine and freshwater, regardless of the genotype. The broad host range and general clinical signs of disease have contributed to confusing the nomenclature for ISKNV, other megalocytiviruses and fish iridoviruses. A clear naming system based on numerical identification of the clearly differentiated ISKNV genotypes and clades would support regional and international biosecurity.

In 2016, off the northern coast of Bali, a group of farmers reported mass mortality events in hybrid grouper within 2–4 weeks of transfer to sea cages. Chapter 3 demonstrated how the application of a broad range of techniques for diagnostic investigation using samples obtained based on an epidemiologic framework was able to identify the primary pathogen causing epidemic disease. A targeted sampling strategy was applied at 9 farms during the acute mortality events (Aug-Nov 2016) to collect samples across the range of disease presentation, including 24 fish with clinical signs and 12

fish without clinical signs per affected population. Two key pathogens, *Nervous necrosis virus* (NNV) and ISKNV were identified. NNV was identified in 55% and 57% of fish with and without clinical signs, respectively. For ISKNV the proportion positive in each group was 81% and 83%. Importantly, histopathology confirmed that ISKNV-related lesions were present at a true prevalence of 94% (95% Confidence interval 79–100%) for fish with clinical signs and 47% (95% CI 27–70%) in fish without clinical signs. There were no histopathological lesions consistent with viral nervous necrosis (VNN) disease (true prevalence <0.01– 0.4%) indicating that the NNV infection was subclinical. The ISKNV considered the most likely primary cause of the epidemics was identified as genotype ISKNV, Clade 1 using Illumina Miseq and Blast+ taxonomic labelling. The targeted sampling approach combined with thorough disease investigation in this chapter was essential to identify the main causative agent of the mortality events in circumstances where several pathogens were identified. Future research should focus on understanding the risk factors for ISKNV and NNV expressing as disease in grouper aquaculture and should utilise a diagnostic framework capable of differentiating other primary disease aetiologies.

Understanding the genomic characteristics of ISKNV using an epidemiological approach is important for disease control. The whole-genome of ISKNV can enable high resolution molecular epidemiology to identify genomic diversity and determine patterns of distribution of ISKNV. Chapter 4 describes the application of a hybrid capture DNA enrichment method to 16 archival samples to determine whole-genome sequences directly from clinical specimens. This was advantageous as there are limited reliable cell culture methodologies for ISKNV. This method was able to recover the whole genome sequence from archival samples and produced the same result compared to Illumina sequencing without enrichment on samples with a sufficient viral load to determine the complete genome directly. This also provided an advantage for preserved samples collected in remote areas for later analysis. Genomic analysis showed that the ISKNV genome was very stable with >98.81% nucleotide similarity across 14

samples from ISKNV Clade 1. These samples represented a broad range in year of collection (2011-2018), marine and freshwater environments, and 9 different host fish species. The study identified infection with ISKNV and RSIV genotypes at the same farm when sampled in different months. Each infection caused disease in hybrid grouper with indistinguishable clinical signs, yet despite being from the same viral species, these isolates were notably different with 88% nucleotide similarity across the whole genome. Gene-by-gene analysis with representative ISKNV genomes identified 59 core genes within the species, whilst the 14 Clade 1 ISKNV genomes in this study had 92-105 out of 122 predicted genes with 100% amino acid identity. Phylogenetic analysis based on the 59 core genes supported the differentiation of the 3 ISKNV genotypes. This finding provided essential evidence to consider ISKNV, RSIV, and TRBIV as separate pathogens to implement functional biosecurity measures. This is particularly relevant in development and interpretation of diagnostic tests and application of vaccination.

Despite the high similarity of the ISKNV genome, phylogenetic analysis using single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) identified clustering of samples that shared a common collection location. This analysis will provide a useful surveillance tool to understand the transboundary spread of ISKNV, including through international trade in fish and fish products. In particular, trading of ornamental fish has been implicated in the global spread of ISKNV (Go et al., 2006; Rimmer et al., 2015; Jung-Schroers et al., 2016; Koda et al., 2018). High resolution molecular epidemiology can predict the origin of ISKNV in the event of an outbreak to identify deficiencies in disease control and biosecurity measures. For example, one sample obtained from a fish collected in a pet shop in Sydney, Australia with an unknown country of origin was predicted to come from Indonesia based on SNP analysis.

Application of disinfection measures is an essential practice in biosecurity to prevent spread of ISKNV. The one previous study conducted by He et al. (2002) only tested inactivation of ISKNV under conditions of low organic load in the sample, leaving some questions about effective disinfection

protocols under high soiling conditions expected in aquaculture facilities (e.g. aquaculture water has a high loading of organic material). In Chapter 5, effective ISKNV disinfection protocols were evaluated under high soiling conditions. These were informed by guidelines for disinfection efficacy provided by the Australian Pesticides and Veterinary Medicines Authority (<https://apvma.gov.au/node/1026>) and the American Standard Testing and Material (ASTM) International standard (ASTM, 2018). Using a bioassay with Murray cod (*Maccullochella peelii*) to evaluate the infectivity of ISKNV, the study found that effective disinfection was accomplished by heating at 65°C for 20 minutes, chlorine at 1000 ppm for 30 minutes, pH 3 and pH 11 for 30 minutes, Virkon™ 1% and a quaternary ammonium compound at 650 ppm for 10 minutes. The stability of ISKNV in aquarium water was also studied in Chapter 5, revealing that ISKNV remained infectious in aquaria water for at least 48 hours at 25°C in the absence of a fish host. Further, the bioassay provided a more sensitive test for ISKNV compared to real-time polymerase chain reaction (qPCR). This finding emphasised the importance of water disinfection in aquaculture facilities with recirculating systems, such as those commonly used in the ornamental industry to house numerous fish species. These results were essential to inform functional disinfection protocols providing data that is specific for ISKNV to ensure effective disease control where ISKNV is endemic. The findings are suitable for land-based aquaculture facilities with recirculating aquaculture systems where disinfecting water and equipment is feasible.

The general discussion (Chapter 6) elaborates on the key findings from research described in Chapters 3 to 5 to define the knowledge gaps remaining in effective ISKNV disease control. In the context of complex multifactorial diseases in aquaculture, the importance of a multi-modal diagnostic approach and consideration of an appropriate sample size with collection of specimens at different stages of disease was emphasised. Despite the relative similarity and stability of ISKNV compared to many other aquatic viral pathogens, molecular epidemiology using complete genomes provides a tool for enhanced surveillance. This also contributed to knowledge about the considerable differences

between the genotypes of ISKNV which has not been appreciated due to overlaps in the host fish species and clinical signs of disease. This highlights the need for diagnostic test validation to provide methods that can detect and differentiate each of these genotypes. Further genotype specific studies of the epidemiology and pathobiology, particularly of subclinical infection will help understand the transmission pathways that can lead to disease outbreaks. Disease control using effective disinfection will be important as ISKNV becomes an established endemic pathogen in many aquaculture settings. However, further measures such as vaccination and enhanced surveillance are required to minimise disease impacts. This requires ISKNV genotypes to be differentiated using clear taxonomy and nomenclature to communicate information unambiguously as new species of megalocytiviruses are described.

In conclusion, this thesis has narrowed the knowledge gap about ISKNV to inform enhanced disease control in aquaculture including illustrating a sound diagnostic approach, the molecular epidemiology of ISKNV, and evaluation of practical disinfection protocols. There is an urgency to further study the epidemiology and pathobiology of ISKNV, particularly to differentiate risk factors for acute disease compared to subclinical infection. An outcome of this thesis is to encourage the OIE to re-evaluate regulation of ISKNV which relies on outdated nomenclature, disease knowledge and the absence of validated diagnostic tests. This should be facilitated by acceptance of a universal naming system for ISKNV isolates using a numeric system for genotype and clade groups.

List of Publications and Conference Presentations

Publications

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I co-designed the study, conducted negotiation with farmers for their active participation in the study, trained the field team from UGM on the sampling techniques, conducted the first sample collection (Population 1 at Farm A), completed all laboratory testing, collated the data, did the descriptive data analysis, and wrote the first draft of the manuscript and revised the manuscript with comments from supervisors and reviewers from the manuscript submission process.

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I co-designed the study, assembled the panel of archived samples, collected the archived samples, performed laboratory testing and data analysis, and wrote the first draft of the manuscript and revised the manuscript with comments from supervisors.

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I co-designed the study, conducted the experimental trials, completed the sample collection, laboratory testing and data analysis, and wrote the first draft of the manuscript and revised the manuscript with comments from supervisors and reviewers from the manuscript submission process.

Attesting authorship attribution

In addition to the statements above, in cases where I am not the corresponding author of a published item, permission to include the published material has been granted by the corresponding author.

Cahya Kurnia Fusianto

June 2021

As supervisor for the candidature upon which this thesis is based, I can confirm that the authorship attribution statements above are correct.

Associate Professor Dr Joy A. Becker

30 June 2021

As supervisor for the candidature upon which this thesis is based, I can confirm that the authorship attribution statements above are correct.

Associate Professor Dr Paul M. Hick

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Table of Contents

Declaration of Authorship	ii
Acknowledgements	iii
Summary	v
List of Publications and Conference Presentations	xi
Publications	xi
Presentations.....	xi
Authorship attribution	xii
Attesting authorship attribution	xiv
List of Tables	xxii
List of Figures	xxv
Abbreviations	xxvii
1. Chapter 1 – Literature Review	1
1.1 Introduction.....	1
1.2 The emergence and geographic distribution of <i>Infectious spleen and kidney necrosis virus</i>	4
1.3 Morphology, structure, and genomic characteristics of <i>Infectious spleen and kidney necrosis virus</i>	18
1.4 Taxonomy and phylogeny of <i>Infectious spleen and kidney necrosis virus</i>	19
1.5 Clinical signs and gross pathology	24
1.6 Histopathology	24

1.7	Epidemiology of <i>Infectious spleen and kidney necrosis virus</i>	25
1.7.1	Pathogen risk factors.....	25
1.7.2	Host risk factors.....	29
1.7.3	Environmental risk factors	30
1.7.4	Transmission of <i>Infectious spleen and kidney necrosis virus</i>	30
1.8	Detection of <i>Infectious spleen and kidney necrosis virus</i> and diagnosis of disease	31
1.8.1	Cell culture	32
1.8.2	Indirect fluorescent antibody test (IFAT)	34
1.8.3	Polymerase chain reaction	34
1.9	Prevention and control of <i>Infectious spleen and kidney necrosis virus</i>	38
1.9.1	Disinfection.....	38
1.9.2	Vaccination.....	41
1.9.3	Translocation and regulations.....	44
1.10	Conclusions.....	45
1.11	Thesis objectives.....	45
2.	General Materials and Methods	47
2.1	Introduction.....	47
2.2	Reagents.....	47
2.2.1	General reagents.....	47
2.2.2	Reagents for DNA methods.....	48

2.3	Sampling	50
2.3.1	General guidelines.....	50
2.3.2	On farm sampling	51
2.3.3	Manual homogenisation	51
2.3.4	Bead-beating sample homogenization	51
2.4	Nucleic acid methods	52
2.4.1	General guidelines.....	52
2.4.2	Nucleic acid extraction	52
2.4.2.1	Spin column.....	52
2.4.2.2	MagMax Express-96	53
2.4.2.3	Phenol Chloroform extraction.....	54
2.4.3	Evaluation of DNA purity.....	54
2.4.4	Quantitative polymerase chain reaction (qPCR) assay for ISKNV	55
2.4.5	Reverse transcriptase quantitative polymerase chain reaction (RT-qPCR) assay for <i>Nervous necrosis virus</i>	56
2.4.6	Preparation of sample sections for histopathology	57
3.	Chapter 3 - Outbreak investigation attributes <i>Infectious spleen and kidney necrosis virus</i> as a necessary cause of a mortality epidemic in farmed grouper (<i>Epinephelus spp.</i>) in Bali, Indonesia	58
3.1	Abstract	58
3.2	Introduction.....	59
3.3	Materials and methods	62
3.3.1	Site description.....	62

3.3.2	Study design	62
3.3.3	Fish collection.....	65
3.3.4	Examination for ectoparasites	65
3.3.5	Necropsy and sample collection	66
3.3.6	Nucleic acid purification.....	66
3.3.7	qPCR assay for MCV	67
3.3.8	RT-qPCR assay for Nervous necrosis virus.....	67
3.3.9	Histopathology	67
3.3.10	Unbiased sequencing for potential novel pathogens	68
3.3.10.1	DNA purification and sequencing.....	68
3.3.10.2	Sequence analysis	68
3.3.10.3	Genome assembly and phylogenetic analysis.....	69
3.3.10.4	Statistical Analysis	70
3.4	Results	71
3.4.1	Case detection.....	71
3.4.2	Ectoparasites and gross pathology.....	73
3.4.3	Proportion of fish with NNV infection.....	73
3.4.4	Proportion of fish with MCV infection	76
3.4.5	Metagenomic sequencing for unknown pathogens	78
3.4.6	Characterisation of the MCV genome.....	78
3.5	Discussion.....	81

4. Chapter 4. Genotypic characterization of <i>Infectious spleen and kidney necrosis virus (ISKNV)</i> in Southeast Asian aquaculture	92
4.1 Summary.....	92
4.2 Introduction.....	93
4.3 Methods	96
4.3.1 Samples of ISKNV infected fish.....	96
4.3.2 Purification of nucleic acids and quantification of ISKNV	98
4.3.3 Design of hybrid bait capture sequences.....	98
4.3.4 Sequencing library preparation, hybridisation and sequencing	99
4.3.5 Genome assembly and annotation	101
4.3.6 Genetic and phylogenetic analysis.....	102
4.3.7 Comparison of hybrid capture enrichment with direct sequencing of clinical specimens	103
4.4 Results	103
4.4.1 Hybrid bait capture design.....	103
4.4.2 Evaluation of hybrid capture genome enrichment methods of ISKNV.....	104
4.4.3 MCV genome assembly and annotation	104
4.4.4 Genome structure and sequence identity	107
4.4.5 Phylogenetic analysis	111
4.5 Discussion.....	116
4.6 Conclusion	121

5. Chapter 5: Stability of <i>Infectious spleen and kidney necrosis virus</i> and susceptibility to physical and chemical disinfectants	130
5.1 Abstract	130
5.2 Introduction.....	131
5.3 Materials and methods	133
5.3.1 Fish and Experimental Conditions.....	133
5.3.2 Source of infective ISKNV	133
5.3.2.1 Trial 1.....	134
5.3.2.2 Trial 2.....	134
5.3.3 <i>ISKNV preparation for assessment of disinfection treatments</i>	135
5.3.4 Bioassays	138
5.3.5 Stability of ISKNV in water.....	142
5.3.6 Quantitative PCR for ISKNV	142
5.4 Results	142
5.4.1 Trial 1 and Trial 2.....	142
5.4.2 Donor Murray cod for Trial 3 and Trial 4.....	143
5.4.3 Trial 3 and 4: Bioassays testing disinfectant treatments	143
5.4.3.1 Heating	143
5.4.3.2 Chemical disinfectants and pH disruption	144
5.4.3.3 Positive Control Groups	144
5.4.3.1 Negative Controls.....	145
5.4.4 Trial 5 Stability of ISKNV in water.....	147
5.5 Discussion.....	149

6. General discussion	153
6.1 Introduction.....	153
6.2 Multi-modal diagnostic approach to investigate epidemics at sea cage farms	154
6.3 Characteristic of <i>Infectious spleen and kidney necrosis virus</i>	157
6.4 Subclinical infection of <i>Infectious spleen and kidney necrosis virus</i>	160
6.5 Disinfection measures of <i>Infectious spleen and kidney necrosis virus</i>	160
6.6 Recommendations.....	162
6.7 Conclusion	163
7. References	164

List of Tables

Table 1. 1. Reports of disease caused by ISKNV reported in the peer reviewed scientific literature for food fish (FF) and ornamental fish (OF), in marine (M) and freshwater (F) environments... ..	8
Table 1.2. List of cell lines developed for ISKNV propagation.	33
Table 1.3. Summary of widely used primers for ISKNV detection by PCR.	37
Table 1.4. Specific disinfection protocols for ISKNV that have been evaluated.	39
Table 1.5. Summary of published vaccine development for ISKNV.	42
Table 3.1. Reported cases of acute high mortality disease at grouper farms between August and November 2016 on the northern coast of Bali.	72
Table 3.2. Proportion of individual fish with abnormalities observed at post-mortem and odds ratios for the presence of abnormalities in samples targeted to fish showing behavioural clinical signs of disease at the time of sampling.	74
Table 3.3. Results for the detection of viral pathogens by PCR for fish classified on the presence of clinical signs at the time of sampling.	75
Table 4. 1. Description of samples used to evaluate ISKNV genomic diversity in Southeast Asian aquaculture.	97
Table 4. 2. Comparison of ISKNV genomes determined using the hybrid bait capture enrichment method compared to direct sequencing of tissue homogenate for two samples with a high concentration of viral DNA.	105
Table 4. 3. Characteristics of the MCV genomes determined using a hybrid capture enrichment method for fish tissue homogenates.	106
Table 4. 4. Pairwise comparison of whole genomes characterized in the present study.	109
Table 4. 5. Amino acid similarity for gene-by-gene comparison within the predicted ORFs in the samples from the present study and reference samples from similar genotypes.	110

Table 5. 1. Summary of disinfection treatments tested for inactivating ISKNV..	137
Table 5. 2. The disinfection of ISKNV using heat as assessed by bioassay and qPCR (Trial 3).....	139
Table 5. 3. The disinfection of ISKNV as assessed by bioassay and qPCR.....	140
Table 5. 4. The negative control groups tested with ISKNV-negative challenge material (Trial 4).	146
Table 5. 5. Stability of ISKNV in water as assessed by bioassay and qPCR (Trial 5).....	148
Supplemental Table S3. 1. Molecular identification of the parasites was based on BLAST results of the DNA sequence of 18s rRNA gene amplified with the indicated primers.....	86
Supplemental Table S3. 2. Summary of diagnostic observations for the individual fish selected for unbiased sequencing using Illumina Miseq.....	87
Supplemental Table S3. 3. By population, the proportion of individuals with gross pathological observations for fish in which clinical signs were present (P) or absent (A) when fish were selected from the sea cage.....	88
Supplemental Table S3. 4. Results for <i>Megalocytivirus</i> qPCR and nervous necrosis virus (NNV) RT- qPCR testing by population for fish in which clinical signs were present (P) or absent (A)..	89
Supplemental Table S3. 5. BLASTN results for contigs generated from de novo assembly of high throughput sequencing.....	90
Supplemental Table S3. 6. Taxonomic identification of the translated amino acid sequences from the Illumina reads after host genome depletion against Bacteria, Archaea and Viruses BLAST nr database using Kaiju web-based program.....	91
Supplementary Table S4. 1. <i>In-silico</i> evaluation of probe design by mapping to ISKNV reference genomes and comparison with the genomes derived from the hybrid probe enrichment study..	123
Supplementary Table S4. 2. Conserved repeated sequence regions identified in ISKNV and RSIV clade 1 and 2. ISKNV genomes mentioned in Figure 2 excluding TRBIV were analyzed using tandem repeats finder (Benson, 1999).....	126

Supplementary Table S4. 3. Core genes of members of the species ISKNV after a cut-off point
of 95% amino acid identity across ISKNV genotypes. 128

List of Figures

Figure 1. 1. Illustration of the global distribution of the three genotypes of ISKNV classified according to the ATPase and or MCP gene sequences..... 22

Figure 1. 2. (A) Transmission electron photomicrograph of a grunt fin cell (cultured in vitro) infected with three spot gourami iridovirus (TSGIV) showing a paracrystalline array of virus particles.
 (B) Hexagonal nucleocapsids TSGIV virions with dense cores, medium-density cores, and lucent cores. Use with permission from Koda et al. (2018)..... 23

Figure 1. 3. Phylogenetic tree of 26 MCV whole genome sequences and information table for the sequences showing the relationship between the three genotypes of ISKNV, each with two clades.. 26

Figure 1. 4. Megalocytic inclusion bearing cells in Hybrid grouper displaying clinical signs and infection with ISKNV (a) anterior kidney with multiple stages of megalocytes (white arrows: early stage, black arrows: late stage of megalocytes) associated with necrosis. (b) normal anterior kidney of grouper without clinical signs.. 28

Figure 3.1. Sampling locations of the 12 grouper grow-out farms in Bali, Indonesia 64

Figure 3.2. Megalocytic inclusion bearing cells in (A) infected anterior kidney (from Population 7). Multiple stages of megalocytes (white arrows: early stage, black arrows: late stage of megalocytes) were observed in anterior kidney associated with necrosis. (B) normal anterior kidney of grouper without clinical signs (Population 10).. 77

Figure 3.3. Phylogenetic tree for representative genotypes of the ISKNV species of megalocytiviruses and the hybrid grouper ISKNV isolate (this study, ID # 3-9 and 7-10 Supplemental Table S3.5), calculated by the maximum likelihood method with the general time reversible model and 1000 bootstraps.... 80

Figure 4. 1. Maximum likelihood phylogenetic cladogram based on 59 ISKNV species core genes and information table for the sequences. 113

Figure 4. 2. Cladogram of the whole genome sequence of the 16 study samples and ISKNV species based on single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP).. 114

Supplementary Figure S4. 1. Hybrid probe design for ISKNV genome enrichment from fish samples..122

Supplementary Figure S4. 2. Genome structure view developed after progressive alignment in MAUVE indicating consistent genome structure across all samples from this study and two ISKNV reference genome, Angelfish iridovirus AFIV-16 (MK689685) and Banggai cardinal fish iridovirus BCIV-2012 (MN432490) 124

Supplementary Figure S4.3. Dot plots for pairwise comparison between samples: A. Sample 1 (representing the ISKNV Clade 1 samples in this study) with MK689685 Angelfish iridovirus AFIV-16 , B. Sample 3 (ISKNV Clade 2) and MN432490 Banggai cardinal fish iridovirus (BCIV), C. Sample 16 (RSIV genotype clade 2) and MK098186.1 Pompano iridovirus isolate PIV 2014a, D. Sample 5 (ISKNV genotype Clade 1) and Sample 16 (RSIV genotype) which were the amongst the most dissimilar genomes detected in this study and obtained from the same aquaculture site showed high collinearity. 125

Abbreviations

°C	Degrees centigrade
µg	Micrograms
µL	Microlitre
AGRF	Australian Genome Research Facility
ASTM	American Standard Testing and Material
AUD	Australian dollars
BCIV	Banggai cardinal fish iridovirus
BF-2	Bluegill fry-2
BLOD	Below level of detection
BLOQ	Below the limit of quantification
bmGH	Brown-marbled grouper heart
bp	base pairs
cDNA	Complementary deoxyribonucleic acid
cDNA	Complementary deoxyribonucleic acid
Ct	Cycle threshold
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic acid
ECIV	European chub iridovirus
EDTA	Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid

EHNV	Epizootic hematopoietic necrosis virus
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organisation
FBS	Foetal bovine serum
FEC	Flounder embryonic cell line
FKC	Formalin killed cell
g	Grams
<i>g</i>	Gravity
G	Needle gauge
GF	Grunt fin
Hz	Hertz
ICTV	The International Committee for Taxonomy of Viruses
IFAT	Indirect fluorescent antibody test
IP	Intraperitoneal
ISKNV	<i>Infectious spleen and kidney necrosis virus</i>
Kg	Kilograms
L	litres
M	Molar
Mab	Monoclonal antibody
MCP	Major capsid protein

MCV	<i>Megalocytivirus</i>
MFF-1	Mandarin fish fry-1
MFF-8C1	Mandarin fish fry-8C1
Mg	Milligrams
mL	Millilitres
mm	Millimetres
MQ	Milli-Q
mRNA	Messenger ribonucleic acid
NCBI	National Center for Biotechnology Information
ng	Nanogram
nM	Nanomolar
NNV	<i>Nervous necrosis virus</i>
NSW	New South Wales
OIE	World Organisation for Animal Health
ORF	Open reading frame
OsHV-1	Ostreid herpesvirus-1 microvariants
PBS	Phosphate buffered saline
PCR	Polymerase chain reaction
pDGIV-MCP1	Plasmid dwarf gourami iridovirus-major capsid protein 1

ppm	Parts per million
ppt	Parts per thousand
qPCR	Quantitative PCR
RNA	Ribonucleic acid
RSBF-2	Red sea bream fin-2
RSIV	Red sea bream iridovirus
RT	Reverse transcriptase
s	Seconds
SAV	<i>Salmon pancreas disease virus</i>
SDDV	<i>Scale Drop Disease Virus</i>
SE Asia	Southeast Asia
SGIV	<i>Singapore grouper iridovirus</i>
SKJ-9	Spotted knifejaw-9
SNPs	Single nucleotide polymorphisms
SPB	Snubnose pompano brain
TF	Turbot fin
TiLV	<i>Tilapia lake virus</i>
Tm	Melting temperature
TRBIV	Turbot reddish body iridovirus

TSIV	Three spine stickleback iridovirus
UV	Ultraviolet
v	Volume
VNN	Viral nervous necrosis
w	Weight
WSSV	<i>White spot syndrome virus</i>

1 **1. Chapter 1 – Literature Review**

2 **1.1 Introduction**

3 The global human population is growing at 1.2 per cent per year in the period 2015-2020 resulting in
4 increasing demand for food, including fish (United Nations and Social Affairs, 2019). Global fish
5 consumption has increased by 3.1 per cent per year from 1961, higher than other animal protein foods
6 which increased by 2.1 per cent per year (FAO, 2020). According to the Food and Agriculture Organisation
7 of the United Nations (FAO), the total world fisheries production was 179 million tonnes in 2018, and of
8 this 82 million tonnes (46%) came from aquaculture (FAO, 2020). The trend for aquatic food production
9 reflects the increasing importance of aquaculture which continues to increase whilst the capacity for
10 capture fisheries has been maximised (FAO, 2020).

11 Despite increased output, all forms of aquaculture are limited by infectious diseases (FAO, 2020). The
12 impacts of disease can be very substantial including direct production loss and closure of aquaculture
13 facilities. Follow-on impacts include loss of employment in aquaculture and related upstream and
14 downstream industries and loss of domestic markets due to public concerns over the safety of consuming
15 fish and shellfish (FAO, 2020). To control the negative impact of diseases in aquaculture, the World
16 Organisation for Animal Health (OIE) publishes a list of notifiable diseases for aquaculture to reduce the
17 risk of spreading pathogens whilst facilitating international trade (OIE, 2021). One of the notifiable
18 diseases listed by the OIE is Red sea bream iridoviral disease which refers to infection with red sea bream
19 iridovirus (RSIV), a genotype of the species, *Infectious spleen and kidney necrosis virus* (ISKNV) within the
20 genus *Megalocytivirus* (MCV), family *Iridoviridae* (OIE, 2019b). The OIE Manual of Diagnostic Tests for
21 Aquatic Animals also state the disease is caused by the genotype ISKNV (OIE, 2019b). The listing of this
22 disease reflected the high level of mortality as well the need to contain the relative narrow geographical
23 distribution of a pathogen with a very broad range of susceptible species recognised to include at least 52

24 marine fish species (Wang et al., 2007) and 30 species of freshwater fish (Joon et al., 2008; Subramaniam
25 et al., 2014). Economic loss due to outbreaks of disease caused by ISKNV were severe, resulting in
26 mortality from 50 to 100% in freshwater (He et al., 2000; Subramaniam et al., 2016) and marine
27 aquaculture (Shi et al., 2004; Nakajima and Kurita, 2005). Due to the lack of host specificity and ease of
28 translocation through fish trading, ISKNV has become the subject of import regulation in many countries
29 (OIE, 2019a). ISKNV is widespread in aquaculture in Indonesia (Sah Putra et al., 2020; Sukenda et al., 2020;
30 Fusianto et al., 2021), however in Australia it remains listed as an exotic pathogen despite several
31 incursions (Lancaster et al., 2003; Rimmer et al., 2015; Go et al., 2016).

32 Knowledge about the genus *Megalocytiavirus* has developed rapidly since it was established in 2005
33 (Chinchar et al., 2017). This includes recognition of a second species, *Scale Drop Disease Virus* (SDDV)
34 which requires a change in terminology as the species name ISKNV and the genus MCV were often used
35 interchangeably. The species ISKNV encompasses three genotypes i.e. ISKNV, RSIV, and Turbot reddish
36 body iridovirus (TRBIV) (Chinchar et al., 2017). The genotypes of ISKNV show limited host specificity and
37 have been reported in at least in at least 52 marine fish species (Wang et al., 2007) and 30 species of
38 freshwater fish (Joon et al., 2008; Subramaniam et al., 2014). ISKNV has been distributed to many
39 locations worldwide, with trading of ornamental fish considered to be an important route (Rimmer et al.,
40 2015). The broad host range and wide geographic distributions of ISKNV have complicated the taxonomy
41 and generated confusion that impacts disease control. There has been a tendency to name isolates after
42 the host fish followed by the iridovirus descriptor, resulting in a large number of virus names within the
43 ISKNV species (Table 1.1). For example, ISKNV was identified recently causing disease in giant gourami
44 (*Osphronemus goramy*) in Indonesia and was reported as giant gourami iridovirus (GGIV) (Sukenda et al.,
45 2020). Based on viral sequence this virus isolate belonged to the ISKNV genotype of the ISKNV species.
46 Without an agreed standard nomenclature for ISKNV isolates, confusion can be overcome by using

47 indicating the ISKNV species and genotype classification according to a numbered system established by
48 phylogenetic analysis of the major capsid protein gene (Kurita and Nakajima, 2012).

49 There are minimal disease control options for ISKNV resulting in the need for preventative measures. Strict
50 biosecurity in aquaculture facilities is essential to limit local and transboundary spread of ISKNV (OIE,
51 2019b). Resilient biosecurity requires basic knowledge of pathogens (e.g. biology, pathogenicity, and
52 genetic diversity) and their hosts (e.g. susceptible species and vulnerable life stages), robust diagnostic
53 tests for detection and effective prevention measures that are applicable in aquaculture facilities (FAO,
54 2019). An accurate identification for ISKNV requires laboratory assays as ISKNV infections and the disease
55 presents with non-specific clinical signs (OIE, 2019b), or no signs in the case of subclinical infection (Sah
56 Putra et al., 2020). At present, the OIE Manual of Diagnostic Tests does not list a real-time PCR assay for
57 ISKNV due to insufficient validation data. The subclinical infection stage which has the potential to spread
58 the virus undetected (Rimmer et al., 2015), has received less attention from OIE. Studies regarding
59 preventative procedures for ISKNV are limited. Effective disinfection protocols are reported in a single
60 study (Fusianto et al., 2019). Research on ISKNV vaccine development has been piloted, however, only
61 one vaccine is licenced and commercially available (OIE, 2019b). The only commercial vaccine for ISKNV
62 is designed for RSIV genotype and does not protect against other genotypes (Dong et al., 2017).
63 Knowledge gaps in the prevention measures of ISKNV require epidemiological studies to identify the
64 disease risk factors relating to the host and environment, and transmission risks for the various ISKNV
65 genotypes (OIE, 2019b; FAO, 2020). Research considering the epidemiology of ISKNV, diagnostic test
66 validation and vaccine development for all ISKNV genotypes are a priority to safeguard many large
67 aquaculture industries.

68 The emergence of ISKNV has become a serious constraint for aquaculture with the potential for greater
69 impacts by virtue of the existence of several potentially distinct genotypes which each have a broad range

70 of susceptible fish through tropical and temperate marine and freshwater environments. It is therefore
71 imperative to limit the widespread distribution of ISKNV which can occur through fish trading both of
72 ornamental and food fish, and to identify risk factors that can be addressed to reduce the disease impact
73 where the viruses are endemic. Robust disease control in aquaculture requires knowledge of the
74 pathogens and their hosts and detailed understanding the epidemiology of the disease (FAO, 2019). The
75 objective of this literature review was to consolidate information about ISKNV and identify the knowledge
76 gaps that are limiting improved disease control in aquaculture.

77

78 **1.2 The emergence and geographic distribution of *Infectious spleen and kidney necrosis virus***

79 In the 1990s, multiple disease outbreaks were reported from diverse locations and fish species with
80 common histopathology lesions associated with the presence of viruses consistent with the electron
81 microscopic appearance of iridoviruses (Inouye et al., 1992; He et al., 2000). In 2001, the first whole
82 genome associated with the iridovirus-related mortality of fish was published and assigned as ISKNV (He
83 et al., 2001) which was recognised as the type species *Infectious spleen and kidney necrosis virus* of genus
84 *Megalocyctivirus* by the ICTV in 2005 (Chinchar et al., 2017). The whole genome sequence of RSIV was
85 published in 2002 and TRBIV was in 2010 confirming the taxonomic assignment as a genotype of ISKNV
86 species (Chinchar et al., 2017). Since then, natural outbreaks of ISKNV have been reported in multiple
87 species worldwide including frequent recent first descriptions of ISKNV genotypes in new host species and
88 locations (Table 1.1).

89 The second species in genus *Megalocyctivirus* is *Scale drop disease virus*, SDDV (Chinchar et al., 2017) which
90 has only been reported in farmed barramundi (*Lates clarifier*) in Southeast Asia (de Groof et al., 2015;
91 Nurliyana et al., 2020). Scale drop syndrome (SDS) with an indication of involvement of an infectious
92 agent, was first reported in farmed barramundi in Penang, Malaysia, in 1992 with histopathology and

93 electron microscopic evidence of an iridovirus infection (Gibson-Kueh et al., 2012; de Groof et al., 2015).
94 In 2015, a whole-genome sequence from affected fish from Singapore in 2010 and 2011 revealed that the
95 causative agent was SDDV (de Groof et al., 2015). SDDV infection has been reported in barramundi more
96 frequently in SE Asian countries, such as Indonesia, Thailand, (Senapin et al., 2019; Kayansamruaj et al.,
97 2020), and Malaysia (Nurliyana et al., 2020). Currently, there are two unclassified viruses within the
98 *Megalocytivirus* genus, European chub iridovirus (ECIV) (Halaly et al., 2019) and three spine stickleback
99 iridovirus (TSIV) (Waltzek et al., 2012) from very different fish species and locations. The remainder of this
100 literature review will focus on the ISKNV species and within it the genotypes ISKNV, RSIV and TRBIV.

101 In 1990, the first disease outbreak due to an iridovirus in marine fish was reported in Japan in cultured
102 Red sea bream (*Pagrus major*) with mortality ranging from 20 to 60% (Inouye et al., 1992). Severe
103 anaemia, petechiae of the gills and enlargement of the spleen were observed in the affected fish.
104 Histopathology showed enlarged cells in the spleen, heart, kidney, liver and gill (Inouye et al., 1992). Based
105 on virion morphology under electron microscopy, the causative agent was classified as a member of virus
106 family *Iridoviridae* and designated as RSIV (Inouye et al., 1992). Since then, mortalities of farmed fish due
107 to RSIV infection have been reported in East Asia countries (Table 1.1). From 1991 to 2000, RSIV infection
108 was reported in 31 species of marine fish in Japan (Matsuoka et al., 1996; Kawakami and Nakajima, 2002).
109 In 1998, RSIV was first detected in South Korea in cultured rock bream (*Oplegnathus fasciatus*) (Jeong et
110 al., 2003). Subsequently, RSIV infection has been detected every year until 2018 in multiple species of
111 farmed marine fish in South Korea (Do et al., 2005; Kim et al., 2019). In China, the first report of RSIV
112 infection was in 2002 in Mandarin fish (*Siniperca chuatsi*), which was the first report of RSIV in fresh water
113 fish (Dong et al., 2013b). Subsequent reports in China include spotted knifejaw (*Oplegnathus punctatus*)
114 in 2007 (Dong et al., 2010). Outside East Asia, RSIV infections were reported in South East (SE) Asia in
115 farmed humpback grouper (*Cromileptes altivelis*) in Malaysia in 2006 and 2007 (Razak et al., 2014) and
116 Indonesia (Murwantoko et al., 2018). In Central America, RSIV was reported in 2010, 2014 and 2016 in

117 farmed Florida pompano (*Trachinotus carolinus*) in the Dominican Republic (Lopez-Porras et al., 2018;
118 Koda et al., 2019).

119 The first outbreak of disease associated with the ISKNV genotype was reported in farmed Mandarin fish
120 in 1998 in Nanhai, Guangdong Province in China where mortality reached 100% within 10 days (He et al.,
121 2000). Anorexia, abnormal swimming, light body pigmentation, pale gills and petechial haemorrhages in
122 the operculum were observed in infected fish (He et al., 2000). Hypertrophic cells were observed in spleen,
123 kidney, liver, intestine, and gills which were similar to the first outbreak of RSIV in 1990 in Japan (He et
124 al., 2000). Whole-genome sequence published a year later classified the virus as ISKNV (He et al., 2001).
125 The first confirmed case of ISKNV in ornamental fish was in 2000, in Japan from an African lampeye
126 (*Aplocheilichthys normani*) imported from Indonesia (Sudthongkong et al., 2002). ISKNV has been
127 increasingly reported from ornamental and food fish representing multiple species of marine and
128 freshwater fish in many countries across the world (Table 1.1).

129 In 2004, mortality up to 70% of cultured turbot fry (*Scophthalmus maximus*) was reported in China which
130 represented the first report of the TRBIV genotype (Shi et al., 2004). The infected fish had non-specific
131 clinical sign such as pale gills with local haemorrhages, petechial haemorrhages in fins muscle and skin
132 (Shi et al., 2004). Transmission electron microscopy revealed infection with an iridovirus-like virus and
133 later the whole-genome sequence confirmed it as a genotype of ISKNV (Shi et al., 2010). TRBIV infection
134 was initially reported in flatfish in aquaculture settings in Korea (Kim et al., 2019), China (Shi et al., 2004),
135 and Taiwan (Huang et al., 2011; Tsai et al., 2020). Disease caused by TRBIV has been found in more diverse
136 species including high-mortality disease of Taiwanese farm rearing rock bream (*Oplegnathus fasciatus*)
137 (Huang et al., 2011) and barramundi (Tsai et al., 2020). In ornamental fish, TRBIV was reported from
138 archived samples in 1991 the US (Koda et al., 2018) and Australia (Go et al., 2016) (Table 1.1.).

139 Mortality of fish due to ISKNV infection has now been reported across most regions of the world, from
140 tropical areas (Murwantoko et al., 2018) to temperate regions (Nakajima and Kurita, 2005) (Figure 1.1).
141 ISKNV infection has been reported in temperate regions in North America (Subramaniam et al., 2016),
142 Europe (Jung-Schroers et al., 2016), East Asia (He et al., 2001; Kurita et al., 2002; Shi et al., 2010) and
143 Australia (Lancaster et al., 2003; Rimmer et al., 2015). Regions with tropical climate include Australia
144 (Rimmer et al., 2015), Central America (Lopez-Porras et al., 2018), South America (de Lucca Maganha et
145 al., 2018), Africa (Ramírez-Paredes et al., 2020), South Asia (Girisha et al., 2020) and SE Asia (Mahardika
146 et al., 2008; Sukenda et al., 2020). In SE Asia, where ISKNV has been predominantly reported, it is
147 recognised in numerous species of both freshwater and marine fish in Indonesia (Sudthongkong et al.,
148 2002; Mahardika et al., 2008; Sukenda et al., 2020), Malaysia (Razak et al., 2014; Subramaniam et al.,
149 2014), Vietnam (Dong et al., 2017), and Thailand (Baoprasertkul and Kaenchan, 2019) (Table 1.1). ISKNV
150 and other megalocytiviruses are emerging pathogens with an increasing host and geographical range.
151 Despite overlaps in the type of disease and fish species that are impacted, the genotypes within ISKNV are
152 distinct and require individual consideration. For example, the same host fish species can harbour more
153 than one ISKNV genotype as reported for mandarin fish (Dong et al., 2013b) and grouper (Murwantoko et
154 al., 2018). Additionally, natural recombination between ISKNV and RSIV genomes has been reported in
155 cultured sea bream in Taiwan (Shiu et al., 2017), emphasising the importance of these pathogens in
156 aquatic biosecurity.

157

158 **Table 1. 1.** Reports of disease caused by ISKNV reported in the peer reviewed scientific literature for food fish (FF) and ornamental fish (OF), in
 159 marine (M) and freshwater (F) environments. The table was adapted from (Go, 2015). Note: ND = not done.

Genotype of ISKNV	Year	Location	Cumulative Mortality	Outbreak Water temperature (°C)	Age/size	Host Common Name	Host Scientific Name	Habitat	Fish type	References	Family	Order
ISKNV	2010	USA	ND	24	24 cm	Orbicular batfish	<i>Platax orbicularis</i>	M	OF	Sriwanayos et al., 2013	<i>Ehippiidae</i>	<i>Acanthuriformes</i>
RSIV	2005	Taiwan	30-50	ND	ND	Common ponyfish	<i>Leiognathus equula</i>	M	FF	Wang et al., 2009	<i>Leiognathidae</i>	
RSIV	2004	Japan	40	ND	ND	Japanese seabass	<i>Lateolabrax japonicus</i>	M	FF	Kurita and Nakajima, 2012	<i>Lateolabracidae</i>	<i>Acropomatiformes</i>
RSIV	1996-2000	Japan	ND	ND	ND	Japanese seabass	<i>Lateolabrax japonicus</i>	M	FF	Matsuoka et al., 1996		
RSIV	1999	Korea	ND	ND	ND	Japanese seabass	<i>Lateolabrax japonicus</i>	M	FF	Do et al., 2005		
RSIV	2013, 2015-2017	Korea	ND	ND	Juvenile	Japanese seabass	<i>Lateolabrax japonicus</i>	M	FF	Kim et al., 2019		
RSIV	1999	Korea	ND	ND	ND	Seabass	<i>Lateolabrax sp.</i>	M	FF	Jeong et al., 2003		
ISKNV	2000	Australia	ND	ND	ND	Dwarf gourami	<i>Trichogaster lalius</i>	F	OF	Go and Whittington, 2006	<i>Osphronemidae</i>	<i>Anabantiformes</i>
TRBIV	1988	Australia	ND	ND	3-4 cm	Dwarf gourami	<i>Trichogaster lalius</i>	F	OF	Go et al., 2016		
ISKNV	2018-2019	India	ND	ND	6.5 cm	Gold gourami	<i>Trichopodus trichopterus</i>	F	OF	Girisha et al., 2021		
ISKNV	2015	Brazil	ND	ND	ND	Three spot gourami	<i>Trichogaster trichopterus</i>	F	OF	de Lucca Maganha et al., 2018		
ISKNV	2015	Brazil	ND	ND	ND	Pearl gourami	<i>Trichogaster leeri</i>	F	OF			
ISKNV	2015	Brazil	ND	ND	ND	Paradisefish	<i>Macropodus opercularis</i>	F	OF			

ISKNV	2020	Indonesia	90	ND	300 g	Giant gourami	<i>Osphronemus goramy</i>	F	FF	Sukenda et al., 2020		
ISKNV	2000	Japan	ND	ND	ND	Dwarf gourami	<i>Trichogaster lalius</i>	F	OF	Sudthongkong et al., 2002; 2002a		
ISKNV	2004	Korea	ND	26	4.5 g/ 6 cm	Pearl gourami	<i>Trichogaster leerii</i>	F	OF			
ISKNV	2004	Korea	ND	26	ND	Dwarf gourami	<i>Trichogaster lalius</i>	F	OF	Joon et al., 2008		
ISKNV	2004	Korea	ND	26	ND	Silver gourami	<i>Trichogaster microlepis</i>	F	OF			
ISKNV	2012	Malaysia	ND	ND	2-7 cm	Pearl gourami	<i>Trichogaster leerii</i>	F	OF	Subramaniam et al., 2014		
ISKNV	2000	Singapore	ND	ND	ND	Dwarf gourami	<i>Trichogaster lalius</i>	F	OF	Kurita and Nakajima, 2012		
ISKNV	2016-2018	Thailand	ND	ND	ND	Gourami	<i>Trichogaster sp.</i>	F	OF	Baoprasertkul and Kaenchan, 2019		
ISKNV	2016-2018	Thailand	ND	ND	ND	Siamese fighting fish	<i>Betta splendens</i>	F	OF			
TRBIV	1991	USA	ND	ND	ND	three spot gourami	<i>Trichopodus trichopterus</i>	F	OF	Koda et al., 2018		
RSIV	2010-2016	Dominican Republic	ND	ND	Juvenile	Florida pompano	<i>Trachinotus carolinus</i>	M	FF	Lopez-porras et al., 2018		
RSIV	1996-2000	Japan	ND	ND	Juvenile	Buri-hira hybrid	<i>Seriola quinqueradiata</i> x <i>S. aureovittata</i>	M	FF	Kawakami and Nakajima, 2002		
RSIV	1996-2000	Japan	ND	ND	ND	Greater amberjack	<i>Seriola dumerili</i>	M	FF	Matsuoka et al., 1996; Kawakami and Nakajima, 2002		
RSIV	1996-2000	Japan	ND	ND	Juvenile	hybrid of yellowtail amberjack and Japanese amberjack	<i>Seriola lalandi</i> x <i>S. quinqueradiata</i>	M	FF	Kawakami and Nakajima, 2002		
RSIV	1996-2000	Japan	ND	ND	ND	Japanese amberjack	<i>Seriola quinqueradiata</i>	M	FF			
RSIV	1996-2000	Japan	ND	ND	ND	Japanese jack mackerel	<i>Trachurus japonicus</i>	M	FF			
RSIV	1996-2000	Japan	ND	ND	ND	Snubnose pompano	<i>Trachinotus blochii</i>	M	FF	Matsuoka et al., 1996; Kawakami and Nakajima, 2002		
RSIV	1996-2000	Japan	ND	ND	ND	White trevally	<i>Pseudocaranx dentex</i>	M	FF			
RSIV	1996-2000	Japan	ND	ND	Juvenile	Yellowtail amberjack	<i>Seriola lalandi</i>	M	FF			
RSIV	1996-2000	Japan	ND	ND	ND	Yellowtail amberjack	<i>Seriola lalandi</i>	M	FF			

Carangidae

Carangiformes

RSIV	1996-2000	Japan	ND	ND	Juvenile	Cobia	<i>Rachycentron canadum</i>	M	FF		<i>Rachycentridae</i>
RSIV	1996-2000	Japan	ND	ND	ND	Largescale blackfish	<i>Girella punctata</i>	M	FF	Matsuoka et al., 1996; Kawakami and Nakajima, 2002	<i>Girellidae</i>
RSIV	2007	China	>90	ND	ND	spotted knifejaw	<i>Oplegnathus punctatus</i>	M	FF	Dong et al., 2010	<i>Oplegnathidae</i>
RSIV	1996-2004	Japan	ND	ND	ND	Barred knifejaw	<i>Oplegnathus fasciatus</i>	M	FF	Matsuoka et al., 1996; Kawakami and Nakajima, 2002	
RSIV	1996-2000, 2007	Japan	ND	ND	ND	spotted knifejaw	<i>Oplegnathus punctatus</i>	M	FF		
RSIV	1996-2004	Korea	60	ND	Juvenile	Barred knifejaw	<i>Oplegnathus fasciatus</i>	M	FF	Jung and Oh, 2000; Kim et al., 2002; Jeong et al., 2003; Do et al., 2005; Song et al., 2008	
RSIV	2012-2018	Korea	ND	ND	Juvenile	Barred knifejaw	<i>Oplegnathus fasciatus</i>	M	FF	Kim et al., 2019	
TRBIV	2001-2009	Taiwan	100	ND	ND	Barred knifejaw	<i>Oplegnathus fasciatus</i>	M	FF	Song et al., 2008; Huang et al., 2011	
ISKNV	2003	Australia	90	26-27	4-6 cm	Murray cod	<i>Macullochella peelii</i>	F	FF	Lancaster et al., 2003	<i>Percichthyidae</i>
ISKNV	1998	China	100	28	ND	Mandarin fish	<i>Siniperca chuatsi</i>	F	FF	He et al., 2000;	<i>Sinipercaidae</i>
ISKNV	2012	Japan	100	28	ND	Mandarin fish	<i>Siniperca chuatsi</i>	F	FF	Tanaka et al., 2014	
RSIV	2002-2009	China	100	25-28	13-20 g	Mandarin fish	<i>Siniperca chuatsi</i>	F	FF	Dong et al., 2013	
RSIV	Since 2009	China	100	>25	Juvenile/30-120 g	Leopard mandarin fish	<i>Siniperca scherzeri</i>	F	FF	(Zhang et al., 2020)	
RSIV	2016, 2018	Korea	100	ND	Juvenile	Leopard mandarin fish	<i>Siniperca scherzeri</i>	F	FF	Kim et al., 2019	

ISKNV	2015	Brazil	ND	ND	ND	Red piranha	<i>Pygocentrus nattereri</i>	F	OF	de Lucca Maganha et al., 2018	Serrasalminidae	Characiformes
TRBIV	1986	Australia	ND	ND	3-4 cm	Angelfish	<i>Pterophyllum scalare</i>	F	OF	Go et al., 2016	Cichlidae	Cichliformes
ISKNV	2016	Australia	ND	ND	ND	Angelfish	<i>Pterophyllum scalare</i>	F	OF	Kawato et al., 2020		
TRBIV	1991-1992	Australia	ND	ND	3-4 cm	Oscar	<i>Astronotus ocellatus</i>	F	OF	Go et al., 2016		
ISKNV	2012-2013	Australia	>25	ND	ND	Oscar	<i>Astronotus ocellatus</i>	F	OF	Nolan et al 2015		
ISKNV	2014	Germany	10-100	ND	1.4g/3 cm	Angelfish	<i>Pterophyllum</i> spp.	F	OF	Jung-Schroers et al., 2016		
ISKNV	2018	Ghana	50-70	ND	20-650 g	Nile tilapia	<i>Oreochromis niloticus</i>	F	FF	Ramírez-Paredes et al., 2020		
ISKNV	2018-2019	India	ND	ND	10 cm	Mango oscar	<i>Astronotus ocellatus</i>	F	OF			
ISKNV	2018-2019	India	ND	ND	4.5 cm	Ram cichlid	<i>Mikrogeophagus ramirezi</i>	F	OF	Girisha et al., 2021		
ISKNV	2018-2019	India	ND	ND	5.5 cm	Angelfish	<i>Pterophyllum scalare</i>	F	OF			
ISKNV	2012	Malaysia	ND	ND	2-7 cm	Ram cichlid	<i>Mikrogeophagus ramirezi</i>	F	OF	Subramaniam et al., 2014		
ISKNV	2016-2018	Thailand	ND	ND	ND	Cichlid	<i>Cichlasoma</i> sp.	F	OF			
ISKNV	2016-2018	Thailand	ND	ND	ND	Discus	<i>Symphysodon</i> sp.	F	OF	Baoprasertkul and Kaenchan, 2019		
ISKNV	2016-2018	Thailand	ND	ND	ND	Oscar	<i>Astronotus ocellatus</i>	F	OF			
ISKNV	2016	Thailand	ND	ND	200-500 g	Nile tilapia	<i>Oreochromis niloticus</i>	F	FF	Suebsing et al., 2016		
TRBIV	1991	USA	ND	ND	ND	keyhole cichlid	<i>Cleithracara maronii</i>	F	OF	Koda et al., 2018		
ISKNV	2012	USA	50-75	15	3.6-7.5 cm	Nile tilapia	<i>Oreochromis niloticus</i>	F	FF	Subramaniam et al., 2016		
TRBIV	1991	USA	ND	ND	ND	Oscar	<i>Astronotus ocellatus</i>	F	OF	Koda et al., 2018		
ISKNV	2018-2019	India	ND	ND	8.5 cm	Goldfish	<i>Carassius auratus</i>	F	OF	Girisha et al., 2021	Cyprinidae	Cypriniformes
ISKNV	2015	Brazil	ND	ND	ND	Goldfish	<i>Carassius auratus</i>	F	OF	de Lucca Maganha et al., 2018		

ISKNV	2018-2019	India	ND	ND	3.5 cm	Koi	<i>Cyprinus carpio</i>	F	OF	Girisha et al., 2021		
ISKNV	2015	Brazil	ND	ND	ND	Common carp	<i>Cyprinus carpio</i>	F	OF	de Lucca Maganha et al., 2018		
ISKNV	2018-2019	India	ND	ND	3.5 cm	Cherry barb	<i>Puntius titteye</i>	F	OF	Girisha et al., 2021		
ISKNV	2012	Malaysia	ND	ND	2-7 cm	Zebra fish	<i>Danio rerio</i>	F	OF	Subramaniam et al., 2014	Danioidea	
ISKNV	2012-2013	Australia	>25	ND	ND	Blue lyretail	<i>Fundulopanchax gardneri</i>	F	OF	Nolan et al 2015	Nothobranchiidae	
ISKNV	2012-2013	Australia	>25	ND	ND	Common platy	<i>Xiphophorus maculatus</i>	F	OF	Nolan et al 2015	Poeciliidae	Cyprinodontiformes
ISKNV	2012-2013	Australia	>25	ND	ND	Green swordtail	<i>Xiphophorus hellerii</i>	F	OF			
ISKNV	2011	Australia	ND	ND	ND	Platy	<i>Xiphophorus maculatus</i>	F	OF	Rimmer et al., 2015		
ISKNV	2012-2013	Australia	>25	ND	ND	Sailfin molly	<i>Poecilia latipinna</i>	F	OF	Nolan et al 2015		
ISKNV	2018-2019	India	ND	ND	5 cm	White molly	<i>Poecilia sphenops</i>	F	OF			
ISKNV	2018-2019	India	ND	ND	3 cm	White tail guppy	<i>Poecilia reticulata</i>	F	OF	Girisha et al., 2021		
ISKNV	2018-2019	India	ND	ND	5 cm	Black molly	<i>Poecilia sphenops</i>	F	OF			
ISKNV	2015	Brazil	ND	ND	ND	White tail guppy	<i>Poecilia reticulata</i>	F	OF	de Lucca Maganha et al., 2018		
ISKNV	2012	Malaysia	ND	ND	2-7 cm	Common platy	<i>Xiphophorus maculatus</i>	F	OF	Subramaniam et al., 2014		
ISKNV	2012	Malaysia	ND	ND	2-7 cm	Sword tail	<i>Xiphophorus helleri</i>	F	OF			
ISKNV	2016-2018	Thailand	ND	ND	ND	Green swordtail	<i>Xiphophorus hellerii</i>	F	OF			
ISKNV	2016-2018	Thailand	ND	ND	ND	Platy	<i>Xiphophorus maculatus</i>	F	OF	Baoprasertkul and Kaenchan, 2019		
ISKNV	2016-2018	Thailand	ND	ND	ND	Platy	<i>Xiphophorus variatus</i>	F	OF			
ISKNV	2016-2018	Thailand	ND	ND	ND	Guppy	<i>Poecilia reticulata</i>	F	OF			

ISKNV	2016-2018	Thailand	ND	ND	ND	Sailfin molly	<i>Poecilia velifera</i>	F	OF			
ISKNV	1998	Japan	ND	ND	ND	African lampeye	<i>Aplocheilichthys normani</i>	F	FF	Sudthongkong et al., 2002a	Proctopodidae	
RSIV	2009-2010	Taiwan	40	ND	24	Marble goby	<i>Oxyeleotris marmoratus</i>	F	FF	Chen et al. 2013; Huang et al. 2011	Butidae	Gobiiformes
ISKNV	2009	Taiwan	85	ND	ND	Marble goby	<i>Oxyeleotris marmoratus</i>	F	FF	Wang et al., 2011		
ISKNV	2003-2004	USA	100	ND	ND	Banggai cardinalfish	<i>Pterapogon kauderni</i>	M	OF	Weber et al 2009	Apogonidae	Kurtiformes
RSIV	2013, 2017	Korea	ND	ND	Juvenile	So-iuy mullet	<i>Planiliza haematocheila</i>	M	FF	Kim et al., 2019	Mugilidae	Mugiliformes
ISKNV	1999/2000	Singapore	10-80	ND	Juvenile/10-20 g	Flathead grey mullet	<i>Mugil cephalus</i>	M	FF	Gibson-Kueh et al., 2004		
RSIV	1996-2000	Japan	ND	ND	ND	Chicken grunt	<i>Parapristipoma trilineatum</i>	M	FF	Matsuoka et al., 1996; Kawakami and Nakajima, 2002	Haemulidae	Perciformes
RSIV	1996-2000	Japan	ND	ND	Juvenile	Crescent sweetlips	<i>Plectorhynchus cinctus</i>	M	FF	Kawakami and Nakajima, 2002		
RSIV	2018	India	ND	ND	Juvenile	Barramundi	<i>Lates calcarifer</i>	M	FF	Puneeth et al, 2020	Latidae	
ISKNV	2000	Malaysia	50	ND	ND	Barramundi	<i>Lates calcarifer</i>	M	FF	Kurita and Nakajima, 2012		
ISKNV	2001-2009	Taiwan	ND	ND	5-200	Barramundi	<i>Lates calcarifer</i>	M	FF	Huang et al., 2011		
TRBIV	2017	Taiwan	90	ND	5-8 cm	Barramundi	<i>Lates calcarifer</i>	M	FF	Tsai and Huang, 2020		
RSIV	2007, 2008	Taiwan	30-50	ND	50-500 g	Barramundi	<i>Lates calcarifer</i>	M	FF	Wang et al., 2009		

ISKNV	2017	Indonesia	ND	29-30	5-8 cm/5.2 g	Barramundi	<i>Lates calcarifer</i>	M	FF	(Thanasaksiri et al., 2021)	
ISKNV	2012-2014	Vietnam	40-71	ND	3-35 g	Barramundi	<i>Lates calcarifer</i>	M	FF	Dong et al., 2017	
RSIV	2005	Taiwan	30-50	ND	20-30 g	Common ponyfish	<i>Leiognathus equulus</i>	M	FF	Wang et al., 2009	Leiognathidae
RSIV	1996-2000	Japan	ND	ND	Juvenile	Chinese emperor	<i>Lethrinus haematopterus</i>	M	FF	Kawakami and Nakajima, 2002	Lethrinidae
RSIV	2002	Taiwan	ND	ND	ND	Crimson snapper	<i>Lutjanus erythropterus</i>	M	FF	Huang et al., 2011	Lutjanidae
RSIV	1999-2001	China	75	27-30	10-14 cm	Large yellow croaker	<i>Larimichthys crocea</i>	M	FF	Chen et al., 2003	Sciaenidae
ISKNV	1996-2001	China	70	25-30	15-17 cm	Red drum	<i>Sciaenops ocellata</i>	M	FF	Weng et al., 2002	Sciaenidae
RSIV	2000-2002	Korea	ND	ND	Juvenile	Korean rockfish	<i>Sebastes schlegeli</i>	M	FF	Kim et al., 2002; Do et al., 2005	Sebastidae
ISKNV	2004	China	60	ND	ND	Orange-spotted grouper	<i>Epinephelus coioides</i>	M	FF	Kurita and Nakajima, 2012	Serranidae
RSIV	2002	China	60	ND	ND	Orange-spotted grouper	<i>Epinephelus coioides</i>	M	FF	Kurita and Nakajima, 2012	
RSIV	1996-2000	China	90	ND	Juvenile/ 3 cm	Orange-spotted grouper	<i>Epinephelus coioides</i>	M	FF	Ma et al., 2012	
ISKNV	2010	Indonesia	ND	ND	Juvenile	Brown-marbled grouper	<i>Epinephelus fuscoguttatus</i>	M	FF	Murwantoko et al., 2018	
RSIV/ ISKNV	2001	Indonesia	70	ND	Juvenile/ 3-4 cm	Coral grouper	<i>Epinephelus corallicola</i>	M	FF	Johnny and des Roza, 2009	

RSIV	2010	Indonesia	ND	ND	Juvenile	Humpback grouper	<i>Cromileptes altivelis</i>	M	FF	Murwantoko et al., 2018
RSIV	2015	Indonesia	ND	ND	8-18 cm	Orange-spotted grouper	<i>Epinephelus coioides</i>	M	FF	Sah Putra et al., 2020
ISKNV	2016	Indonesia	90	28-31	14-32 cm	Hybrid grouper	<i>E. fuscoguttatus</i> ♀ × <i>E. lanceolatus</i> ♂	M	FF	Fusianto et al., 2021
ISKNV	2015	Indonesia	ND	ND	8 cm	Hybrid grouper	<i>E. fuscoguttatus</i> ♀ × <i>E. lanceolatus</i> ♂	M	FF	Sah Putra et al., 2020
ISKNV	2016	Indonesia	90	28-31	17-21cm	Hybrid grouper	<i>E. fuscoguttatus</i> ♀ × <i>E. polyphkadion</i> ♂	M	FF	Fusianto et al., 2021
ISKNV	2015	Indonesia	ND	ND	7 cm	Hybrid grouper	<i>E. fuscoguttatus</i> ♀ × <i>E. polyphkadion</i> ♂	M	FF	Sah Putra et al., 2020
RSIV	1996-2000	Indonesia	80	ND	Juvenile	Orange-spotted grouper	<i>Epinephelus coioides</i>	M	FF	Murwantoko et al., 2009
RSIV	1996-2000	Japan	ND	ND	Juvenile	Banded grouper	<i>Epinephelus awoara</i>	M	FF	Kawakami and Nakajima, 2002
RSIV	1996-2000	Japan	ND	ND	Juvenile	Kelp grouper	<i>Epinephelus moara</i>	M	FF	Kawakami and Nakajima, 2002
RSIV	1996-2000	Japan	ND	ND	Juvenile	Malabar grouper	<i>Epinephelus malabaricus</i>	M	FF	Kawakami and Nakajima, 2002
RSIV	1996-2000	Japan	ND	ND	Juvenile	Orange-spotted grouper	<i>Epinephelus coioides</i>	M	FF	Kawakami and Nakajima, 2002
RSIV	1996-2000	Japan	ND	ND	Juvenile	Red spotted grouper	<i>Epinephelus akaara</i>	M	FF	Kawakami and Nakajima, 2002
RSIV	1996-2000	Japan	ND	ND	Juvenile	Sevenband grouper	<i>Epinephelus septemfasciatus</i>	M	FF	Kawakami and Nakajima, 2002
ISKNV	2006, 2007	Malaysia	ND	28-33	Adult/ 25-30 cm	Brown-marbled grouper	<i>Epinephelus fuscoguttatus</i>	M	FF	Razak et al., 2014
ISKNV	2006, 2007	Malaysia	ND	28-35	Adult/ 25-30 cm	Giant grouper	<i>Epinephelus lanceolatus</i>	M	FF	Razak et al., 2014
ISKNV	2006, 2007	Malaysia	ND	28-32	Adult/ 25-30 cm	Humpback grouper	<i>Cromileptes altivelis</i>	M	FF	Razak et al., 2014
ISKNV	2006, 2007	Malaysia	ND	28-34	Adult/ 25-30 cm	Hybrid grouper	<i>E. fuscoguttatus</i> × <i>E. lanceolatus</i>	M	FF	Razak et al., 2014
ISKNV	2001-2009	Malaysia	ND	28-32	Adult/ 25-30 cm	Orange-spotted grouper	<i>Epinephelus coioides</i>	M	FF	Razak et al., 2014
ISKNV	2000	Philippines	ND	ND	ND	Orange-spotted grouper	<i>Epinephelus coioides</i>	M	FF	Kurita and Nakajima, 2012

RSIV	1999/2000	Singapore	100	ND	Juvenile/10-20 g	Brown-marbled grouper	<i>Epinephelus fuscoguttatus</i>	M	FF	Gibson-Kueh et al., 2004		
RSIV	2002	Singapore	100		Juvenile	Brown-marbled grouper	<i>Epinephelus fuscoguttatus</i>	M	FF	Kurita and Nakajima, 2012		
ISKNV	2005, 2007	Taiwan	ND	ND	600 g- 2 kg	Giant grouper	<i>Epinephelus lanceolatus</i>	M	FF	Wang et al., 2009		
ISKNV	≤2000	Taiwan	up to 100	25-35	Juvenile	Hybrid grouper	<i>E. malabaricus x E. akaara</i>	M	FF	Chao et al., 2002		
ISKNV	2001-2009	Taiwan	ND	ND	Juvenile/2.2-11.6 g	Orange-spotted grouper	<i>Epinephelus coioides</i>	M	FF	Huang et al., 2011		
RSIV	1996-2000	Japan	ND	ND	ND	Black sea bream	<i>Acanthopagrus schlegeli</i>	M	FF	Matsuoka et al., 1996; Kawakami and Nakajima, 2002; Jeong et al., 2003	Sparidae	
RSIV	1990	Japan	20-60	ND	ND	Red sea bream	<i>Pagrus major</i>	M	FF	Inouye et al., 1992		
RSIV	1996-2000	Japan	20-60	ND	Juvenile	Red sea bream	<i>Pagrus major</i>	M	FF	Matsuoka et al., 1996; Kawakami and Nakajima, 2002; Do et al., 2005		
RSIV	1996-2000	Japan	ND	ND	Juvenile	Yellowback seabream	<i>Dentex tumifrons</i>	M	FF	Matsuoka et al., 1996; Kawakami and Nakajima, 2002		
RSIV	2004	Japan	ND	ND	ND	Yellowfin sea bream	<i>Acanthopagrus latus</i>	M	FF	Kurita and Nakajima, 2012		
RSIV	2014	Korea	ND	ND	Juvenile	Red sea bream	<i>Pagrus major</i>	M	FF	Kim et al., 2019		
RSIV	Since 1993	Taiwan	50-90	Summer	7–10 cm	Red sea bream	<i>Pagrus major</i>	M	FF	Wang et al., 2003		
RSIV	Since 1993	Taiwan	30-50	Summer	7–10 cm	Red sea bream	<i>Pagrus major</i>	M	FF	Wang et al., 2009		
RSIV	2005	Taiwan	30-50	ND	10-15 g	Yellowback seabream	<i>Dentex tumifrons</i>	M	FF	Wang et al., 2009		
TRBIV	2003	China	80	ND	Juvenile	Bastard halibut	<i>Paralichthys olivaceus</i>	M	FF	Do et al., 2005	Paralichthyidae	Pleuronectiformes
RSIV	1995-2000	Japan	ND	ND	ND	Bastard halibut	<i>Paralichthys olivaceus</i>	M	FF	Kawakami and Nakajima, 2002		
TRBIV	2014	Korea	ND	ND	Juvenile	Bastard halibut	<i>Paralichthys olivaceus</i>	M	FF	Kim et al., 2019		
ISKNV	2002	Korea	60-80	ND	Juvenile	Bastard halibut	<i>Paralichthys olivaceus</i>	M	FF	Wang et al., 2007		
ISKNV	2005	Taiwan	60-80	ND	Juvenile	Bastard halibut	<i>Paralichthys olivaceus</i>	M	FF	Huang et al., 2011		
RSIV	2000	Japan	ND	ND	ND	Spotted halibut	<i>Verasper variegatus</i>	M	FF	Kawakami and Nakajima, 2002	eu	

TRBIV	2009	Korea	60	ND	Juvenile/ 22 g	Starry flounder	<i>Platichthys stellatus</i>	M	FF	Won et al., 2013		
TRBIV	2002, 2005, 2006	China	40	ND	Juvenile/ 50 g	Turbot	<i>Scophthalmus maximus</i>	M	FF	Shi et al., 2004; Wu et al., 2009; Zhang et al., 2009	Scophthamini	
TRBIV	2003	Korea	50-70	ND	Juvenile	Turbot	<i>Scophthalmus maximus</i>	M	FF	Kim et al., 2005		
RSIV	1996- 2000	Japan	ND	ND	ND	Atlantic bluefin tuna	<i>Thunnus thynnus</i>	M	FF	Matsuoka et al., 1996; Kawakami and Nakajima, 2002	Scombridae	Scombriformes
RSIV	1996- 2000	Japan	ND	ND	Juvenile	Chub mackerel	<i>Scomber japonicus</i>	M	FF	Kawakami and Nakajima, 2002		
RSIV	1996- 2000	Japan	ND	ND	Juvenile	Japanese Spanish mackerel	<i>Scomberomorus niphonius</i>	M	FF	Kawakami and Nakajima, 2002		
RSIV	1998- 2002	Korea	ND	ND	Juvenile	Korean rockfish	<i>Sebastes schlegelii</i>	M	FF	Kim et al., 2002	Sebastidae	
RSIV	2017	Korea	ND	ND	Juvenile	Threadsail filefish	<i>Stephanolepis cirrhifer</i>	M	FF	Kim et al., 2019	Monacanthidae	Tetraodontiformes
RSIV	1996- 2000	Japan	ND	ND	Juvenile	Japanese pufferfish	<i>Takifugu rubripes</i>	M	FF	Matsuoka et al., 1996; Kawakami and Nakajima, 2002	Tetraodontidae	

161 **1.3 Morphology, structure, and genomic characteristics of *Infectious spleen and kidney necrosis***
162 ***virus***

163 Like other members of the family *Iridoviridae*, ISKNV has an icosahedral capsid structure with a size
164 ranging from 115 to 162 nm. The capsid contains a large double-stranded DNA genome (He et al., 2000;
165 Go et al., 2016; Koda et al., 2018) (Figure 1.2). The virion structure includes an internal lipid membrane
166 and outer envelope (Williams et al., 2005). These viral structures played an important role in infection of
167 a host through the involvement in virus entry to cells (Williams et al., 2005; Kurita and Nakajima, 2012).
168 However, unlike most other enveloped viruses, the envelope was not essential for cell entry and naked
169 virions can also be infectious (Williams et al., 2005; Shuang et al., 2013). Transmission electron microscopy
170 identified only non-enveloped virions from three spot gourami iridovirus (TSGIV, TRBIV genotype)
171 cultured in bluegill fry (BF-2) cell line (Koda et al., 2018). Enveloped virions were observed in Nile tilapia
172 (*Oreochromis niloticus*) infected with ISKNV in Ghana (Ramírez-Paredes et al., 2020) and in cultured rock
173 bream infected with RSIV in China in 2009 (Li et al., 2011).

174 The double-stranded DNA genome of ISKNV is highly methylated at cytosine residues and is circularly
175 permuted (He et al., 2000; Chinchar et al., 2017; Shiu et al., 2017). The genome is 111-112 kilobase pairs
176 with a G+C content of 53–55% and 119-132 open reading frames (ORFs) (He et al., 2000; Shiu et al., 2017;
177 Kawato et al., 2020). Phylogenetic analysis based on the 26 Iridovirus core genes described by Eaton et al.
178 (2007) distinguished ISKNV from other members of family *Iridoviridae* and provided separation among
179 ISKNV genotypes (Koda et al., 2018) which is supported using whole-genome sequences as the input for
180 the same analysis (Figure 1.3).

181 The replication of iridoviruses comprises both nuclear and cytoplasmic stages that have been investigated
182 primarily through the study of *Frog virus 3* (FV3), the type species of the genus *Ranavirus* (Williams et al.,
183 2005; Chinchar et al., 2009). The replication strategy of ISKNV is assumed to be similar to FV3 but different

184 in some characteristics as the difference in the number of predicted open reading frames (ORFs) on FV3
185 (97 ORFs) and ISKNV (115-122 ORFs) (Eaton et al., 2007). The exact mechanism of ISKNV cell entry is
186 unknown. Unlike FV3, ISKNV does not employ envelope proteins to activate receptor-mediated
187 endocytosis for cellular entry (He et al., 2000; Gibson-Kueh et al., 2003; Sriwanayos et al., 2013; Koda et
188 al., 2018). *In vitro* studies with the ISKNV genotype suggested that ISKNV entered cells via caveola-
189 dependent endocytosis (Guo et al., 2012; Jia et al., 2013). Inside the host cell, viral DNA processing
190 including uncoating and transport to the nucleus occurs by poorly understood mechanisms. The viral
191 assembly site of ISKNV is in the cytoplasm of the host cell (Mahardika et al., 2009), similar to *Singapore*
192 *grouper iridovirus* (SGIV), a *Ranavirus*, which formed cytoplasmic viral assembly sites in infected cells 1-2
193 hours post-infection (Liu et al., 2016). At the late stage of infection, the assembly site expanded to contain
194 complete viral particles and pushed the nucleus to the side of the cell (Liu et al., 2016; Kawato et al., 2020).
195 Mature virions are observed with full and partial envelope and no envelope (Kawato et al., 2020) and
196 often form paracrystalline arrays (Mahardika et al., 2009; Koda et al., 2018) (Figure 1.2). The specific exit
197 mechanisms of ISKNV from the cell is unknown. The ranaviruses FV3 and SGIV can exit by the formation
198 of budding vacuoles for enveloped virions and cell lysis for non-enveloped virions (Williams et al., 2005;
199 Liu et al., 2016).

200

201 **1.4 Taxonomy and phylogeny of *Infectious spleen and kidney necrosis virus***

202 The genus *Megalocyttivirus* is classified within the subfamily *Alphairidovirinae*, family *Iridoviridae*
203 (Chinchar et al., 2017). The subfamily has ectothermic vertebrate hosts (bony fish, amphibians, and
204 reptiles) and is distinguished from the other subfamily, *Betairidovirinae*, with invertebrate (insects and
205 crustaceans) hosts (Chinchar et al., 2017). Subfamily *Alphairidovirinae* also includes the genera
206 *Lymphocystivirus* and *Ranavirus* which are distinguished by the level of nucleotide/amino acid sequence

207 identity, host range, G+C content, phylogenetic relatedness, genome co-linearity, disease manifestations
208 and antigenicity (Chinchar et al., 2017). Viruses within a genus generally share greater than 50% sequence
209 identity for the 26 iridovirus core genes (Chinchar et al., 2011). Viruses within a genus with sequence
210 identity of more than 95% are considered genotypes of the same virus species. Based on these criteria
211 MCV includes two currently recognised species, SDDV and ISKNV (Chinchar et al., 2017) (Figure 1.3).

212 Considerable diversity within the ISKNV species is reflected by division into three genotypes, each with 2
213 clades based on the sequence of the major capsid protein (MCP) and ATPase genes: RSIV genotype, ISKNV
214 genotype and TRBIV genotype (Shi et al., 2010; Go et al., 2016). These classifications are supported by
215 phylogenetic analysis of an increasing number of whole genomes (Figure 1.3). Based on the MCP gene,
216 RSIV is divided into the Japan subgroup (Clade 1) and Korea and China subgroup (Clade 2) (Do et al., 2005;
217 Koda et al., 2019). A report of RSIV Clade 1 in farmed Florida pompano in the Dominican Republic showed
218 that geographic boundaries of RSIV genotype is no longer applicable (Lopez-Porras et al., 2018). There are
219 also 2 distinct clades based on the genomic sequence for the ISKNV genotype, although no features
220 regarding the host species or location distinguish Clade 1 and 2 (Figure 1.3). The two Clades of TRBIV are
221 differentiated based on the genomic sequences and no clear boundaries separate the two Clades
222 regardless the Clade 1 identified in flatfishes from East Asia (Shi et al., 2010) and Clade 2 identified in
223 ornamental fish imported to the US (Koda et al., 2018) and Australia (Go et al., 2016).

224 There has been a convention to name isolates of ISKNV based on the host species of the origin or the
225 geographical region which has led to a confusing array of names for the same virus genotypes based on
226 their broad host and geographical range (Chinchar et al., 2017). Firstly, confusion can arise when nearly
227 identical viruses are assigned different name such as Angelfish iridovirus (Kawato et al., 2020) which is
228 99.9% similarity over the complete genome to ISKNV (He et al., 2001). Second, the same name has been
229 assigned to different MCVs. For example, isolates of ISKNV XQ, XT, HT, and Hzh from Mandarin fish are
230 belong to RSIV (Fu et al., 2011). Moreover, RBIV (Red bream iridovirus)-KOR-GJ from Rock bream belongs

231 to RSIV while RBIV-KOR-CS belongs to TRBIV (Song et al., 2008). A numbering system for the genotype
232 classification offers the most practical approach to ISKNV nomenclature which overcomes the confusion
233 of a genotype name overlapping with the species i.e., Genotypes I (RSIV), II (ISKNV) and III (TRBIV) (Kurita
234 and Nakajima, 2012). Chinchar et al. (2020) has suggested a standard nomenclature for ISKNV isolates
235 which describe the identity of the viral species, followed by parentheses that contain the host species
236 from which the virus is isolated, the location of isolation, the isolate number, and the year of isolation and
237 Clade. For example, from Figure 1.3, RBIV-C1 (Acc number KC244182) can be named as ISKNV Genotype
238 I, Red bream, Japan, 2009, Clade 2.

239

240

241 **Figure 1. 1.** Illustration of the global distribution of the three genotypes of ISKNV classified according to
 242 the ATPase and or MCP gene sequences. Only one per categories (Genotype, food/ornamental, clade) per
 243 country included. Map generated using Mapbox studio®. Shapes represent each genotype (circle: ISKNV,
 244 square: RSIV, and triangle: TRBIV). Colours represent ornamental fish (red) and food fish (green), and black
 245 border on the shapes represent Clade 1 while Clade 2 is borderless.

246

247 **Figure 1. 2.** (A) Transmission electron photomicrograph of a grunt fin cell (cultured in vitro) infected with
248 three spot gourami iridovirus (TSGIV) showing a paracrystalline array of virus particles. Scale bar = 1 μ m.
249 (B) Hexagonal nucleocapsids TSGIV virions with dense cores, medium-density cores, and lucent cores.
250 Scale bar = 200 nm. Use with permission from Koda et al. (2018).

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258 1.5 Clinical signs and gross pathology

259 Disease caused by ISKNV infection presents with general clinical signs including anorexia, discolouration
260 (darker or lighter), and lack of responsiveness to stimuli e.g. netting (Subramaniam et al., 2016). External
261 lesions include petechial haemorrhages on the surface of the body particularly the operculum, mandible,
262 orbit around the eye, base of dorsal and ventral fins, caudal fin and abdomen were observed in Mandarin
263 fish (He et al., 2002) and zebrafish (*Danio rerio*) (Xu et al., 2008). Internal lesions include enlargement of
264 the posterior and anterior kidneys and spleen, and discolouration of the heart and liver has been reported
265 (He et al., 2002; Mahardika et al., 2008; Subramaniam et al., 2016). ISKNV infection with the absence of
266 the clinical signs and pathology (subclinical infection) has been reported in adult Nile tilapia (Suebsing *et*
267 *al.*, 2016), spotted green pufferfish (*Tetraodon nigroviridis*) (Xu et al., 2008), grass carp
268 (*Ctenopharyngodon idella*) (He et al., 2002), groupers (*Epinephelus* spp.) (Sah Putra et al., 2020) and
269 numerous ornamental fish imported to Australia (Rimmer et al., 2015), Germany (Jung-Schroers et al.,
270 2016), the US (Koda et al., 2018), Japan (Sudthongkong et al., 2002) and Korea (Do et al., 2005). Due to
271 the non-specific clinical signs displayed by infected fish and the potential for subclinical infection, the
272 diagnostic process requires a combination of histopathology and procedures to detect the virus.

273 1.6 Histopathology

274 Infection with each genotype of ISKNV results in the characteristic appearance of inclusion body-bearing
275 cells (IBC) referred to also as megalocytes (Nakajima and Kurita, 2005) (Figure 1.4). When examined with
276 hematoxylin and eosin-stained histopathology slides, IBCs are hypertrophied cells containing large foamy
277 or granular basophilic inclusions that expand the cytoplasm and dislocate the nucleus (Mahardika et al.,
278 2008; Go and Whittington, 2019; Kawato et al., 2020). IBCs were frequently observed in hematopoietic
279 organs, i.e., spleen and kidney, and in the heart (Nakajima and Kurita, 2005). Systemic distribution of IBCs
280 is possible with reports in the gill connective tissue in Murray cod (*Maccullochella peelii*) (Lancaster et al.,

281 2003), submucosa and tunica propria of the stomach and intestine of African lampeye, dwarf gourami
282 (*Trichogaster lalius*) (Sudthongkong et al., 2002) and oscar (*Astronotus ocellatus*) (Koda et al., 2018), and
283 the cranial connective tissue of mandarin fish (He et al., 2000). In some cases, IBC were not observed even
284 with the high viral load during a mass mortality event (Dong et al., 2017) or from experimental infections
285 (Rimmer et al., 2017; Go and Whittington, 2019).

286

287 **1.7 Epidemiology of *Infectious spleen and kidney necrosis virus***

288 **1.7.1 Pathogen risk factors**

289 Initially, the three genotypes of ISKNV were known for having certain fish hosts separated on marine and
290 freshwater environments (Kurita and Nakajima, 2012). This understanding is no longer appropriate as
291 there are increasing reports of ISKNV infections for each genotype across a broad range of hosts and
292 aquatic environments (Table 1.1, Figure 1.1). Certain fish species have been reported susceptible to
293 multiple ISKNV genotypes. ISKNV genotype RSIV and ISKNV have been reported in Mandarin fish (Dong et
294 al., 2013b) and groupers (Murwantoko et al., 2018). Another genotype, TRBIV, has been reported in
295 barramundi in Taiwan (Tsai et al., 2020) and ornamental fishes (Go et al., 2016; Koda et al., 2018) while
296 previously only reported in farmed turbot. The report of TRBIV infection in barramundi, an important
297 aquaculture species in Australia and SE Asia, makes this species susceptible to all genotypes of ISKNV after
298 ISKNV and RSIV infection also been reported (Dong et al., 2017). In terms of virulence, all genotypes exhibit
299 the similar clinical signs and cumulative mortality (Table 1.1). All ISKNV genotypes should be considered
300 as an individual pathogen including diagnostic and preventive measures. The current standard diagnostic
301 method published by OIE (2019b) which includes the ISKNV and RSIV genotypes should also include TRBIV
302 as a target for diagnosis and surveillance and a method to distinguish the genotypes.

313 **Figure 1. 3.** Phylogenetic tree of 26 MCV whole genome sequences and information table for the sequences showing the relationship between
 314 the three genotypes of ISKNV, each with two clades. Whole genomes reported in GenBank were aligned using MAFFT with fftns option (Kato
 315 and Standley, 2013) to produce an alignment with 53,869 nucleotide sites. Any nucleotide site containing gaps were removed (complete
 316 deletion). Phylogenetic analysis was performed using IQ-Tree with general time reversible model with unequal rates (6 categories) and unequal

317 base freq (Nguyen et al., 2015). The tree was evaluated using ultrafast bootstrap for 1000 iterations after applying best model finder using
318 ModelFinder (Kalyaanamoorthy et al., 2017).

319 References for the isolates are: 1. Lü et al. (2005), 2. Wen and Hong (2016), 3. Kawato et al. (2020), 4. Matsuyama et al., 2017*, 5. Zhang et al.
320 (2013), 6. Puneeth et al. (2021), 7. Do et al. (2004), 8. Wang et al. (2020)*, 9. Kurita et al. (2002), 10. Koda et al. (2019), 11. Ao and Chen (2006),
321 12. Koda et al. (2020)*, 13. Shiu et al. (2017), 14. Fusianto et al. (2021), 15. He et al. (2001), 16. Koda et al. (2018), 17. Shi et al. (2010),
322 18. Kayansamruaj et al. (2020), 19. de Groof et al. (2015). *: Direct submission to NCBI.

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Figure 1. 4. Megalocytic inclusion bearing cells in Hybrid grouper displaying clinical signs and infection with ISKNV (a) anterior kidney with multiple stages of megalocytes (white arrows: early stage, black arrows: late stage of megalocytes) associated with necrosis. (b) normal anterior kidney of grouper without clinical signs. Scale bars = 50 µm.

338 1.7.2 Host risk factors

339 Analysis of natural outbreaks of ISKNV showed that food fishes from family *Serranidae* were most
340 frequently affected (Table 1.1). For ornamental fish, members of family *Poeciliidae* were most frequently
341 reported, which might indicate differential susceptibility to infection and disease (Table 1.1). One member
342 of family *Serranidae* which is severely affected by ISKNV is groupers (*Epinephelus* spp.) with mortality up
343 to 100% (Chao et al., 2002). Several ISKNV outbreaks have been reported in grouper aquaculture in
344 Indonesia with significant epidemics in 2016 creating mortality up to 90% in grow out farms in Bali
345 (Fusianto et al., 2021).

346 Life stage of the fish has been reported as one of the risk factors of increased severity of disease caused
347 by ISKNV in aquaculture. Mortality due to ISKNV infection has been mostly reported in juvenile fish (He et
348 al., 2001; Kurita et al., 2002; Shi et al., 2010; Subramaniam et al., 2016; Koda et al., 2019; Sukenda et al.,
349 2020) (Table 1.1). ISKNV related mortality has been reported in juvenile Nile tilapia (Subramaniam et al.,
350 2016), giant gourami (Sukenda et al., 2020), mandarin fish (He et al., 2001), and Angelfish (*Pterophyllum*
351 *scalare*) (Jung-Schroers et al., 2016). There is a limited number of reports regarding natural infection of
352 ISKNV in adult fish. ISKNV infection on adult Nile tilapia was reported to be subclinical compared to severe
353 clinical signs in juveniles (Suebsing et al., 2016). Decreasing severity with age was also demonstrated by
354 experimental infection of barramundi (Thanasaksiri et al., 2021). Mortality up to 90% on adult fish was
355 reported on market-size hybrid grouper in Indonesia (Fusianto et al., 2021). Research on how life stages
356 impact the susceptibility on ISKNV infection is an area for continued observation as confounding factors
357 related to the management of fish at different ages may impact these observations.

358 Although subclinical infections have been identified (Wang et al., 2007), to date, there have been no
359 reports of ISKNV mortality in wild fish. High density aquaculture and chemical parasite treatments
360 including hydrogen peroxide and peracetic acid, increase stress and suppress the immune system of the

361 fish (Lieke et al., 2020). Intensive aquaculture setting also increase the likelihood of horizontal viral
362 transmission and the exposure dose to pathogens in general (Kennedy et al., 2016). Each of these
363 situations can align to increase mortality (Lieke et al., 2020), with a specific fish density threshold for each
364 fish species and associated pathogen likely to apply (Krkošek, 2010).

365 **1.7.3 Environmental risk factors**

366 ISKNV infection is temperature-dependent with the optimum replication temperature between 20°C-27°C
367 (Jung and Oh, 2000; He et al., 2002; Nakajima et al., 2002; Wang et al., 2003). *In vivo* culture of ISKNV
368 showed the same result (Nakajima and Sorimachi, 1994; He et al., 2002). Experimental ISKNV infection in
369 mandarin fish showed that at 15°C and 20°C, no clinical signs and mortality were observed (He et al., 2002)
370 and mortality reached 100% at 25, 28, 30 and 34°C (He et al., 2002). The results were consistent with
371 natural outbreaks of ISKNV which were reported only when the temperature was above 20°C (He et al.,
372 2002; Lancaster et al., 2003; Sukenda et al., 2020). Studies considering the effects of increasing water
373 temperature on the transition of subclinical RSIV infection in rock bream showed no mortality for infected
374 fish kept at 13°C (Jun et al., 2009), 17°C (Jung et al., 2015) and 18°C (Kyung Choi et al., 2006). When the
375 water temperature was raised from 18 to 21, 25, 26 and 29°C, a cumulative mortality up to 100% in 21
376 days was observed (Kyung Choi et al., 2006; Jun et al., 2009; Jung et al., 2015). The RSIV genotype has a
377 similar optimal replication temperature to ISKNV between 23 to 27°C (Jung and Oh, 2000; Nakajima et al.,
378 2002; Wang et al., 2003). Detailed risk factor studies have not been undertaken to determine the role of
379 additional environmental risk factors on the severity of disease.

380

381 **1.7.4 Transmission of Infectious spleen and kidney necrosis virus**

382 There is limited evidence that ISKNV can be transmitted vertically from parent to offspring as well as by
383 horizontal transmission. Vertical transmission of ISKNV was suspected in Nile tilapia after ISKNV was

384 detected in fertilized eggs using *in situ* loop-mediated isothermal amplification (LAMP) assay (Suebsing et
385 al., 2016). Horizontal transmission of ISKNV has been demonstrated experimentally via cohabitation
386 without contact between fish (Go and Whittington, 2019) and from the environment through ISKNV
387 contaminated water (He et al., 2002; Fusianto et al., 2019). ISKNV remained infectious in aquarium water
388 for at least 48 hours at 25°C , without a host and despite the water being below the level of quantification
389 of the qPCR assay (below 100 copies of ISKNV genome per mL aquaria water) was able to create infection
390 in Murray cod (Fusianto et al., 2019).

391 The other possible routes of ISKNV transmission are feeding and ectoparasites. The use of low-value fish
392 “trash fish” as the main feed in grouper aquaculture in Indonesia (Rimmer et al., 2013) and Malaysia
393 (Lajimin et al., 2015) poses a risk for ISKNV transmission. ISKNV was detected in trash fish used in grouper
394 aquaculture in Malaysia (Lajimin et al., 2015) and Indonesia (Rimmer et al., 2019). There is no study on
395 ectoparasite transmission of ISKNV between fish, however, ectoparasites have potential as a virus vector
396 as demonstrated on two ectoparasites, *Lernanthropus* sp. and *Diplectanum* sp. which tested positive for
397 SDDV in an outbreak caused by this similar *Megalocytivirus* in farmed barramundi in Vietnam (Charoenwai
398 et al., 2020). Understanding the epidemiology and the risk factors for ISKNV infection can provide essential
399 information for disease management in aquaculture facilities.

400

401 **1.8 Detection of *Infectious spleen and kidney necrosis virus* and diagnosis of disease**

402 *Infectious spleen and kidney necrosis virus* infection exhibits general clinical signs as previously described.
403 Therefore, further laboratory diagnosis including PCR or indirect fluorescent antibody test (IFAT) is
404 required accompanied with histopathology to provide an aetiological diagnosis of disease. Methods for
405 detection and diagnosis of ISKNV recommended by OIE (2019b) are cell culture, IFAT, and PCR.

406

407 **1.8.1 Cell culture**

408 Permissive cell lines provide a method of demonstrating the presence of infectious ISKNV in a sample (OIE,
409 2019b). Propagation of ISKNV in cells is also an essential tool for studies of ISKNV to consider functional
410 genomics, proteomics, virus-host interactions, and virus characterization (Dong et al., 2008; Dong et al.,
411 2011). Viral cell culture can accommodate mass virus propagation for vaccine development (Nakajima et
412 al., 1999; Caipang et al., 2006). However, the development of cell lines for ISKNV has been challenging. All
413 the ISKNV genotypes were difficult to culture using commercially available cell lines and the viral titre of
414 the isolates often decreased after serial passages (Nakajima et al., 1999; Dong et al., 2008; Dong et al.,
415 2011). Highly susceptible cell lines for ISKNV have been developed for ISKNV research (Table 1.2).

416 The cell line recommended by OIE (2019b) for ISKNV and RSIV propagation is Grunt fin (GF) cell line with
417 incubation at 25°C. For diagnostic purposes, GF cells were reported to be adequate for providing a virus
418 titre for identification which has been successful for ISKNV (Jitrakorn et al., 2020), RSIV (Koda et al., 2019),
419 and TRBIV (Koda et al., 2018) from clinical samples. However, the GF cell line has a limitation on stability
420 of viral titre, which declined with additional passages (Ito et al., 2013) and so was not ideal for other
421 purpose rather than diagnosis (Kawato et al., 2017). Tailored cell lines which were reported to have a high
422 and stable propagation rate have been developed for RSIV (spotted knifejaw (SKJ-9)) (Kawato et al., 2017),
423 ISKNV (early primary culture of mandarin fish fry (MFF-8C1)) (Dong et al., 2014), and TRBIV (turbot fin cell
424 line (TF)) (Fan et al., 2010). These have advanced gene expression and vaccine development research.

425

426 **Table 1.2.** List of cell lines developed for ISKNV propagation.

Cell line name	Year of the first report usage for ISKNV	The origin of cell line	Optimum incubation temperature	ISKNV genotype	Reference
Bluegill fry-2 (BF-2)	1998	Bluegill fry	25°C	RSIV	(Nakajima et al., 1998)
Grunt fin (GF)*	1998	Grunt fin cell	25°C	RSIV, ISKNV, TRBIV	(Nakajima et al., 1998) (Koda et al., 2018)
Flounder embryonic cell line (FEC)	2004	Gastrula-stage embryos of Japanese flounder	24-30°C	TRBIV	(Chen et al., 2004)
CRF-1	2007	Fibroblast of the tail fin of red sea bream	24°C	RSIV	(Imajoh et al., 2007)
Mandarin fish fry-1 (MFF-1)	2008	Two-day-old mandarin fish fry	27°C	ISKNV	(Dong et al., 2008)
Brown-marbled grouper heart (bmGH)	2009	The heart of brown-marbled grouper	24°C	TRBIV	(Wei et al., 2010)
Red sea bream fin-2 (RSBF-2)	2010	The dorsal fin of red sea bream	28°C	RSIV	(Ku et al., 2010)
Turbot fin (TF)	2010	Turbot fin	24°C	TRBIV	(Fan et al., 2010)
Mandarin fish fry-8C1 (MFF-8C1)	2013	Fibroblast cell line from an early primary culture of mandarin fish fry	25°C	RSIV and ISKNV	(Dong et al., 2014)
Snubnose pompano brain (SPB)	2013	The brain of snubnose pompano	20-35°C	RSIV and ISKNV	(Wen et al., 2013)
Spotted knifejaw-9 (SKJ-9)	2017	Larvae of spotted knifejaw 48 h after hatching	25°C	RSIV and ISKNV	(Kawato et al., 2017)

427 *Recommended by OIE for RSIV and ISKNV isolation and identification.

428

429 **1.8.2 Indirect fluorescent antibody test (IFAT)**

430 An indirect fluorescent antibody test (IFAT) for ISKNV was first developed by Nakajima and Sorimachi
431 (1995) for detection of RSIV in red sea bream and 10 other species of cultured marine fish. The IFAT assay
432 involved incubation of the preparation of smears from spleen, liver, or anterior and posterior kidneys and
433 incubation with a specific monoclonal antibody (MAb) for RSIV, followed by detection with a secondary
434 anti-mouse antibody conjugated to a fluorescein isothiocyanate fluorochrome. The MAb-secondary
435 antibody complex could then be visualised by fluorescent microscopy to contribute to a specific diagnosis
436 within two hours (Nakajima and Sorimachi, 1995). This assay also detected ISKNV but not *Ranavirus*
437 (Nakajima et al., 1998; OIE, 2019b).

438 Polyclonal antibodies for the ISKNV MCP and Viral protein 23R were developed for use in
439 immunohistochemistry and immunofluorescence studies of ISKNV in experimentally infected zebrafish
440 (Xu et al., 2008), mandarin fish (Xu et al., 2010b) and spotted green pufferfish (*Tetraodon nigroviridis*) (Xu
441 et al., 2010a). The ISKNV MCP and Vp23R polyclonal antibodies were applied for viral protein expression
442 studies within the host cells (Xu et al., 2008; Xu et al., 2010a; Xu et al., 2010b). The assay accurately
443 demonstrated the locations of the viral protein expression (Xu et al., 2008; Xu et al., 2010a; Xu et al.,
444 2010b). Like the IFAT, immunohistochemistry provides a diagnostic approach to confirm ISKNV as the
445 cause of clinical disease.

446 **1.8.3 Polymerase chain reaction**

447 PCR is the most sensitive, rapid, and effective method for ISKNV detection which makes it suitable for
448 surveillance in support of aquaculture biosecurity. The target organs for ISKNV PCR assays are spleen,
449 kidney, or liver which need to be homogenised or swabbed with subsequent purification of nucleic acids
450 (OIE, 2019b). PCR assays have been developed for the purpose of detecting specific genotype of ISKNV

451 (Lin et al., 2017) and multiple genotypes of ISKNV (Gias et al., 2011; Kurita and Nakajima, 2012; Rimmer
452 et al., 2012; Mohr et al., 2015). A summary of PCR assay described for ISKNV is provided in Table 1.3.

453 The first PCR assay for MCV detection which designed for RSIV, was established by Oshima et al. (1996).
454 The development of PCR assay was rapid after the publication of whole-genome sequences of ISKNV (He
455 et al., 2001) and RSIV (Kurita et al., 2002). The emergence of ISKNV and RSIV emphasised the importance
456 of the development of PCR assay which could detect both genotypes for aquaculture biosecurity. The
457 ISKNV detection recommended by OIE (2019b) is one-step conventional PCR which amplifies the *Pst* I
458 fragment (570 bases) target for RSIV and ISKNV. Another one-step conventional PCRs for ISKNV detection
459 was developed with five primer sets to identify all ISKNV genotypes (Kurita and Nakajima, 2012).
460 Conventional PCR as described in the present OIE method has a limitation of detection of 1×10^4 copies
461 of the viral genome. This is not sufficient for samples containing a low virus load which occurs frequently
462 in subclinical subsample (Rimmer et al., 2012; Rimmer et al., 2015) or during clinical disease (Rimmer et
463 al., 2017; Sah Putra et al., 2020; Fusianto et al., 2021). Sensitive and accurate detection in a subclinical
464 sample or very early infection of ISKNV is crucial for biosecurity to prevent the transboundary spread of
465 ISKNV. Two-step nested PCR (nPCR) was developed to achieve greater sensitivity compared to the PCR
466 assays (Rimmer et al., 2012). The first round nPCR test used set of primers to amplify a 430 bp primary
467 sequence, and the “nested” second-round primers to amplify a 167 bp secondary sequence from the
468 *Megalocytivirus* major capsid protein gene (Table 1.3) (Rimmer et al., 2012). The nPCR has sensitivity up
469 to 2.21×10^3 copy virus (Rimmer et al., 2012).

470 The most sensitive and accurate method, real-time quantitative PCR (qPCR), has been established for
471 ISKNV (Table 1.3). Universal ISKNV SYBR Green qPCRs have been developed by Caipang et al. (2003), Gias
472 et al. (2011), and Rimmer et al. (2012) which report analytical sensitivity of 100 copies of the ISKNV
473 genome virus per mg tissue. The TaqMan qPCR method for ISKNV has been developed by Lin et al. (2017)
474 which could detect 8.75×10^1 copy virus, which was 10,000 times more sensitive than conventional PCR.

475 At present there is limited diagnostic validation data for the qPCR assays, but they are being adopted
476 where high throughput surveillance is required (Crane and Moody 2018). Detection of ISKNV using qPCR
477 has become Australian and New Zealand standard diagnostic procedures (Crane and Moody 2018).
478 Australia uses qPCR assay described by Rimmer et al. (2012) and Mohr et al. (2015) while New Zealand
479 uses qPCR test described by Gias et al. (2011).

480 Quantification of ISKNV DNA by qPCR relies on the construction of a standard curve obtained from
481 amplification of a serial dilution of reference DNA (Mackay et al., 2002). Due to complications in
482 propagating ISKNV in cell culture, the reference DNA for ISKNV for some qPCR assays was derived from a
483 plasmid containing a target ISKNV sequence (Rimmer et al., 2012; Mohr et al., 2015). The advantages of
484 using plasmid as reference DNA are easy to multiply using bacteria as a cloning vector in a large scale
485 production and very stable from mutation (Green and Sambrook, 2012).

486

487 **Table 1.3.** Summary of widely used primers for ISKNV detection by PCR.

Assay/Primer name	Sequence (5'-3')	Amplicon size (bp)	Gene	Virus target	Reference
Single step PCR					
1-F (OIE Primer)	CTC AAA CAC TCT GGC TCA TC	570	<i>Pst</i> I	ISKNV, RSIV	(Kurita et al., 1998)
1-R (OIE Primer)	GCA CCA ACA CAT CTC CTA TC				
MCP-uni332-F3	AGG TGT CGG TGT CAT TAA CGA CCT G	777	MCP	ISKNV, RSIV, TRBIV	(Kurita and Nakajima, 2012)
MCP-uni1108-R8	TCT CAG GCA TGC TGG GCG CAA AG				
MCP-specT37-F1	TTC ATC GAC ATC TCC GCT TTC	453	MCP	TRBIV	(Kurita and Nakajima, 2012)
MCP-specT440-R1	TST GAC CGT TGG TGA TAC CGG AG				
MCP-specI465-F3	GGT GGC CGG CAT CAC CAA CGG C	415	MCP	ISKNV	(Kurita and Nakajima, 2012)
MCP-specI879-R3	ACG GGG TGA CTG AAC CTG				
Nested PCR					
C1105	GGG TTC ATC GAC ATC TCC GCG	430	MCP	ISKNV, RSIV	(Rimmer et al., 2012)
C1106	AGG TCG CTG CGC ATG CCA ATC				
C1073	AAT GCC GTG ACC TAC TTT GC	167	MCP		
C1074	GAT CTT AAC ACG CAG CCA CA				
qPCR Sybr green					
MCPS F	CTG CGT GTT AAG ATC CCC TCC A	429	MCP	RSIV	(Caipang et al., 2003)
MCPS R	GAC ACC GAC ACC TCC TCA ACT A				
C1073	AAT GCC GTG ACC TAC TTT GC	167	MCP	ISKNV, RSIV	(Rimmer et al., 2012)
C1074	GAT CTT AAC ACG CAG CCA CA				
Mega1	GTGTGGCTGCGTGTTAAG	214	MCP	ISKNV, RSIV	(Gias et al., 2011)
Mega2	TGCCAATCATCTTGTGTAGC				
Mega3	GAGGAACTCACTGGTCAGG	150	MCP	ISKNV	(Gias et al., 2011)
GTT-MB	d FAM-cgcgatc (ACA TCC GCT GGT GTG ACA ATC TGA TG) gatcgcg-BHQ-1				
qPCR TaqMan					
RSIV RT F	TGA CCA GCG AGT TCC TTG ACT T	125	MCP	ISKNV, RSIV	(Mohr et al., 2015)
RSIV RT R	CAT AGT CTG ACC GTT GGT GAT ACC				
RSIV Probe	FAM-AAC GCC TGC ATG ATG CCT GGC-TAMRA				
Forward	CGCCTTTAACGTGGGATATATTG	83	ORF007	ISKNV	(Lin et al., 2017)
Reverse	CGAGGCCACATCCAACATC				
Probe	FAM-CACCAAACCTGACCGCGACTCGT-Eclipse				

488

489 **1.9 Prevention and control of *Infectious spleen and kidney necrosis virus***

490 **1.9.1 Disinfection**

491 Disinfection is part of disease management tool in aquaculture establishment as a part of a biosecurity
492 plan (OIE, 2017). The purpose of disinfection is to prevent entry and exit of the target pathogens to the
493 aquaculture facility (OIE, 2017). There are knowledge gaps with limited studies investigating the stability
494 of ISKNV against disinfection agents (Table 1.4). Disinfection of ISKNV was investigated using the RSIV
495 genotype (Nakajima and Sorimachi, 1994; Kasai et al., 2002) and the ISKNV genotype (He et al., 2002) for
496 virus preparations under low soiling conditions. Disinfection protocols for ISKNV under high soiling
497 conditions encountered in aquaculture facility were investigated by Fusianto et al. (2019).

498 In aquaculture facilities, ISKNV can be transmitted through water contact only (Fusianto et al., 2019) and
499 potentially via shared equipment. Application of physical disinfection measures including heating and UV
500 exposure for water and equipment disinfection are preferable as treatments that do not leave a residue.
501 Ultraviolet sterilisation has been widely used for water and equipment treatment in aquaculture facilities
502 which was effective for aquatic pathogens including viruses, sea lice, bacteria, and fungi (Sharrer et al.,
503 2005; Barrett et al., 2020; Lieke et al., 2020). Ultraviolet exposure is also applicable for fertilized egg
504 sterilisation (Barrett et al., 2020). Chemical disinfection is more suitable for wastewater or foot bath as
505 the treatments as they leave residues which are potentially harmful for fish and the environment (Lieke
506 et al., 2020).

507

508 **Table 1.4.** Specific disinfection protocols for ISKNV that have been evaluated.

Genotype of ISKNV	Treatment	Concentration	Contact time (minutes)	Soiling condition	Testing method	Methods of detection	Outcome	Reference	
ISKNV	Heating to 40°C	na	20	High (10% v/v Foetal bovine serum)	Bioassay (Murray cod)	qPCR	not effective	(Fusianto et al., 2019)	
	Heating to 60°C	na	5				not effective		
	Heating to 65°C	na	20				effective		
	pH 3	na	30				effective		
	pH 11	na	30				effective		
	Virkon™	1%	10				effective		
	Sodium hypochlorite	1000 ppm	30				effective		
	Benzalkonium chloride	650 ppm	10				effective		
	Iodine	25	15				not effective		
		50	15				not effective		
		100	15	not effective					
	Potassium permanganate	25	15	not effective					
		50	15	not effective					
		100	15	effective					
	Formaldehyde	500	15	not effective					
		1000	15	not effective					
		2000	15	effective					
	Sodium hypochlorite	50	15	not effective					
		100	15	effective					
		200	15	not effective					
		Stored at 25°C		>15 days	na	Bioassay (Mandarin fish)	Histopathology	not effective	(He et al., 2002)
		Stored at 4°C		>6 months				not effective	
		Stored at -20°C		>18 months				not effective	
		Stored at -70°C		>18 months				not effective	
		Heating to 30°C		30				not effective	
		Heating to 40°C		30				not effective	
		Heating to 50°C	na	30				effective	
		Heating to 60°C		30				effective	
		UV exposure 20 W, wavelength: 253.7 µm, distance 50 mm		30				effective	
		pH 3		30				effective	
	pH 7		30			not effective			
	pH 11		30			not effective			
RSIV	pH 3		na			Cytopathic effect (CPE) on cell line	effective	(Nakajima and Sorimachi, 1994)	
	pH 7		na				not effective		
	pH 11		na				not effective		
	Heating to 56°C	na	30	na	Cell line BF-2 and KRE-3		effective		
	Chloroform		na				effective		
	Ether		na				effective		
Two cycles of freezing (-80°C) and thawing (20°C)		na				not effective			

509

Ultrasonication at 45 KHz	1		not effective
UV exposure 104 μ W sec/m ²	na	Cell line	effective (Kasai et al., 2002)

510 1.9.2 Vaccination

511 Three type of vaccines have been developed for ISKNV: Formalin killed cell (FKC) vaccine for RSIV
512 (Nakajima et al., 1999) and ISKNV (Dong et al., 2013a), recombinant protein vaccine for RSIV (Shimmoto
513 et al., 2010) and ISKNV (Fu et al., 2012; Li et al., 2015; Zhao et al., 2020), and DNA vaccine for RSIV (Caipang
514 et al., 2006), and TRBIV (Zheng et al., 2016; Zheng et al., 2017) (Table 1.5). The efficacy of ISKNV vaccine
515 is likely host species dependent. RSIV-FKC vaccine was reported effective to fish belonging to the genus
516 *Seriola*, striped jack (*Pseudocaranx dentex*), Malabar grouper (*Epinephelus malabaricus*), and orange-
517 spotted grouper (*Epinephelus coioides*) but not effective to fish species belong to the genus *Oplegnathus*
518 (Nakajima et al., 1999). The duration of protection after vaccination was reported up to four months in
519 mandarin fish which were vaccinated with ISKNV-FKC vaccine (Dong et al., 2013b).

520 Development of vaccines for ISKNV has shown success at the experimental stage. However, unfortunately
521 at present none have been extensively evaluated to make available for commercial use. The only licenced
522 commercial vaccine available for ISKNV is a FKC vaccine designed for the RSIV genotype (Nakajima et al.
523 (1997); Nakajima et al. (1999). This vaccine commercially available with brand Aquavac® IridoV
524 (www.aquavac-vaccines.com). Despite the similarity between RSIV and ISKNV, the RSIV commercial
525 vaccine did not provide cross protection to ISKNV genotype which caused an outbreak in RSIV vaccinated
526 barramundi in Vietnam with mortality up to 71% of the juvenile (3-15 g) (Dong et al., 2017). Cross
527 protection has been reported on ISKNV-FKC vaccine against RSIV in two experimental vaccination studies
528 on mandarin fish (Dong et al., 2013b). Extensive evaluation is needed for the developed ISKNV vaccine to
529 provide wider option for commercial ISKNV vaccine selection.

530 **Table 1.5.** Summary of published vaccine development for ISKNV. Bolding indicates the commercially available vaccine.

Genotype of ISKNV	Year	Vaccine type	Gene target	Adjuvant	Administration	Vaccine dose	Validation			Efficacy (%)	Reference
							Fish species	Number of fish	Size (g)		
RSIV	1999	FKC	Whole RSIV virus	na	Intra peritoneal	0.1 mL of supernatant of RSIV infected GF cell	<i>Pagrus major</i>	1000	6.2	80.2	(Nakajima et al., 1999)
	2006	DNA	pCMV-MCP	na	Intra muscular	25 µg of plasmid DNA resuspended in 100 mL of sterile PBS.	<i>Pagrus major</i>	150	5-10	71.4	(Caipang et al., 2006)
	2010	Recombinant protein	RSIV capsid protein 351R and glyceraldehyde 3-phosphate dehydrogenase (GAPDH) from the bacterium <i>Edwardsiella tarda</i>	na	Intra peritoneal	400 µg of FKC (<i>E.coli</i>) in 100 mL of sterile PBS.	<i>Pagrus major</i>	60	10	94	(Shimmoto et al., 2010)
	2012	FKC	Whole ISKNV virus	white oil adjuvant MARCOL 52	Intra peritoneal	0.2 mL vaccine dose (5 x 10 ⁵ TCID ₅₀ /0.1 mL)	<i>Siniperca chuatsi</i>	1000	13-20	99	(Dong et al., 2013)
ISKNV	2013	FKC	Whole ISKNV virus	na	Intra peritoneal	0.2 mL vaccine dose (5 x 10 ⁵ TCID ₅₀ /0.1 mL)	<i>Siniperca chuatsi</i>	50	72 ± 15	90	(Dong et al., 2013a)
	2012	Recombinant protein	MCP in expression vector <i>pBV220</i>	ISA763 (oil adjuvant)	Intra peritoneal	50 µg	<i>Siniperca chuatsi</i>	60	40-50	64.3	(Fu et al., 2012)
	2014	Recombinant protein	ORF93 in expression vector pcDNA3.1	Freund's incomplete adjuvant was	Intra peritoneal	50 µg	<i>Siniperca chuatsi</i>	30	40-50	57	(Li et al., 2015)
	2019	Recombinant protein	MCP in expression vector <i>pE-SUMO</i> combined with single-walled carbon nanotubes	na	immersion for 10 hours	20 mg/L	<i>Siniperca chuatsi</i>	50	6 ± 0.5	69.6	(Zhao et al., 2019)

	2020	Recombinant protein	MCP in expression vector <i>pE-SUMO</i> combined with single-walled carbon nanotubes	na	immersion for 8 hours	20 mg/L		43	3 ± 0.5	86.7	(Zhao et al., 2020)
							<i>Siniperca chuatsi</i>				
TRBIV	2016	DNA encapsulated in chitosan nano particle	MCP	na	Oral (direct to stomach)	10 µg pDNA in 0.5 mL PBS	<i>Scophthalmus maximus</i>	60	18	68	(Zheng et al., 2016)
	2017	DNA	pVAX1-TRBIV- MCP	na	Intra muscular	5 µg pDNA in 100 µL PBS	<i>Scophthalmus maximus</i>	100	70 ± 0.5	70	(Zheng et al., 2017)

531

532 **1.9.3 Translocation and regulations**

533 International trade of live aquatic animals has been identified as a major route for pathogen introduction
534 to new geographic areas (Whittington and Chong, 2007). The increasing worldwide distribution of ISKNV
535 reflects, in part, inadequate biosecurity measures applied to ornamental fish (Rimmer et al., 2015). The
536 emergence of RSIV in multiple food fish species in Japan was suggested to have arisen from imported fish
537 fingerlings from SE Asia (Kurita and Nakajima, 2012). TRBIV was detected in Taiwan in imported rock
538 bream fingerling from Korea (Huang et al., 2011) and barramundi fingerlings from Thailand (Tsai et al.,
539 2020).

540 Fish trading and insufficient biosecurity measures have driven ISKNV outbreaks in many ornamental fish
541 importing countries such as Germany (Jung-Schroers et al., 2016), Australia (Rimmer et al., 2015), Japan
542 (Sudthongkong et al., 2002), Korea (Joon et al., 2008; Kim et al., 2010), the USA (Weber et al., 2009), and
543 the UK (Sriwanayos et al., 2013). A study conducted by Rimmer et al. (2015) on imported fish prior to
544 entering quarantine, during quarantine, and post quarantine in Australia showed that ISKNV was detected
545 at all stages under a previous national biosecurity plan. ISKNV was detected in fish sold by aquatic retail
546 outlets in Australia (Rimmer et al., 2015) and was suggested to have illustrated the biosecurity risk
547 pathway previously responsible for mass mortality of Murray cod on a farm in Victoria, Australia
548 (Lancaster et al., 2003).

549 Two members of ISKNV species, ISKNV and RSIV, are named in the OIE Manual of Diagnostic Tests for
550 Aquatic Animals (OIE, 2019b). For many countries, certification of freedom from ISKNV and RSIV is
551 mandatory prior to trade of susceptible fish species (OIE, 2019a). For example in Australia where ISKNV is
552 exotic, since 1 March 2016, for the importation of all fish species belonging to the families *Osphronemidae*
553 (gouramis, paradise fish, bettas), *Cichlidae* and *Poeciliidae* require health certification showing freedom
554 from MCVs After arriving in Australia, imported freshwater fish require post-arrival quarantine for 7 day

555 (except for goldfish which is 21 days) before release to the Australian aquarium market (Australian
556 Department of Agriculture, Water, and the Environment, 2021). Marine ornamental fish being imported
557 into Australia do not require a specific health certification to be free of MCVs (Australian Department of
558 Agriculture, Water, and the Environment, 2021) despite several commonly imported species (e.g. Banggai
559 cardinal fish (Weber et al., 2009)) being susceptible to ISKNV. The laboratory assays presently
560 recommended by the OIE are not compatible with the large sample size of fish that require testing with
561 sensitivity to detect subclinical infection, a task for which qPCR assays are best suited.

562 **1.10 Conclusions**

563 The continued emergence of ISKNV is impacting a very broad range of tropical and temperate fish species
564 across an increasing portion of the world. This disease threat is a major constraint on aquaculture and
565 restricts the production to meet the growing demands for fish consumption. Effective measures for
566 disease prevention and management require enhanced knowledge of the pathogens and a clear
567 nomenclature. Some knowledge gaps have been identified in an attempt to control ISKNV including
568 outdated ISKNV diagnostic method and understanding of ISKNV genotypes described by OIE (2019b),
569 unstandardized nomenclature, limited epidemiology study, insufficient vaccine development and
570 inadequate effective disinfection study. These areas are essential to be fulfilled for effective biosecurity
571 implementation.

572

573 **1.11 Thesis objectives**

574 The objective of this thesis was to generate new knowledge about ISKNV to inform improved disease
575 control in aquaculture whilst recognizing the virus is endemic in some regions (e.g. SE Asia) and exotic in
576 others (e.g. Australia). The specific aims were:

- 577 1. To apply a diagnostic approach to multifactorial diseases in aquaculture using epidemiological
578 approaches to inform the integration of emerging diagnostic technology with a thorough clinical
579 outbreak investigation.
- 580 2. To apply developed methods for complete genome characterisation of ISKNV and apply molecular
581 epidemiology to inform disease control approaches for this emerging viral pathogen.
- 582 3. To evaluate disinfection measures for ISKNV to inform effective biosecurity at aquaculture facilities.
- 583

584 **2. General Materials and Methods**

585 **2.1 Introduction**

586 This chapter describe the general materials and methods used throughout the thesis. These methods will
587 be referred to in the experimental chapters where procedures specific to individual experiments are
588 described in detail. Common and scientific names for all fish species used in this thesis are from Fish Base
589 (www.fishbase.org).

590 **2.2 Reagents**

591 **2.2.1 General reagents**

592 *Milli-Q water*

593 Milli-Q (MQ) water used throughout this study was generated with a Milli-Q® Biocel Ultrapure
594 Water Purification System (Millipore, Billerica, MA) with the following specifications: resistivity =
595 18.2 MOhms·cm at 25°C; total organic carbons = 5–10 parts per billion; pyrogens <0.001 EU/mL;
596 bacteria <1 cfu/mL; flow rate = 1 L/minute.

597

598 *Phosphate buffered saline (PBS)*

599 1 x PBS tablet (Amresco)

600 100 mL of MQ water Autoclave at 121°C for 15 minutes

601 Stored at room temperature

602 *Ethanol, 70% (v/v)*

603 70 mL of ethanol (Sigma Aldrich)

604 Made up to 100 mL with of MQ water

605 Stored at room temperature

606

607 *Virkon® disinfection solution, 1% (w/v)*
608 10 g Virkon® (Du-Pont™)
609 1 L Municipal tap water
610
611 *Benzocaine (ethyl-4-aminobenzoate), 100 g/L*
612 10 g of benzocaine (Sigma)
613 100 mL of 100% ethanol (Sigma)
614 Stored in a dark and light-proof container at room temperature

615
616 *10% neutral buffered formalin*
617 200 mL of 37–40% formaldehyde (Sigma)
618 4 g of sodium phosphate monobasic (Sigma)
619 6.5 g of sodium phosphate dibasic (Sigma)
620 MQ water made up to 1 L
621 Stored at room temperature

622
623 **2.2.2 Reagents for DNA methods**

624 *High Pure Viral Nucleic Acid Kit (Roche, Germany) reagents*
625 Inhibitor Removal Buffer
626 33 mL inhibitor removal buffer concentrate
627 20 mL 100% ethanol (Sigma)
628 Stored at room temperature
629 Wash Buffer
630 10 mL wash buffer concentrate

631 40 mL 100% ethanol (Sigma)
632 Stored at room temperature
633 Elution Buffer
634 Nuclease free water
635 Poly (A)
636 2 mg lyophilised Poly (A) carrier RNA
637 0.5 mL elution buffer
638 Stored in 50 µL aliquots at –20°C
639 Proteinase K
640 100 mg lyophilised Proteinase K
641 5 mL elution buffer
642 Stored in 200 µL aliquots at –20°C
643 Binding Buffer working solution
644 50 µL Poly (A)
645 2.5 mL binding buffer
646
647 *MagMax-96 Viral Isolation Kit (Ambion, USA) reagents*
648 Lysis Binding Solution
649 625 µL carrier DNA
650 80 mL lysis binding solution concentrate 40 mL
651 100% isopropanol (Sigma)
652 Mixed by vortexing and stored at room temperature
653 Wash Solution 1
654 180 mL wash solution 1 concentrate 60 mL

655 100% isopropanol (Sigma)
656 Mixed by vortexing and stored at room temperature
657 Wash Solution 2
658 200 mL wash solution 2 concentrate 160 mL
659 100% ethanol (Sigma)
660 Mixed by vortexing and stored at room temperature
661 Binding beads working solution
662 Number of reactions × 20 µL binding beads
663 Number of reactions × 20 µL lysis binding enhancer
664 Mixed by gentle vortexing and placed on ice

665 *Phenol Chloroform DNA extraction reagents*

666 360 µL RLT lysis buffer
667 40 µL proteinase K
668 400 µL phenol:chlorophorm:isoamyl-alcohol (25:24:1)
669 3M Sodium Acetate
670 1200 µL absolute ethanol (-20°C)
671 500 µL 70% ethanol (-20°C)
672 50 µL TE buffer (elution)

673

674 **2.3 Sampling**

675 **2.3.1 General guidelines**

676 Organ sampling and preparation procedures occurred in a class 2 biosafety cabinet. Before processing
677 the sample, all surfaces of the cabinet were wiped with Trigene advance (1:100 dilution) and exposed to
678 UV light for 15 minutes. All glassware, forceps, scissors, blades, and plastic-ware were either autoclaved

679 or manufacturer-certified sterile prior to use. After usage, the instruments were soaked in a disinfection
680 solution (1% Virkon®) for 30 minutes, washed in detergent and water and sterilised by autoclaving before
681 reuse. For on-farm sampling, instruments used for necropsy and work surfaces were disinfected by
682 immersion in 200 ppm sodium hypochlorite for 10 minutes, rinsing in clean tap water and then spraying
683 70% ethanol between each use. Different sterile disposable scalpel blades were used, and gloves were
684 changed for each fish.

685 **2.3.2 On farm sampling**

686 Tissue of approximately 2 g each from liver, spleen, anterior and posterior kidney were pooled in a 5 mL
687 tube for each individual fish. The samples were preserved for DNA purification using a 3:1 volumetric ratio
688 with 80% ethanol. For purification of viral RNA, retina and brain from individual fish were pooled in a 5
689 mL tube with 80% ethanol. Whole organs including the heart, liver, spleen, anterior and posterior kidney,
690 brain and eyes from different fish were preserved in 10 times volume of 10% neutral buffer formalin to
691 preserve them for histopathology (Noga, 2010).

692 **2.3.3 Manual homogenisation**

693 Manual tissue sample homogenisation was performed by grinding (0.05 g) (equal parts of liver, spleen,
694 anterior and posterior kidney) with nine parts homogenising medium (PBS) (0.45 g) (1:10 w/v) with a
695 chilled mortar and sterile pestle. An amount of sterile sand was added just before grinding. Mortar and
696 pestles were soaked in a 1% Virkon® disinfection solution for 30 minutes, rinsed in water and autoclaved
697 for reuse.

698 **2.3.4 Bead-beating sample homogenization**

699 Semi-automated micro bead-beating tissue sample homogenisation was performed in a 2 mL tube
700 containing 0.1 mm zirconia/silica beads (Daintree Scientific, St. Helens, Australia) and 0.15 g total weight

701 of equal parts liver, spleen, anterior and posterior kidney samples. Tubes were subjected to
702 homogenisation using the TissueLyser II (Qiagen) with a frequency of 30 Hz for 60 seconds. The tubes
703 were inverted and the homogenisation cycle was repeated with the same setting. Samples were then
704 incubated on ice for at least 5 minutes. Tissue homogenates were clarified by centrifugation at $1000 \times g$
705 for 10 minutes in a microcentrifuge at room temperature. The supernatant was retained for analysis and
706 stored at -80°C .

707 **2.4 Nucleic acid methods**

708 **2.4.1 General guidelines**

709 Activities for molecular tests were performed in three physically separated laboratories to prevent cross
710 contamination. A sperate clean room was dedicated to preparation of PCR reagent, another for adding
711 template nucleic acids to assay and another for post-amplification procedures. Each laboratory space had
712 dedicated equipment (e.g. lab coats, pipettes, pipette tips, reagents and racks) and these tools were not
713 removed from the areas where they were assigned. The PCR Bench (Aora PCR), Biosafety cabinet class II
714 (Ultra safe series 2010), micropipettes, and racks were cleaned with Trigene advance (1:100 dilution) and
715 exposed to UV light for 15 minutes prior and after usage. For each nucleic extraction and PCR, positive
716 and negative or blank reactions (water substituted for template) were handled using the same conditions
717 as the experimental samples.

718

719 **2.4.2 Nucleic acid extraction**

720 **2.4.2.1 Spin column**

721 Nucleic acids were purified using a High Pure Viral Nucleic Acid Kit (Roche) from preserved samples.
722 Samples were air dried for 3 minutes prior nucleic acid extraction. A starting sample of 25 mg of pooled
723 organs: equal parts of liver, spleen, and kidneys for viral DNA; or brain and retina for viral RNA was placed

724 in a sterile nuclease free 1.5 mL microcentrifuge tube with 200 μ L of binding buffer working solution and
725 50 μ L of proteinase K. The sample was disrupted by grinding using a sterile plastic mortar. The sample was
726 incubated for 10 minutes at 72°C and another 100 μ L of binding buffer was added. The homogenates then
727 were clarified by centrifugation at 12000 $\times g$ for 10 minutes in a microcentrifuge at room temperature.
728 The supernatant was transferred into the upper reservoir of a combined high pure filter and collection
729 tube and centrifuged at 8,000 $\times g$ for 1 minute. The next purification steps including centrifugation and
730 reagent addition were performed according to instruction manual. A volume of 75 μ L elution buffer was
731 added and the tube was centrifuged at 8,000 $\times g$ for 1 minute. The eluted nucleic acid was stored at -20°C
732 or -80°C until required.

733

734

2.4.2.2 MagMax Express-96

735 Nucleic acids were extracted from 50 μ L aliquots of clarified 1:10 w/v tissue homogenate using a
736 MagMax-96 Viral Isolation Kit (Ambion) according to the directions of the manufacturer. A MagMax
737 Express-96 standard plate (Applied Biosystems, USA) was labelled and 50 μ L of elution buffer was added
738 in each well. Two MagMax Express-96 standard plates were labelled and 150 μ L of wash solution 1 was
739 distributed in each well. Two MagMax Express-96 standard plates were labelled and 150 μ L of wash
740 solution 2 was added in each well. A MagMax Express-96 deep well plate was labelled and 130 μ L of lysis
741 binding solution was distributed in each well. As much as 50 μ L of clarified tissue homogenate was added
742 to each well in the deep well plate. A volume of 20 μ L of binding bead working solution was distributed
743 to each well. A MagMax Express deep well tip comb then was placed onto a new MagMax Express-96
744 standard plate and assembled along with all other prepared plates into the MagMax Express-96 magnetic
745 particle processor (Applied Biosystems). Each plate was loaded into the MagMax Express-96 magnetic
746 particle processor and nucleic acids were extracted using the manufacturer program, AM1836-DW-

747 standard. An adhesive plate sealer was sealed on the elution plate after completion of the procedure. The
748 plate then was stored at -20°C until required.

749 **2.4.2.3 Phenol Chloroform extraction**

750 The phenol-chloroform precipitation method was adapted from Green and Sambrook (2012). This
751 method was applied for samples prior to Illumina sequencing. A pool of 0.5 g of equal parts of liver, spleen,
752 and kidney were removed from ethanol preservative, air dried and washed with PBS. The pooled organs
753 were homogenised by grinding using plastic pestles in RLT lysis buffer (Qiagen) with the addition of 50 μL
754 of 10 μL proteinase K (Sigma-Aldrich) before overnight incubation at 56°C until completely lysed. RNase A
755 (2 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ DNase-free, Qiagen) was added, and the preparation was incubated at 37°C for 1 hour to remove
756 RNA. A volume of 400 μL phenol:chloroform:isoamyl-alcohol (25:24:1) was added and followed by
757 incubation at ambient temperature for 15 minutes in a fume hood (Conditionaire International). After the
758 incubation, centrifugation at 2,000 $\times g$ for 10 minutes was performed and the aqueous layer was collected.
759 DNA precipitation was performed by adding 1/20 volume (aqueous layer) of 3M Sodium acetate and 3
760 volumes of absolute ethanol followed by overnight incubation at -20°C . The DNA precipitation continued
761 by adding 500 μL of 70% ethanol (-20°C), followed by air drying. The DNA pellet was resuspended in 100
762 μL of Tris-EDTA buffer (pH 8). Series of dilutions at 1/10 and 1/100 volume were done prior to the quality
763 and quantity measurement.

764 **2.4.3 Evaluation of DNA purity**

765 The quality of nucleic acid preparations was determined by measuring the purity and quantity of DNA in
766 the samples to meet the requirements for Illumina sequencing. A NanoDrop spectrophotometer 1000
767 (Thermo Fisher Scientific) was used according to directions to estimate DNA purity by measuring A_{260}/A_{280}
768 ratio which should be between 1.8-2.0. The concentration of the DNA was measured using a Qubit[®] dsDNA

769 BR Assay Kits on a Qubit® fluorometer (Invitrogen) according to manufacturer directions. The volume of
770 sample used for measurement was 2 µL.

771

772 **2.4.4 Quantitative polymerase chain reaction (qPCR) assay for ISKNV**

773 The qPCR assay for ISKNV was adopted from Rimmer et al. (2012), which is expected to detect ISKNV
774 genotypes RSIV and ISKNV. The method was performed to detect and quantify the major capsid protein
775 gene. Individual samples were tested in duplicate 25 µL reactions containing: 5 µl of template DNA; 250
776 nM each of the forward primer (C1073: AATGCCGTGACCTACTTTGC) and reverse primer (C1074:
777 GATCTTAACACGCAGCCACA); 12.5 µl of Quantitech SYBR green PCR master mix (Qiagen); and 7.25 µl
778 molecular biology grade nuclease-free water. The controls used on each pPCR plate were: a tissue
779 homogenate from a fish confirmed to be infected with ISKNV; a negative extraction control and a no
780 template control (water). A standard curve was prepared using duplicate reactions prepared with a 7-
781 step, 10-fold dilution series of the linear plasmid DNA (pDGIV-MCP1) (Rimmer et al., 2012) which
782 contained a 694 nucleotide portion of MCP gene sequence. This dilution series was prepared in sterile
783 water each time a plate was run to provide 10^1 to 10^7 copies of template per reaction. The qPCR assay
784 was performed using an Mx3000P Multiplex Quantitative PCR System (Stratagene) run under the
785 following conditions: 1 cycle of initial denaturation at 95°C for 15 minutes (hot start activation); 40 cycles
786 of denaturation at 95°C for 30 s, annealing at 62°C for 30 s, and extension at 72°C for 30 s, with
787 fluorescence acquisition at the end of the annealing step. A dissociation curve was determined after the
788 amplification cycles by dissociating the reaction products at 95°C for 1 minute; annealing at 55°C for 30 s;
789 and then heating to 95°C at a rate of 1°C every 30 s with the collection of fluorescent data every cycle. A
790 valid PCR run was defined as amplification of both replicates of the positive control with a cycle threshold
791 (Ct) within the range of the standard curve ($r^2 > 0.95$ and efficiency between 90 and 110%) and no
792 amplification of negative controls. A sample was considered to be positive when the melting temperature

793 of the product was in the range 84.3 – 85.5°C and a threshold cycle (Ct) value was obtained for at least
794 one of the duplicates. Quantification of viral DNA in the experimental samples was estimated by
795 interpolation from the plasmid DNA standard curve. The number of copies of the MCP gene in the samples
796 was converted to the number of viral genome copies per mg of fish tissue based on the volume of eluate
797 and weight used for DNA extraction. A sample determined as below the level of quantification (BLOQ)
798 when the copy number of the virus was below 100 and below level of detection (BLOD) when one of the
799 duplicate qPCR return negative (Rimmer et al., 2012).

800 **2.4.5 Reverse transcriptase quantitative polymerase chain reaction (RT-qPCR)**
801 **assay for *Nervous necrosis virus***

802 Detection and quantification of NNV by RT-qPCR followed the method described by Hick and
803 Whittington (2010). Briefly, samples were tested in duplicate using 5 µL of purified nucleic acid as the
804 template in 25 µL reactions prepared using the QuantiTect Virus OneStep qRT-PCR kit (Qiagen). The
805 primers NNVQR2TF and NNV QR2TR were used at a concentration of 250 nM and NNVQR2T probe at 200
806 nM. Each plate included a positive control prepared from a fish tissue homogenate confirmed to be
807 infected with NNV, a negative extraction control and a no template RT-PCR control (nuclease-free water).
808 A 7-step, 10-fold dilution series of the linear plasmid standard containing the RNA2 NNV capsid protein
809 gene sequence (Hick and Whittington, 2010) was prepared in sterile water with 10¹ to 10⁷ copies of the
810 template. The RT-qPCR assay was performed using an Mx3000P Multiplex Quantitative PCR System
811 (Stratagene) with the following conditions: 1 cycle of reverse transcription at 45°C for 10 minutes; 1 cycle
812 of hot start activation at 95°C for 10 minutes; 40 cycles of denaturation at 95°C for 15 s, and annealing at
813 60°C for 45 s. The FAM fluorescence was baseline corrected and normalised to ROX passive reference dye
814 and a threshold was determined based on the amplification of the plasmid standard using a proprietary
815 algorithm (Stratagene). A sample was considered positive if duplicate reactions had a logarithmic increase
816 in fluorescence that exceeded the threshold. A Ct value was assigned and the number of copies of the

817 RNA2 gene was estimated by extrapolation from the standard curve within the range where efficiency
818 was between 90–110%. A sample determined as BLOQ when the copy number of the virus was below 100
819 (Hick and Whittington, 2010).

820 **2.4.6 Preparation of organ sections for histopathology**

821 Organs which were allocated for histopathology were reserved in 10% neutral buffered or seawater
822 formalin for at least 48 hours and were manipulated in a fume hood. A sufficient proportion of organs
823 (liver, spleen, anterior and posterior kidney, retina, and brain) were cut and placed into one or two
824 cassettes depend on the organ size. The cassettes then were fixed into 10% neutral buffered formalin with
825 the addition of EDTA (125 g/L water) for decalcification and were incubated overnight at ambient
826 temperature in a fume hood (Roberts et al., 2012). Organs were embedded in paraffin, sectioned at 5 µm
827 and stained with haematoxylin and eosin using routine methods at the Veterinary Pathology Diagnostic
828 Services laboratory, The University of Sydney.

829

830 **3. Chapter 3 - Outbreak investigation attributes *Infectious spleen and kidney necrosis virus* as a**
831 **necessary cause of a mortality epidemic in farmed grouper (*Epinephelus spp.*) in Bali, Indonesia**

832 **3.1 Abstract**

833 In 2016, farmers reported mass mortality events in hybrid grouper within 2–4 weeks following transfer to
834 sea cages on the northern coast of Bali. The objective was to obtain an aetiological diagnosis using a broad
835 range of traditional and emerging diagnostic approaches. A group of 24 and 12 fish with and without
836 clinical signs were sampled from 10 affected populations at 9 farms. Samples for histopathology,
837 ectoparasites evaluation and molecular approaches for microbiology were obtained with a diagnostic
838 post-mortem examination. Fish with clinical signs had a significantly higher likelihood of having pale
839 anterior and posterior kidneys and a liver that was pale and reduced in size compared to fish without
840 clinical signs. There were no differences in the prevalence and quantity of *Megalocytivirus* (MCV) or nervous
841 necrosis virus (NNV) in samples observed from fish with and without clinical signs. Nearly 55% of fish were
842 infected with NNV irrespective of clinical signs. There were no histopathological lesions consistent with
843 virial nervous necrosis and the NNV infections were considered sub-clinical. Eighty percent of grouper
844 were infected with MCV, irrespective of clinical signs. A significant proportion of fish with clinical signs
845 (true prevalence 94.4%; 95% CI 79–100) had observed megalocytes and pathology consistent with disease
846 caused by ISKNV compared to those without clinical signs (true prevalence 47.2%; 95% CI 27–70).
847 Metagenomic sequences generated using Illumina Miseq and taxonomically labelled using BlastN +
848 revealed that the Megalocytivirus was 99.9% similar to *Infectious spleen and kidney necrosis virus* (ISKNV).
849 The unbiased sequencing did not detect any novel DNA viruses or bacterial pathogens of clinical
850 significance. The monogenean, *Benedenia epinepheli* and a leech, *Zeylanicobdela arugamensis* were
851 detected at 6/9 and 9/9 farms, respectively. Our approach identified several pathogens reported in
852 grouper aquaculture with histopathology showing that ISKNV was a necessary cause for the mass
853 mortality events.

854 3.2 Introduction

855 Grouper aquaculture is a vital and growing source of income in rural communities across in Indonesia
856 (Rimmer and Glamuzina, 2019). This industry is valued at \$103 million AUD and supports rural livelihoods
857 through employment and new job opportunities across the value chain (Rimmer et al., 2013). Globally,
858 Indonesia is the third largest producer of grouper and in 2015, exported an estimated 5.6 million
859 fingerlings for grow out in other countries (Rimmer and Glamuzina, 2019). The main market for farmed
860 grouper is live export which can provide considerable revenue with capital payback periods generally less
861 than 1 year for small-scale farms (Pomeroy et al., 2006).

862 First generation hybrids of grouper species have been widely cultured in Southeast Asia since first being
863 introduced in 1999 (Kiryakit et al., 2011; Sun et al., 2016). Superior characteristics include high egg
864 hatching rate and larval survival, rapid growth, tolerance for ocean acidification (Mustafa et al., 2014) and
865 disease resistance (Bunlipatanon and U-taynapun, 2017). The most frequently farmed hybrids are Cantang
866 obtained as a cross from ♀ *Epinephelus fuscoguttatus* and ♂ *E. lanceolatus* and Cantik as a cross from ♀
867 *Epinephelus fuscoguttatus* x ♂ *E. polyphekadion*. Cantang and Cantik hybrids have a better growth rate,
868 food conversion ratio, and survival rate compared to *E. fuscoguttatus* (Sutarmat and Yudha, 2013) and
869 have become more popular for aquaculture in Indonesia compared to non-hybrid species (Fachry et al.,
870 2018).

871 A constraint on grouper mariculture is inconsistent production from the impact of infectious diseases and
872 repeated significant mortality events (Rimmer and Glamuzina, 2019). Vibriosis is the most commonly
873 reported bacterial disease in grouper culture (Cameron, 2001; Chong, 2011). Although *Vibrio* species are
874 commonly isolated during disease events, they are not usually considered the primary cause of disease
875 (Cameron, 2001) and most likely have a pathogenic role in multifactorial disease. Infestations with
876 monogenean ectoparasites (e.g. *Benedenia* sp., *Neobenedenia* sp. and *Pseudorhabdosynochus* sp.) are

877 highly prevalent in grouper aquaculture and cause skin lesions which are the site for secondary bacterial
878 infection (Rimmer et al., 2013). *Vibrio alginolyticus*, *Vibrio harveyi*, and *Streptococcus iniae* have caused
879 mass mortality of hybrid grouper in sea cages in east Java, Indonesia (Arif et al., 2016), Japan (Kusuda and
880 Salati, 1993) and Taiwan (Lee, 1995).

881 The predominant viral pathogens in grouper aquaculture are from the Family *Iridoviridae*, genera
882 *Ranavirus*, and *Megalocytivirus*, and Family *Nodaviridae*, nervous necrosis virus (NNV) (Ma et al., 2012;
883 Ma et al., 2016). NNV is an RNA virus that can cause the disease viral nervous necrosis (VNN) which is
884 characterised by abnormal swimming and high mortality (e.g. 80 to 100%) in larval and young juvenile,
885 predominantly marine fish. Infections are frequently subclinical in adult fish with the exception of a few
886 species, notably adult grouper (Chi et al., 2016). Megalocytiviruses (MCVs) are large double stranded DNA
887 viruses which cause a characteristic histopathological lesion of inclusion body cells in liver, kidneys, and
888 spleen (Subramaniam et al., 2012). Grouper are known to develop persistent sub-clinical infections with
889 both NNV and MCV with disease possible in all age classes (Ma et al., 2012; Jitrakorn et al., 2020; Sah
890 Putra et al., 2020).

891 The megalocytivirus, *Infectious spleen and kidney necrosis virus* (ISKNV) was first reported from China
892 following a mass mortality in the freshwater species, mandarin fish (*Siniperca chuatsi*) (He et al., 2000).
893 ISKNV has spread worldwide and caused mortality in grouper aquaculture in Taiwan (Huang et al., 2011),
894 Indonesia (Mahardika et al., 2008), and Malaysia (Razak et al., 2014). Clinical signs of a megalocytivirus
895 infection caused by ISKNV include anorexia, inappropriate regulation of body colour (darker or lighter),
896 and resting at the bottom of the cage with consequent high mortality, in the range 50-90% (Subramaniam
897 et al., 2012). Red seabream iridovirus (RSIV) is a genotype of the ISKNV species that provides the pathogen
898 name listed by the OIE (OIE, 2019b). The ISKNV and RSIV genotypes of ISKNV infect a similar range of
899 marine species used in aquaculture across East and Southeast Asia. Repeated epidemics in barramundi
900 (*Lates calcarifer*) farmed in Vietnam caused by the ISKNV genotype were confused with RSIV infections

901 and an inappropriate vaccine strategy was used (Dong et al., 2017). This was because the PCR assay used
902 was not able to differentiate between ISKNV and RSIV and the typical histopathological lesions for ISKNV
903 infections were not observed (Dong et al., 2017). After the failed vaccine preventative measures,
904 sequence analysis of the major capsid protein confirmed ISKNV infection caused the epidemics rather
905 than RSIV, which was not found (Dong et al., 2017). Grouper sleepy disease is caused by infection with
906 *Singapore grouper iridovirus* (SGIV), a ranavirus. This has been a significant cause of mortality in brown-
907 spotted grouper (*Epinephelus tauvina*) (Chua et al., 1994). Fish infected with SGIV will display similar
908 clinical signs to megalocytivirus infections, including splenomegaly (Qin et al., 2002). Molecular methods
909 can detect persistent infections with viral pathogens in fish with subclinical infection. Further, these
910 viruses have large and overlapping host and geographical ranges which can lead to delays in identifying
911 the primary cause of mortality events and actioning appropriate treatment programs.

912 Advances in nucleotide sequencing technology have enabled breakthroughs for investigating infectious
913 diseases in which pathogen culture and molecular tests for known pathogens are not available.
914 Metagenomic methods do not require knowledge of the sequence of potential pathogens as they use
915 unbiased approaches to generating sequence information from biological samples that may reveal
916 unknown or novel pathogens (Cheval et al., 2011). For example, a novel *Reovirus* was identified in farmed
917 Atlantic salmon (*Salmo salar*) with heart and skeletal muscle inflammation using a metagenomics
918 approach (Palacios et al., 2010). A veterinary epidemiological framework and complete disease
919 investigation process is needed for this new technology to be useful in attributing a role in disease
920 causation for the detected viruses. Critical to this is the use of histopathology to investigate the disease
921 process and determine the prevalence of diseased animals.

922 In 2016, a mass mortality disease of hybrid groupers was reported in grow-out farms in north Bali. Farmers
923 reported mortalities began soon after transfer to the sea cages and were associated with the appearance
924 of clinical signs such as inappetence and lethargy. The objective of this study was to obtain an aetiological

925 diagnosis for a disease syndrome considered novel by the farmers that had become prominent in sea-
926 cage grouper production. Specifically, an active targeted surveillance strategy was implemented to source
927 appropriate farm data and specimens with application of a broad range of clinical and laboratory
928 investigation techniques.

929 **3.3 Materials and methods**

930 **3.3.1 Site description**

931 The disease investigation was undertaken along the northern coast of Bali, Indonesia from August to
932 November 2016. The sampling frame for the study was all grouper sea cages in Pegametan and Sumber
933 Kima Bays during the rainy season (July-December) of 2016. There were 12 farms operating during the
934 time of sampling (Figure 3.1). The surface sea temperature data was derived from radiance measurements
935 collected every 8 days by the Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS) instruments
936 aboard NASA's Terra and Aqua satellites (<https://neo.sci.gsfc.nasa.gov/>).

937 **3.3.2 Study design**

938 A prospective strategy for targeted disease detection was used to obtain diagnostic specimens from cases
939 of mass mortality of grouper. Early identification and efficient case detection were encouraged by
940 engaging with farmers during a series of workshops offered to all staff of the sea-cage grouper farms to
941 share information about diagnosis of fish diseases. At the workshops, farmers reported mortality began
942 two to four weeks after transfer to the sea cages and within seven days of showing signs. They reported
943 the final cumulative mortality would be 80–90% over 14 days. Farmers observed the fish to show signs of
944 inappetence, inactivity with non-responsiveness to stimuli (e.g., being captured in a net) and they
945 reported some fish had a green discoloration on eyes and body surface. The case definition was the
946 sudden onset of mortality affecting at least 20% of the population and with signs of inappetence and non-
947 responsiveness. All farms agreed to participate by notifying of any cases in populations of grouper in sea

948 cages and providing access to collect information and specimens. Project staff from Universitas Gadjah
949 Mada were stationed in the area for four months ready to respond immediately to any farmer reports of
950 disease by conducting sampling for the disease investigation.

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Figure 3.1. Sampling locations of the 12 grouper grow-out farms in Bali, Indonesia (Inset) (Map generated using Mapbox ©).

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3.3.3 Fish collection

967 The targeted approach to disease detection involved sampling affected populations at the time of disease
968 outbreak with approval of the University of Sydney Animal Ethics Committee (AEC 2013/6027).
969 Populations of fish within each farm were defined as all fish of the same species (or hybrid) and age that
970 were obtained at the same time from one source.

971 A sample size of 36 fish was obtained by hand-netting from the affected population and consisted of 24
972 fish with typical clinical signs and 12 fish without clinical signs. This design aimed to sample fish at different
973 stages of the disease. The sample size was calculated based on an estimated 70% sensitivity and 90%
974 specificity for the series of diagnostic steps, to be 95% certain of detecting a disease process with a
975 minimum expected prevalence of 90%. The sample size calculation used the Epitools epidemiological
976 calculator for tests with imperfect sensitivity and specificity (<https://epitools.ausvet.com.au/freecalctwo>)
977 (Cameron and Baldock, 1998).

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3.3.4 Examination for ectoparasites

980 A skin mucus scrape and a gill and fin biopsy were obtained on farm from each sampled fish for
981 ectoparasite examination following brief anaesthesia with clove oil (0.5 mL/L). Specimens were placed
982 immediately onto glass microscope slides with a drop of filtered sea water and a cover slip. Observations
983 at 40x, 200x and 400x magnification were conducted with a light microscope (Olympus CX31) connected
984 to a laptop computer using an Optilab microscope camera (Miconos). Parasites were counted and
985 representative exemplar specimens from each population were collected in 80% ethanol for subsequent
986 identification.

987 Identification was based on morphology and 18s RNA gene sequence approaches. DNA purification was
988 performed as described in Section 3.3.6. The PCR reaction was performed in a final volume of 50 μ L
989 containing 24 μ L FastStart™ PCR Master (Roche), 20 μ L nuclease free water, 2 μ L DNA sample, 2 μ L each

990 of forward and reserve primers (Supplemental Table S3.1). PCR assays were performed using a T100
991 Thermocycler (Biorad) with the following profile: one cycle of denaturation at 95°C for 3 minutes, followed
992 by 30 cycles of denaturation at 95°C for 30 second, annealing at 55°C for 1 minute, and extension at 72°C
993 for 1 minute and one cycle of final extension 72°C for 5 minutes. PCR products were visualised by gel
994 electrophoresis on a 1% agarose gel containing 0.003% FloroSafe DNA staining (1st Base) and DNA Marker
995 XIV (Roche) was used for size comparison. Sequencing of 18s rRNA was done using BigDye® Terminator
996 v3.1 cycle sequencing kit chemistry on ABI PRISM®3700 DNA Analyzer. Taxonomic labelling of 18s rRNA
997 sequences was completed by MegaBLAST on the NCBI website (blast.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Blast.cgi).

998

999 **3.3.5 Necropsy and sample collection**

1000 Fish were euthanized using clove oil in seawater and then measured and weighed. A necropsy was
1001 undertaken while avoiding cross contamination between individual fish. Detailed method for necropsy
1002 and organ sampling referred to Section 2.3 Sampling. Specimens were preserved for nucleic acid
1003 purification from 12 fish with clinical signs and six fish without clinical signs. The remaining fish (i.e. 12
1004 with, 6 without clinical signs) were preserved for histopathology. The detailed methods of nucleic acid
1005 and histopathology preservation referred to Section 2.3.2 on farm sampling.

1006

1007 **3.3.6 Nucleic acid purification**

1008 Nucleic acid purification was conducted at the Universitas Gadjah Mada, Indonesia. Ethanol was removed
1009 by evaporation and preserved samples were rinsed once in PBS. Nucleic acids for MCV testing were
1010 purified from a pool of 0.15 g of organs with equal parts subsampled from the liver, kidney, and spleen of
1011 individual fish. The High Pure Viral Nucleic Acid Kit (Roche®) was used according to the instruction manual.
1012 The samples were homogenised by manual grinding using a plastic pestle (Geneaid) in 400 µL binding

1013 buffer with addition of 50 µL Proteinase K followed by incubation at 72°C for 10 minutes. Nucleic acids for
1014 NNV assays were purified from a 0.15 g subsample of equal parts retina and brain from individual fish.
1015 The High Pure Viral RNA Kit (Roche®) was used according to the instruction manual. The final elution
1016 volume for each procedure and was 50 µL. Purified nucleic acids were stored at -20°C for approximately
1017 one week before being shipped on dry ice to the University of Sydney and stored at -80°C until
1018 testing.

1019

1020 **3.3.7 qPCR assay for MCV**

1021 Detection and quantification of MCV by qPCR was accomplished as described in Chapter 2.4.4
1022 Quantitative polymerase chain reaction (qPCR) assay for ISKNV.

1023 **3.3.8 RT-qPCR assay for Nervous necrosis virus**

1024 Detection and quantification of NNV by RT-qPCR was performed as described in Chapter 2.4.5 Reverse
1025 transcriptase quantitative polymerase chain reaction (RT-qPCR) assay for Nervous necrosis virus.

1026 **3.3.9 Histopathology**

1027 Histopathological examination was undertaken on 12 fish with clinical signs and 6 fish without clinical
1028 signs from each population. At Universitas Gadjah Mada, standard techniques were used to prepare
1029 haematoxylin and eosin-stained slides with gill, heart, liver, spleen, anterior and posterior kidney, retina,
1030 and brain by embedding in paraffin followed by sectioning at 5 µm. To evaluate the relevance of positive
1031 PCR tests for MCV and NNV, a systematic observation of all available kidney, liver, spleen and brain and
1032 retina sections was undertaken at magnification up to 400x. Fish with megalocytic inclusion bearing cells
1033 in one or more samples were considered positive for disease associated with MCV infection. Fish with
1034 vacuolar lesions in the brain or retina were considered positive for VNN disease associated with NNV
1035 infection.

1036

3.3.10 Unbiased sequencing for potential novel pathogens

1037 An unbiased approach to nucleic acid sequence determination was used to test for a potential novel
1038 pathogen associated with this disease syndrome (i.e. RNA viruses were excluded). It was presumed that
1039 sequence from a relevant pathogen would be present at relatively high abundance and high prevalence
1040 in samples of pooled internal organs from clinically affected fish. The sample size ($n = 8$) was calculated to
1041 be 95% confident of identifying a pathogen when the minimum expected prevalence was 90% with an
1042 assumption that the test sensitivity was 90% and specificity was 100%. To increase the confidence of
1043 identifying a relevant pathogen, eight samples were selected from clinically affected fish representing a
1044 range of affected populations and considered most likely to be diagnostically relevant based on
1045 observations at necropsy and histopathology (Supplemental Table S3.2).

1046

3.3.10.1 DNA purification and sequencing

1047 A phenol-chloroform precipitation method (Green and Sambrook, 2012) was used to purify nucleic acids
1048 for unbiased sequencing. The detailed method referred to Section 2.4.2.3 phenol chloroform extraction.
1049 The evaluation of purity and quantity of the DNA was described on section 2.4.3 evaluation of DNA purity.
1050 Nucleic acid samples were submitted to the Australian Genome Research Facility (AGRF) for library
1051 preparation using Nextera XT DNA Library Preparation Kit (Illumina). Sequencing used the MiSeq V2
1052 (Illumina) chemistry for 150 bp paired end reads with 4 samples per lane and 300 cycles to obtain at least
1053 80x depth coverage.

1054

3.3.10.2 Sequence analysis

1055 Sequences were trimmed to remove Illumina adaptor sequence and exclude low quality base calls using
1056 Trimmomatic (Bolger et al., 2014). A minimum Phred score of 20 was applied to provide base call accuracy
1057 of 99% (Ewing et al., 1998). The Fastq files were paired using FASTQ joiner (Blankenberg et al., 2010). As
1058 the genome sequence for grouper was not available, sequence presumed to be the host genome was

1059 removed from the dataset by mapping the reads to the whole genome of multiple fish species:
1060 barramundi (FQ310508.3, FQ310507.3, FQ301506.3), zebra fish (*Danio rerio*) (NC_007112.7-
1061 NC_007124.7), large yellow croaker (*Larimichthys crocea*) (NC_040011.1-NC_040034.1 and NC_011710.1)
1062 and fugu (*Takifugu rubripes*) (NC_018890.1- NC_018911.1 and NC_004299.1). This process used Bowtie2
1063 without trimming and no mismatch on the read alignment (Langmead et al., 2009). The unmapped reads
1064 were processed to *de novo* assembly using SPAdes with careful correction on mismatch and short indels
1065 and K-mers value for reads alignment were set to 21, 33, and 55 (Bankevich et al., 2012). Contigs
1066 generated from SPAdes were processed for taxonomic labelling using BLAST+ (Blastn, National Center for
1067 Biotechnology Information NCBI) using the nucleotide database through CLC Genomic Workbench 12
1068 (Qiagen). Matches were identified using cut off points for the following parameters: Bit score ≥ 50 ;
1069 sequence identity $>80\%$; sequence length > 500 bp. The results were examined to identify matches that
1070 related to fish genomes, manually both using BLAST on NCBI website (blast.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Blast.cgi).
1071 Additionally, taxonomic classification was performed by submitting non-host reads to Kaiju web-based
1072 program (<http://kaiju.binf.ku.dk/server>) which matched the translated amino acid sequences of each 150
1073 bp paired end read against the NCBI BLAST non-redundant protein database for Bacteria, Archaea and
1074 Viruses (Menzel et al., 2016).

1075

1076 **3.3.10.3 Genome assembly and phylogenetic analysis**

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1078 Assembled contigs included complete MCV genomes from samples with high viral load and partial MCV
1079 genomes from other samples. Identification of the assembled genome by Mega BLAST through the NCBI
1080 website (blast.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Blast.cgi) and annotation was performed using Genome Annotation
1081 Transfer Utility (GATU) with the reference genome for Banggai cardinal fish iridovirus (BCIV) (acc number:
1082 MN432490.1) (Tcherepanov et al., 2006). The annotated genes and predicted open reading frames (ORF)

1083 produced by GATU were assessed using following criteria: (1) larger than 120 nucleotides, (2) not
1084 overlapping with another ORF by more than 25%, and (3) in the case of overlapping ORFs, only the larger
1085 ORF was annotated (Koda et al., 2018). Partial MCV genomes were mapped to the reference genome for
1086 identification. A progressive multiple sequence alignment of the assembled complete genomes using CLC
1087 Genomic workbench 12 (Qiagen) was performed with the published MCV genomes: ISKNV (Acc number:
1088 AF371960.1) (He et al., 2001), RSIV (AB104413) (Kurita et al., 2002), Turbot reddish body iridovirus (TRBIV)
1089 (GQ273492) (Shi et al., 2010), and SGIV (AY521625). Phylogenetic analyses were conducted in Mega X
1090 (Kumar et al., 2018) with the Maximum Likelihood method and General Time Reversible model with 1000
1091 bootstrap value used to generate a maximum likelihood tree.

1092

1093 **3.3.10.4 Statistical Analysis**

1094 Given the proximity of the farms to each other, a shared aquatic environment and a common feed source
1095 of low value trash fish, the data were collapsed on farms and populations. Thus, fish with and without
1096 clinical signs were compared for all observations within the affected populations. Viral loads for MCV and
1097 NNV were analysed after log 10 transformation to satisfy the assumption of normality. The viral loads
1098 were presented as the back transformed geometric mean with 95% confidence interval. Univariate
1099 associations for the presence of clinical signs, and detection of viruses and ectoparasites were determined
1100 using logistic regression and presented with odds ratio and 95% confidence interval. In all instances, the
1101 baseline for the odds ratio was fish without clinical signs. All analyses were conducted using Stata 13
1102 (2013) (StataCorp, USA). The true prevalence for the detection of ISKNV histopathology lesions was
1103 calculated using an online tool (Sergeant, 2018). A Bayesian approach was used to estimate the true
1104 prevalence of VNN lesions when none were observed (e.g. when the apparent prevalence was 0)
1105 (Sergeant, 2018).

1106

1107 **3.4 Results**

1108 **3.4.1 Case detection**

1109 There were 12 grow out farms in Pegametan and Sumber Kima Bay (Figure 3.1). Four farms had more than
1110 30 sea cages and the rest had 12-15 cages. Generally, one population of fish was kept in two cages that
1111 were typically 5 x 5 x 5 m in size. Eight farms had hybrid groupers that were newly transferred to the sea
1112 cages from local land-based nurseries and had been at the grow-out farm generally about one month. The
1113 other four farms had tiger grouper (*Epinephelus fuscoguttatus*) and or humpback grouper (*Cromileptes*
1114 *altivelis*) which had been in the sea cages for more than 3 months. All farms used locally obtained low-
1115 value trash fish as the feed. Leech infestations occurred during the study; previously they were considered
1116 rare in this area of Bali. Farmers reported they changed the ectoparasite control from application of a
1117 weekly freshwater bath to a treatment with an undisclosed dose of malachite green for 10 minutes
1118 administered once to twice per week.

1119 There was a high incidence of sudden mortality with at least one affected population reported at 9 of the
1120 12 farms from 5 August to 3 November 2016 (Table 3.1). No sampling was conducted on the three
1121 unaffected farms. The presentation of the outbreaks was the same at all farms; affected fish had non-
1122 specific clinical signs including inactivity with a preference for the bottom of the net, fin erosion and loss
1123 of appetite (Supplemental Table S3.3). The green colouration reported by farmers on the body surface
1124 and eyes was observed on fish with and without clinical signs in all affected populations. The final
1125 cumulative mortality reported by farmers at each farm was 80% to 90% over the course of one month.
1126 The surface sea temperature from 4 August to 7 November 2016 was reported to be 29.8 ± 0.84 °C
1127 (minimum 28.3 °C; maximum 31.1 °C).

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1129 **Table 3.1.** Reported cases of acute high mortality disease at grouper farms between August and November 2016 on the northern coast of Bali.

1130 Clinical signs in all cases were lethargy, inappetence and non-responsiveness to the stimulus of being captured.

Population ID	Farm ID	Sampling date 2016	Total number of populations on farm at sampling	Species sampled ¹	Days since transferred to sea cage	Number of fish sampled		Weight (g) ²	Total length (mm) ²	Condition factor ^{2,3}
						Without clinical signs	With clinical signs			
1	A	5-6 Aug	5	Cantik	30	12	24	76 ± 25	174 ± 17	1.41 ± 0.32
2	B	1-2 Sep	1	Cantik	30	12	24	54 ± 11	152 ± 10	1.54 ± 0.16
3	C	6 Sep	1	Cantik	30	12	24	47 ± 31	140 ± 27	1.49 ± 0.26
4	D	19 Sep	1	Cantang	30	12	24	71 ± 15	167 ± 11	1.51 ± 0.23
5	E	27 Sep	1	Cantik	45	12	24	82 ± 23	175 ± 15	1.50 ± 0.22
6	F	12 Oct	6	Cantang	60	6	12	108 ± 13	208. ± 13	1.21 ± 0.22
7	G	13 Oct	1	Cantik	30	12	24	50 ± 12	149 ± 12	1.49 ± 0.16
8	H	1 Nov	3	Cantang	60	6	12	139 ± 37	215 ± 12	1.39 ± 0.31
9	I	2 Nov	6	Cantik	210	6	12	467 ± 144	318 ± 38	1.46 ± 0.35
10	H	3 Nov	3	Cantik	30	12	24	47 ± 13	142 ± 13	1.60 ± 0.31

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1132 ¹Cantik = Hybrid grouper ♀ *Epinephelus fuscoguttatus* x ♂ *E. polyphekadion*; Cantang = Hybrid grouper ♀ *Epinephelus fuscoguttatus* x ♂ *E. lanceolatus*

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1134 ² mean ± standard deviation

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1136 ³ condition factor = (weight)(L⁻³)

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3.4.2 Ectoparasites and gross pathology

The leech, *Zeylanicobdela arugamensis* was detected at all nine farms with approximately one third of fish affected (Table 3.2). The monogenean, *Benedenia epinepheli* was detected at six of nine farms with approximately 18-20% of fish infested (Table 3.2). The odds of having an ectoparasite infestation was the same for grouper classified as being with and without clinical signs. A broad array of gross external and internal pathology was noted at moderate prevalence on diagnostic post-mortem examination (Table 3.2). Fish with clinical signs were 2.4 and 4.6 times more like to show fin erosion and green discoloration of the skin and eyes, respectively (Table 3.2; Supplemental Table S3.3). Fish with clinical signs had significantly higher odds of pale discoloration of the anterior kidney, posterior kidney, and liver. Fish with clinical signs were 2.3 and 7.3 times more likely to show an enlarged spleen and a small liver, respectively (Table 3.2). There was a significantly higher odds of a two-tone or patchy liver coloration in fish without clinical signs.

3.4.3 Proportion of fish with NNV infection

NNV was detected at all farms and in all affected populations in both fish with and without clinical signs (Supplemental Table S3.4). Approximately 55-57% of all fish were positive for NNV by qPCR. There were no differences in the proportion of fish infected with NNV and the mean genome copy number when comparing fish with and without clinical signs (Table 3.3). Vacuoles consistent with VNN disease were not observed in the brain and retina of any fish (Table 3.3). The true prevalence (95% CI) for the presence of VNN lesions when none were observed for fish with and without clinical signs was <0.01– 0.4% and <0.1 – 2.4%, respectively.

1158 **Table 3.2.** Proportion of individual fish with abnormalities observed at post-mortem and odds ratios for
 1159 the presence of abnormalities in samples targeted to fish showing behavioural clinical signs of disease at
 1160 the time of sampling.

Post-mortem observation	Clinical signs (%)		Odds Ratio ¹	95% CI	p value
	Present	Absent			
n	204	102			
External					
Fin Erosion	15.2	6.9	2.43	1.03 - 5.73	0.042
Green discoloration	85.3	55.9	4.58	2.64 - 7.94	0.0001
<i>Zeylanicobdela arugamensis</i>	33.8	34.3	0.978	0.593 - 1.62	0.932
<i>Benedenia epinepheli</i>	19.6	17.6	1.14	0.615 - 2.11	0.68
Internal					
Anterior kidney colour pale	12.7	4.9	2.83	1.05 - 7.62	0.039
Fluid in body cavity	22.1	25.5	0.827	0.475 - 1.44	0.503
Gall bladder over distended	71.6	78.4	0.692	0.395 - 1.21	0.199
Liver colour pale	32.4	18.6	2.09	1.17 - 3.73	0.013
Liver colour two-toned or patchy	65.7	81.4	0.438	0.246 - 0.780	0.005
Liver enlarged (hepatomegaly)	4.4	8.8	0.477	0.183 - 1.24	0.129
Liver reduced	12.7	2.0	7.3	1.70 - 31.4	0.008
Posterior kidney colour pale	19.6	4.9	4.73	1.81 - 12.4	0.002
Posterior kidney enlarged	4.4	0.0	-		
Spleen enlarged (splenomegaly)	16.2	7.8	2.27	1.00 - 5.11	0.048
Spleen reduced	15.2	9.8	1.65	0.774 - 3.51	0.195

1161 ¹ baseline for odds ratio are fish without clinical signs and bolding indicates statistical significance.

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1163 **Table 3.3.** Results for the detection of viral pathogens by PCR for fish classified on the presence of
 1164 clinical signs at the time of sampling. Bolding indicates a statistically significant difference.

Virus ¹	Clinical signs		p value
	Present (n)	Absent (n)	
<i>Megalocytivirus</i>			
Percent positive by qPCR	80.8 (120)	83.3 (60)	0.683
Percent of positive samples above BLOQ	76.3 (97)	84 (50)	0.278
Mean genome copy per mg of tissue	1.21 x 10 ⁴	3.49 x 10 ³	0.0983
95% CI of mean genome copy	4.45 x 10 ³ – 3.27 x 10 ⁴	1.42 x 10 ³ – 8.57 x 10 ³	
Percent positive by histopathology	66.7 (120)	38.3 (60)	0.0003
NNV			
Percent positive by qPCR	55 (120)	56.7 (60)	0.832
Percent of positive samples above BLOQ	45.5 (66)	44.1 (34)	0.895
Mean genome copy per mg of tissue	2.47 x 10 ³	1.74 x 10 ³	0.670
95% CI of mean genome copy	7.91 x 10 ² – 7.74 x 10 ³	4.69 x 10 ² – 6.48 x 10 ³	
Percent positive by histopathology	0 (120)	0 (60)	0.999

1165 ¹ BLOQ: below the level of quantification

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3.4.4 Proportion of fish with MCV infection

MCV was detected at all farms and in all affected populations, in both fish with and without clinical signs (Supplemental Table S3.4). Approximately 80-83% of all fish were positive for MCV by qPCR. There were no differences in the proportion of fish infected with MCV and the mean genome copy number when comparing fish with and without clinical signs (Table 3.3). Two-thirds of fish with clinical signs had histopathological lesions consistent with disease caused by MVC infection, which was a significantly higher proportion than those without clinical signs (38%) (Table 3.3). The estimated true prevalence for the presence of ISKNV histopathology lesions in fish with and without clinical signs is 94.4% (95% CI 79–100) and 47.2% (95% CI 27–70), respectively. Megalocytic inclusion bearing cells were observed in samples of fish from all populations (Supplemental Table S3.4) and were found in multiple organs including the anterior and posterior kidney, spleen, and liver. Multiple stages of megalocyte formation were observed with early stages associated with hypertrophied cells and late stages also associated with necrotic cells (Figure 3.2). In the anterior and posterior kidneys, megalocytes were observed in glomeruli, rarely in renal tubules and frequently in haematopoietic cells. In the liver, megalocytes were found in hepatocytes and were observed in blood vessels. Large numbers of megalocytes were observed in the spleen, predominantly in red pulp areas containing haematopoietic cells. Megalocytes were often found in the sub-endothelial cells of blood vessels in all observed organs.

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1186 **Figure 3.2.** Megalocytic inclusion bearing cells in (A) infected anterior kidney (from Population 7). Multiple

1187 stages of megalocytes (white arrows: early stage, black arrows: late stage of megalocytes) were observed

1188 in anterior kidney associated with necrosis. (B) normal anterior kidney of grouper without clinical signs

1189 (Population 10). Scale bars = 50 μ m.

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1191 **3.4.5 Metagenomic sequencing for unknown pathogens**

1192 The sequencing data provided 5.5 to 6.2 million 150 bp paired end reads per sample. Host genome
1193 depletion using genomic data from other fish species only reduced the number of reads by 1-3% (data not
1194 shown). Comparing two taxonomic labelling methods, BLAST+ method gave better accuracy after manual
1195 checking using BLASTN. Kaiju gave more diverse result compared to BLAST+ (Supplemental Table S3.6).
1196 BLASTN identified the virus species ISKNV (genus *Megalocytivirus*) as the only virus present and it was
1197 detected in all samples (Supplemental Table S3.5). There were matches for a small number of potentially
1198 pathogenic bacteria in some of the samples including *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus* spp., *Pseudomonas*
1199 spp., *Enterococcus* spp., and *Clostridium* sp. that were not considered to be relevant to the disease
1200 process. No internal parasites were identified (Supplemental Table S3.5).

1201 **3.4.6 Characterisation of the MCV genome**

1202 A full length genome sequence of MCV was obtained as a single contig from two samples, ID# 3-9
1203 (Genbank accession number MW557381) and ID# 7-10 (accession number MW464172) (Supplemental
1204 Table S3.2). Partial MCV genomes were obtained from two samples (Supplemental Table S3.2.; ID # 6-1
1205 and 12-12) which covered 25% (fully and partially covered 1 and 81 ORFs, respectively) and 49% (fully and
1206 partially covered 5 and 106 ORFs, respectively) of the MCV genome. The other four samples had sequence
1207 matches to MCV with less than 10% genome coverage. The size of the full length genomes was 110,919
1208 bp and 110,961 bp with the average depth of coverage being 164 and 307 times, respectively. The full
1209 genome samples had 99.9% nucleotide similarity and BLASTN showed that both full length genomes had
1210 99.9% nucleotide similarity with ISKNV (AF371960.1) and 99.5% with ISKNV strain RSIV-Ku (KT781098.1).
1211 The partial genomes had MCP genes similarity of 100% (ID# 12-12) and 99.3% (ID# 6-1) to ISKNV
1212 (AF371960.1) and ISKNV strain RSIV-Ku (KT781098.1). Phylogenetic analysis confirmed that the fish were

1213 infected with ISKNV rather than RSIV (Figure 3.3). Genomes from both samples had 122 predicted genes
1214 and the sequence identity of predicted amino acid sequence was 100% for all genes.

1226 **Figure 3.3.** Phylogenetic tree for representative genotypes of the ISKNV species of megalocytiviruses and
 1227 the hybrid grouper ISKNV isolate (this study, ID # 3-9 and 7-10 Supplemental Table S3.5), calculated by
 1228 the maximum likelihood method with the general time reversible model and 1000 bootstraps. Initial
 1229 tree(s) for the heuristic search were obtained automatically by applying Neighbour-Join and BioNJ
 1230 algorithms to a matrix of pairwise distances estimated using the Maximum Composite Likelihood (MCL)
 1231 approach, and then selecting the topology with superior log likelihood value. A discrete Gamma
 1232 distribution was used to model evolutionary rate differences among sites (5 categories, +G, parameter =
 1233 0.2099). The scale bar indicates substitution rate per site. Whole genome sequences were used for the
 1234 analysis excluding gaps. There was a total of 66,660 positions in the final dataset. Evolutionary analyses
 1235 were conducted in MEGA X.

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3.5 Discussion

The main pathogen responsible for the acute mass mortality events in hybrid groupers was ISKNV. A high proportion of fish (80–83%) were infected with ISKNV regardless of the presence of clinical signs within targeted samples from affected populations. There was histopathological confirmation of disease caused by ISKNV infection in 67% and 38% of fish with and without clinical signs, respectively. The true prevalence was estimated to be 94% (95% CI 79–100) for the presence of ISKNV lesions in fish with clinical signs. A range of clinical and pathological presentations represented the varying stages of pathogenesis in each population. This is consistent with the sensitivity of histopathology and the proportion of fish that demonstrate lesions with acute infection (Rimmer et al., 2017; Go and Whittington, 2019). This study demonstrated the importance of a sampling framework that accessed a sufficient sample size and included fish from different stages of disease. This together with a multi-modal diagnostic approach, identified relevant lesions and infections considering that the course of infection and pathology is asynchronous in individual fish. Fish identified with clinical signs were likely to be in the late stages of pathogenesis and had evidence of necrosis associated with megalocytes. Fish with clinical signs had a significantly higher likelihood of having fin erosion, green discolouration, pale haematopoietic organs, small liver, and splenomegaly. Fish without clinical signs had a statistically higher likelihood of having a two-toned or patchy discoloured liver and were considered to be in the early stages of the disease. NNV was detected by qPCR at all farms and in all populations with just over half of the fish infected. However, there was no histopathological evidence of disease caused by this virus and the infection was considered subclinical. The ectoparasites, *Z. arugamensis* and *B. epinepheli* were consistently found during the study and these coinfections may have been a contributing factor to the mortality events due to ISKNV. High throughput sequencing contributed to the diagnostic process by identification and genotyping of ISKNV. No other DNA viruses were identified using this method. Potentially pathogenic bacteria were identified,

1259 however, in the absence of relevant histopathological lesions, the findings were considered least likely to
1260 have caused the high mortality disease.

1261 Farmers reported the mortality events began two to four weeks after the fish were transferred to sea
1262 cages. Fish may have arrived at the farm infected with ISKNV or it was newly acquired upon transfer to
1263 the sea cage. Either scenario is equally likely as these pathogens are endemic to the region and have
1264 persistent infections (Jitrakorn et al., 2020; Sah Putra et al., 2020). ISKNV and NNV were both detected in
1265 juvenile grouper at nurseries in Indonesia in a case where NNV was the cause of disease and ISKNV was
1266 subclinical (Sah Putra et al., 2020). The source of ISKNV infection at the sea cages could have been from
1267 horizontal transmission from infected grouper or wild fish (Wang et al., 2007) or from the feeding of low
1268 value trash fish (Lajimin et al., 2015).

1269 In this study, the histopathological examination was critical to assign an aetiological diagnosis when
1270 subclinical viral infections were present. Due to the lack of evidence of brain or retinal lesions (true
1271 prevalence was <2.4%), it was concluded that NNV was least likely to be the cause of the high mortality
1272 disease. NNV damages nerve cells in the retina and brain leading to abnormal of swimming and vision loss
1273 and is often associated with epidemic losses in larval fish (Ma et al., 2012). Mortality up to 100% was
1274 reported in the 1–2 month-old juvenile of *Epinephelus fuscogutatus* and *Epinephelus akaara* (Chi et al.,
1275 1997) and generally declines with increasing age as observed in Atlantic halibut (*Hippoglossus*
1276 *hippoglossus*) (Johansen et al., 2004), barramundi (*Lates calcarifer*) (Hick et al., 2011) and Australian bass
1277 (*Macquaria novemaculeata*) (Jaramillo et al., 2019). However, NNV was reported to cause mortalities in
1278 up to 50% of market size fish (500– 1800 g) in sevenband grouper *Epinephelus septemfasciatus* (Fukuda
1279 et al., 1996) and sea bass, *Dicentrarchus labrax* (Le Breton et al., 1997). Further, NNV was found to be the
1280 cause of disease outbreaks in juvenile orange-spotted grouper (*E. coioides*) in the nursery stage of
1281 production in Aceh, Indonesia (Sah Putra et al., 2020). Given that the duration of NNV persistence is poorly
1282 understood, it is essential to pair histopathology from a targeted sampling strategy with the results of

1283 molecular testing to identify relevant disease processes. The recent development of a cell culture system
1284 for dual propagation of NNV and ISKNV will support studies to investigate host-pathogen interactions and
1285 vaccine development (Jitrakorn et al., 2020).

1286 The ectoparasites, *Z. arugamensis* and *Benedenia* sp. were detected during the mortality event. Both are
1287 considered common in grouper production in Southeast Asia (Rückert et al., 2009; Kua et al., 2010).
1288 Weekly to fortnightly freshwater bath treatments are used routinely in grouper aquaculture in Indonesia
1289 to reduce the burden of *Benedenia* sp. (Rückert et al., 2009). *Z. arugamensis* was detected in all
1290 populations sampled with the farmers suggesting this is a new parasite in this area of Indonesia. Previous
1291 research has shown that the feeding of low value 'trash' fish was the major transmission route for
1292 ectoparasites such as *Z. arugamensis* in grouper aquaculture (Rückert et al., 2009). Leech larvae were
1293 found on the gills of *Upeneus vittatus*, a trash fish species in sea cages in Lampung, Indonesia (Rückert et
1294 al., 2009). *U. vittatus* was the main trash fish used in grouper aquaculture in north Bali (data not shown).
1295 The use of commercial pellets as food can significantly reduce the risk of parasite transmission in grouper
1296 aquaculture (Rückert et al., 2009). However, there are recognized limitations with the quality and
1297 availability of commercial feed for marine fish in Indonesia and the difficulty in adapting grouper to eat
1298 pellets (Rimmer and Glamuzina, 2019).

1299 From the workshops with the farmers, they reported that some fish has green discolouration on the body
1300 and eyes. During the study, we observed the application of malachite green to the freshwater bath as a
1301 treatment for the leech infestation. The use of malachite green in aquaculture has been banned due to
1302 human health hazards in Europe (EFSA, 2016), Australia (AQIS, 2008) and the USA (FDA, 2019). Malachite
1303 green can be highly toxic to fish and is known to cause pathological changes in the gills including the
1304 separation of epithelial cells, leukocyte infiltration, and lamellar cell necrosis (Sudova et al., 2007).
1305 Malachite green accumulates and persists in skin, muscle, and organs in fish in a coloured and non-
1306 coloured form. The coloured form has been detected in rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*) and channel

1307 catfish (*Ictalurus punctatus*) muscle for at least 5 and 14 days following a 1 hr bath with malachite green,
1308 respectively (Sudova et al., 2007). In our study, the green discolouration observed on the skin and eyes
1309 was presumed to have been caused by the repeated weekly to fortnightly treatments with malachite
1310 green but the extent to which potential malachite green toxicity contributed to clinical signs was not
1311 determined.

1312 Effective disease control is vital for aquaculture to stop the spread of infectious pathogens and reduce the
1313 burden of disease on aquatic farming systems. Currently, there are a diverse range of diagnostic tools
1314 used to detect aquatic pathogens in fish and the environment including traditional (e.g. culture,
1315 microscopy), immunological and molecular methods (Adams and Thompson, 2011). However, a
1316 combination of methods is often required for a definitive diagnosis of disease that is complemented with
1317 histopathology (Adams and Thompson, 2011). One example is the disease syndrome known as heart and
1318 skeletal muscle inflammation in Atlantic salmon that emerged in Norway in 1999 (Palacios et al., 2010).
1319 The pathogen responsible, *Piscine orthoreovirus* was identified a decade later using unbiased sequencing
1320 techniques (Palacios et al., 2010), but not before the virus spread to other significant salmon farming
1321 industries in Scotland, Chile and Canada (Di Cicco et al., 2017). Unbiased sequencing which was once cost
1322 prohibitive is now a complementary tool accessible for pathogen identification during a disease
1323 investigation and will assist in timely identification of appropriate biosecurity measures. This method will
1324 have the greatest impact for investigating disease events with mixed or coinfections and to identify novel
1325 or emerging pathogens for which PCR assays are non-existent or suboptimal. From our study, unbiased
1326 sequencing identified that ISKNV was the genotype responsible for the mortality event after using a qPCR
1327 assay that did not differentiate between ISKNV and RSIV. Unbiased sequencing for pathogen detection
1328 can also be considered for outbreak investigations in remote areas or areas with limited access to
1329 veterinary diagnostic laboratories as samples can be easily preserved at the farm.

1330 ISKNV and the other closely related MCV genotypes (i.e. RSIV and TRBIV) are aquatic pathogens with
1331 increasing global distribution and a broad host range (Hick et al., 2016a). The host range includes fish
1332 species from a variety of habits (Wang et al., 2007; Dong et al., 2017; Rimmer et al., 2017; Tsai et al., 2020)
1333 and with a variety of uses including species critical to food security (He et al., 2001; Subramaniam et al.,
1334 2016), those used for pets (Rimmer et al., 2015; Koda et al., 2018) and those of high conservation value
1335 (Rimmer et al., 2017; Go and Whittington, 2019). It is now known that MCVs were circulating in
1336 ornamental fish species in the late 1980s, which precedes the first outbreak in mandarin fish in 1994 ca.
1337 The early detection of MCVs from ornamental fish mostly originated from Southeast Asia (Go et al., 2016).
1338 The international spread of MCVs may have been aided by the subclinical nature of infections (Joon et al.,
1339 2008; Rimmer et al., 2015) and a lack of effective pre-border disease surveillance polices (Whittington and
1340 Chong, 2007; Johnson et al., 2019).

1341 The targeted sampling approach used in our study combined with a thorough disease investigation
1342 identified ISKNV as the causative pathogen responsible for the mortality of hybrid groupers along the
1343 northern coast of Bali, Indonesia. Our approach identified several known pathogens including NNV and
1344 results from the high throughput sequencing did not identify any unexpected or novel pathogens. There
1345 is a need for greater understanding of the risk factors for disease caused by ISKNV and NNV in grouper
1346 aquaculture in Indonesia given the persistent and subclinical nature of these infections and endemicity to
1347 the region.

1348 **Supplemental Table S3. 1.** Molecular identification of the parasites was based on BLAST results of the DNA sequence of 18s rRNA gene amplified
 1349 with the indicated primers.

Parasite Species	Primer sequence (3'→5')	Expected product size (bp)	18s rRNA BLAST result		
			Accession no.	Similarity	No. of matched bases
<i>Benedenia epinepheli</i>	F: ACGGCTACCACATCCAGGAA R: CCACGAACTAAGAACGGCCAT	1011	EU707802.1	99%	961/964
<i>Zeylanicobdella arugamensis</i>	F: ACGGCTACCACATCCAGGAA R: TGTACAAAGGGCAGGGACGTA	1240	DQ414299.1	99%	1065/1068

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1351 **Supplemental Table S3. 2.** Summary of diagnostic observations for the individual fish selected for unbiased sequencing using Illumina Miseq.

Population ID	Clinical signs	Species	Ectoparasite identified ^{1,2}	Green discoloration	Fin Erosion	Anterior Kidney Pale	Spleen Enlarged	Posterior kidney Pale	Liver			ISKNV ³	NNV ^{3,4}
									Patchy	Pale	Reduced		
2	Present	Cantik	Absent	Absent	Absent	Absent	No	Absent	Present	Absent	Absent	2.88 x10 ⁸	0
3	Present	Cantik	Z	Absent	Absent	Absent	No	Absent	Present	Absent	Absent	4.66 x10 ⁷	BLOQ
4	Present	Cantang	Z	Present	Absent	Absent	Yes	Absent	Present	Absent	Present	5.38 x10 ⁹	0
6	Absent	Cantang	Z	Present	Absent	Absent	Yes	Absent	Present	Absent	Absent	6.70 x10 ³	BLOQ
7	Present	Cantik	Absent	Present	Present	Absent	No	Absent	Absent	Present	Absent	1.27 x10 ⁸	0
8	Present	Cantang	Absent	Present	Absent	Absent	No	Present	Present	Absent	Present	7.35 x 10 ²	0
9	Present	Cantik	Z, B	Present	Absent	Absent	No	Absent	Absent	Present	Absent	BLOQ	BLOQ
10	Present	Cantik	Absent	Present	Absent	Absent	No	Present	Present	Absent	Absent	2.68 x10 ²	0

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1353 ¹Z: *Zeylanicobdella arugamensis*

1354 ²B: *Benedenia epinepheli*

1355 ³ Genome copy number per mg of tissue

1356 ⁴ BLOQ: Below level of quantification

1357 **Supplemental Table S3. 3.** By population, the proportion of individuals with gross pathological observations for fish in which clinical signs were
 1358 present (P) or absent (A) when fish were selected from the sea cage.

Popula tion ID	Farm ID	Fin erosion		Green discolouration		Anterior kidney pale		Liver pale		Liver patchy		Liver reduced		Posterior kidney pale		Spleen enlarged	
		P	A	P	A	P	A	P	A	P	A	P	A	P	A	P	A
		1	A	9/24	2/12	23/24	8/12	0/24	0/12	3/24	7/12	17/24	5/12	18/24	2/12	1/24	0/12
2	B	1/24	1/12	9/24	3/12	0/24	0/12	0/24	0/12	24/24	12/12	0/24	0/12	0/24	0/12	0/24	0/12
3	C	0/24	0/12	21/24	6/12	2/24	0/12	10/24	0/12	14/24	12/12	0/24	0/12	5/24	0/12	4/24	2/12
4	D	0/24	0/12	20/24	7/12	2/24	0/12	2/24	0/12	22/24	12/12	1/24	0/12	0/24	0/12	9/24	0/12
5	E	6/24	1/12	19/24	6/12	6/24	0/12	8/24	1/12	16/24	11/12	0/24	0/12	8/24	0/12	4/24	1/12
6	F	1/12	0/6	12/12	6/6	2/12	1/6	6/12	4/6	6/12	2/6	1/12	0/6	4/12	1/6	2/12	3/6
7	G	9/24	2/12	23/24	9/12	3/24	0/12	16/24	0/12	8/24	12/12	0/24	0/12	2/24	0/12	8/24	0/12
8	H	2/12	1/6	12/12	2/6	0/12	1/6	4/12	3/6	8/12	3/6	4/12	0/6	6/12	2/6	0/12	1/6
9	I	0/12	0/6	11/12	1/6	2/12	0/6	5/12	1/6	7/12	5/6	0/12	0/6	4/12	0/6	0/12	0/6
10	H	3/24	0/12	24/24	7/12	9/24	3/12	12/24	3/12	12/24	9/12	1/24	0/12	10/24	2/12	4/24	0/12

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1361 **Supplemental Table S3. 4.** Results for *Megalocytivirus* qPCR and nervous necrosis virus (NNV) RT- qPCR testing by population for fish in which
 1362 clinical signs were present (P) or absent (A). The proportion of fish with histopathology consistent with disease caused by MCV (megalocytes in
 1363 multiple visceral tissues) or viral nervous necrosis disease caused by NNV infection (vacuoles in retina or brain) is also indicated.

Population	Farm ID	<i>Megalocytivirus</i> ¹						NNV ¹					
		% Positive by qPCR		Mean genome copies per mg		% Positive by histopathology		% Positive by qPCR		Mean genome copies per mg		% Positive by histopathology	
		P (12)	A (6)	P	A	P (12)	A (6)	P (12)	A (6)	P	A	P (12)	A (6)
1	A	100	100	3.06 x10 ²	2.11 x10 ²	67	33	92	100	9.07 x10 ²	7.78 x10 ²	0	0
2	B	75	100	3.21 x10 ⁷	2.67 x10 ⁴	25	33	50	50	6.69 x10 ²	6.04 x10 ³	0	0
3	C	83	100	6.59 x10 ⁶	1.13 x10 ³	50	0	58	0	9.30 x10 ⁶	0	0	0
4	D	100	100	5.43 x10 ⁸	2.98 x10 ⁷	50	50	8	17	5.01 x10 ⁴	BLOQ	0	0
5	E	58	100	BLOQ	1.54 x10 ⁴	33	0	83	83	4.24 x10 ²	1.59 x10 ²	0	0
6	F	100	100	9.29 x10 ³	5.51 x10 ³	83	83	75	83	BLOQ	BLOQ	0	0
7	G	67	100	3.57 x10 ⁷	1.73 x10 ⁴	83	33	33	33	BLOQ	1.42 x10 ²	0	0
8	H	83	67	1.62 x10 ³	1.17 x10 ⁴	83	67	50	83	3.34 x 10 ⁴	1.63 x10 ⁵	0	0
9	I	92	17	1.06 x10 ²	4.09 x10 ²	92	17	42	50	1.30 x10 ⁴	BLOQ	0	0
10	H	50	17	3.78 x10 ²	5.14 x10 ²	100	67	58	67	2.12 x10 ⁶	1.29 x10 ³	0	0

1364 ¹ below the level of quantification

1365

1366 **Supplemental Table S3. 5.** BLASTN results for contigs generated from de novo assembly of high throughput sequencing. Data are the number of
 1367 contigs and (contig size) with BLASTN matches according to the following parameters: Bit score of 50, sequence identity 80%, and sequence
 1368 length of 500bp were applied as cut off points. Many contigs mapped as fish genomic DNA after depletion of host DNA by mapping to reference
 1369 fish genomes for different species. Consistent identification of ISKNV in targeted samples provided support for involvement of this pathogen in
 1370 the disease syndrome and there was no evidence of a novel or unexpected pathogen.

Sample ID	BLASTN results							
	Host DNA	ISKNV	<i>Escherichia coli</i> plasmid	<i>Staphylococcus spp.</i>	<i>Pseudomonas spp.</i>	<i>Enterococcus spp.</i>	<i>Clostridium sp.</i>	Unidentified
3-9	748	1 (110,919)	18 (531-1,380 bp)	0	0	0	0	1
6-1	5348	3 (545, 531, 503 bp)	10 (856-1,092 bp)	44 (1,020 -1,994 bp)	0	0	0	10
7-10	12779	1 (110,961 bp)	1 (839 bp)	2 (839, 872 bp)	0	1 (840 bp)	1 (757 bp)	0
11-15	10767	1 (531 bp)	1 (1,730 bp)	0	0	0	0	0
12-12	16048	1 (1,020 bp)	0	0	0	1 (972 bp)	0	0
14-5	10877	1 (503 bp)	0	0	0	0	0	0
15-4	9722	1 (503 bp)	1 (749 bp)	3 (500, 513, 532 bp)	2 (503, 642 bp)	0	0	10
16-1	9163	1 (1,020 bp)	0	0	0	0	0	0

1371

1372 **Supplemental Table S3. 6.** Taxonomic identification of the translated amino acid sequences from the
 1373 Illumina reads after host genome depletion against Bacteria, Archaea and Viruses BLAST nr database
 1374 using Kaiju web-based program. Numbers in the table indicate the total number of 150 bp reads
 1375 mapped at family level.

KAIJU identification		Sample ID						
		3-9	6-1	7-10	11-15	12-12	14-5	16-1
Unclassified		7,840,029	7,628,951	5,488,137	553,494	6,060,256	7,674,496	5,415,824
Virus	<i>Badnavirus</i>	30	13	217	28	199	223	189
	<i>Retroviridae</i>	106	1,251	1,144	164	1,118	1,389	951
	<i>Iridoviridae</i> (ISKNV)	101,180	11	189,873	2	426	11	4
	<i>Herpesviridae</i>	-	67	-	19	111	84	65
	<i>Alloherpesviridae</i>	-	23	-	5	41	25	28
	<i>Phycodnaviridae</i>	-	9	-	11	77	62	86
	<i>Poxviridae</i>	-	47	-	10	76	71	64
	Others	338	170	44,197	56	474	508	317
Bacteria	<i>Pseudomonadales</i>	68,222	148,476	19,754	811	22,178	26,156	19,590
	<i>Enterobacterales</i>	1,902	4,442	3,314	709	4,445	5,076	3,472
	<i>Burkholderiales</i>	2,337	21,791	8,666	985	15,209	22,068	8,415
	<i>Firmicutes</i>	35,266	233,332	43,922	2,925	59,780	235,919	37,391
	<i>Actinobacteria</i>	2,066	16,674	3,254	451	4,224	17,223	3,081
	<i>Rhizobiales</i>	14,458	1,240	421	1,711	908	1,323	1,240
	<i>Campylobacterales</i>	-	1,513	993	149	1,237	91,423	1,513
	<i>Vibrionales</i>	3,939	779	-	-	737	840	779
	Others	33,534	10,219	14,963	2,170	20,487	52,751	16,456
Archaea		1,382	218,138	8,094	471	6,867	218,977	5,332

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1378 **4. Chapter 4. Genotypic characterization of *Infectious spleen and kidney necrosis virus (ISKNV)* in**
1379 **Southeast Asian aquaculture**

1380 **4.1 Summary**

1381 *Infectious spleen and kidney necrosis virus (ISKNV)*, genus *Megalocytivirus* (MCV) can cause disease with
1382 high mortality in many freshwater and marine fish species and is an emerging threat to aquaculture. ISKNV
1383 was first reported in Southeast Asia, but its detection in ornamental fish with subclinical infection may
1384 contribute to increasing global distribution. The species ISKNV includes distinct genotypes: red seabream
1385 iridovirus (RSIV), turbot reddish body iridovirus (TRBIV) and the ISKNV genotype. Despite the distinct
1386 properties for each genotype, there is an increasing overlap in the geographic distribution and recognized
1387 range of susceptible hosts. To better understand disease caused by various ISKNV genotypes, a nucleic
1388 acid hybrid capture enrichment method prior to sequencing was used to characterize whole genomes
1389 from archived clinical specimens of aquaculture and ornamental fish from SE Asia (n=16). The method was
1390 suitable for viral loads from 2.50×10^4 - 4.58×10^9 ISKNV genome copies mg^{-1} and produced identical results
1391 for samples with high viral load that could be obtained by direct sequencing from tissue samples. Very
1392 high similarity existed within ISKNV genomes from diverse locations, environments, and hosts within the
1393 established genotype classifications (14 ISKNV genotype Clade 1 genomes >98.81% nucleotide similarity).
1394 Meanwhile, there were considerable genomic differences between genotypes obtained from the same
1395 time and location (RSIV and ISKNV from grouper, Indonesia with 87.50-88.14% similarity). Gene-by-gene
1396 analysis with representative ISKNV genomes identified 59 core genes within the species, whilst the 14
1397 Clade 1 ISKNV genomes in this study had 92-105 of 122 predicted genes with 100% amino acid identity.
1398 Despite high similarity, phylogenetic analyses using single nucleotide polymorphisms indicated the
1399 potential for genomic epidemiology as isolates were differentiated based on host species, country of
1400 origin and time of collection. Whole genome studies for ISKNV and other MCVs will provide information
1401 to enhance disease control in aquaculture.

1402 4.2 Introduction

1403 The family *Iridoviridae* contains large double-stranded DNA viruses that are classified within five genera
1404 including *Megalocytivirus* (MCV) which encompasses two species, *Infectious spleen and kidney necrosis*
1405 *virus* (ISKNV) and *Scale drop disease virus* (SDDV) (Chinchar et al., 2017). *Infectious spleen and kidney*
1406 *necrosis virus* (ISKNV) represents three genotypes: ISKNV (genotype), turbot reddish body iridovirus
1407 (TRBIV) and red sea bream iridovirus (RSIV). The genotype RSIV has caused mass mortality in multiple
1408 species of marine fish, including red sea bream (*Pagrus major*) in Japan since 1990 (Inouye et al., 1992;
1409 Matsuoka et al., 1996). Fish infected with ISKNV develop characteristic histopathological lesions
1410 characterized by megalocytes which are enlarged cells containing basophilic cytoplasmic inclusions in
1411 connective and perivascular tissues across a wide variety of organs, reviewed in Hick et al. (2016a). The
1412 disease manifests with non-specific clinical signs including anorexia, lethargy, gill pallor, discolouration,
1413 and internal or external haemorrhages (He et al., 2000; Kurita et al., 2002; Shi et al., 2010; Kurita and
1414 Nakajima, 2012; Go et al., 2016; Dong et al., 2017; Fusianto et al., 2021). Fish of all ages can be affected
1415 with mortality from 20% - 100% in aquaculture settings (Kurita and Nakajima, 2012; Subramaniam et al.,
1416 2012). In addition to clinical disease, ISKNV has been identified in subclinical infections in multiple hosts
1417 both marine and freshwater environments (Rimmer et al., 2015; Sah Putra et al., 2020). The broad host
1418 range of ISKNV includes over 50 species of fish spanning 13 families of the order Perciformes including
1419 marine and freshwater fish (Crane and Moody, 2018; OIE, 2019b).

1420 The megalocytiviruses have icosahedral virions 115 to 200 nm diameter containing a linear double-
1421 stranded DNA genome which is 110-112 kb for ISKNV (Chinchar et al., 2017). Phylogenetic characterization
1422 of ISKNV based on the major capsid protein (MCP) gene and the ATPase genes has identified a consistent
1423 genotypic differentiation between three genotypes named ISKNV, RSIV, and TRBIV (Go et al., 2016). These
1424 genotypes, and two clades within each, have been supported by analysis of increasing numbers of

1425 complete ISKNV genomes providing a sound nomenclature for classification of isolates within the species
1426 (Koda et al., 2019).

1427 The continued emergence of ISKNV is highlighted by the breakdown in the distinct host-geographical
1428 niche that was once attributed to the three genotypes. The RSIV genotype associated with marine fishes
1429 in Japan (Kurita et al., 2002) was also detected in Korea (Do et al., 2004) and China (Zhang et al., 2013).
1430 Subsequently, the range has expanded with RSIV related disease in marine fish in the Dominican Republic
1431 (Koda et al., 2019), barramundi (*Lates calcarifer*) in estuary-based cages in India (Girisha et al., 2020) and
1432 mandarin fish in China in locations previously impacted by the ISKNV genotype (Dong et al., 2013b). The
1433 ISKNV genotype identified initially in freshwater aquaculture (He et al., 2000) is the most globally
1434 widespread, impacting freshwater and marine fish in the Southeast Asian countries including China (Zhu
1435 et al., 2021), Indonesia (Mahardika et al., 2008; Sah Putra et al., 2020; Sukenda et al., 2020; Fusiando et
1436 al., 2021), Malaysia (Razak et al., 2014; Subramaniam et al., 2014), Vietnam (Dong et al., 2017), and
1437 Thailand (Baoprasertkul and Kaenchan, 2019). Reports of the increasing global distribution of the ISKNV-
1438 genotype include North America (Subramaniam et al., 2016), South America (de Lucca Maganha et al.,
1439 2018), Africa (Ramírez-Paredes et al., 2020), Europe (Jung-Schroers et al., 2016), India (Girisha et al., 2021)
1440 and Australia (Rimmer et al., 2015). In recent years, there has also been an expansion of the host range
1441 for ISKNV, most notably affecting several important aquaculture sectors. For example, tilapia
1442 (*Oreochromis niloticus*) is a freshwater species commonly farmed in 127 countries that is critical to
1443 domestic food security in many developing countries and represents just over 5% of global aquaculture
1444 production (Cai et al., 2019). Epidemics due to ISKNV have been recorded in farmed tilapia in the USA
1445 (Subramaniam et al., 2016), Africa (Ramírez-Paredes et al., 2020) and Thailand (Suebsing et al., 2016).
1446 Although TRBIV was initially considered to be restricted to flatfish in China and South Korea (Shi et al.,
1447 2010), it has been reported in retrospective studies of ornamental fish as early as 1986 (Go et al., 2016;

1448 Koda et al., 2018). More recently, TRBIV was the cause of disease in barramundi resulting in severe
1449 mortality of up to 90% at 35 farms in Taiwan (Tsai et al., 2020).

1450 The World Organization for Animal Health (OIE) recognized the importance of controlling disease caused
1451 by ISKNV by listing red sea bream iridovirus disease as notifiable, under a definition including infection
1452 with RSIV and ISKNV-like viruses (OIE, 2019b). There are several barriers restricting the measures to
1453 minimize the spread and disease impacts of ISKNV. First, the nomenclature is confusing with many virus
1454 names reported using the host fish and iridovirus descriptor without reference to the ISKNV species
1455 designation (Chinchar et al., 2017). This excessive array of virus names within ISKNV overlaps with viruses
1456 from different genera such as *Singapore grouper iridovirus (Ranavirus)*. Meanwhile, the use of the generic
1457 term ‘megaloctiviruses’ to refer to all genotypes of ISKNV e.g. (Crane and Moody, 2018) is less
1458 appropriate with the emergence of another pathogenic megalocytivirus species, *Scale drop disease virus*
1459 (de Groof et al., 2015). Second, there is limited validation of high throughput diagnostic tests suitable for
1460 identification and differentiation of each genotype of ISKNV (OIE, 2019b). Third, ISKNV is frequently
1461 refractory to isolation in cell culture which limits the options for characterization of isolates. Improved
1462 disease control and effective policy to limit the spread of ISKNV requires further evaluation of the genomic
1463 diversity within the ISKNV species. Genomic epidemiology can evaluate the pathways for spread of ISKNV
1464 that contribute to the numerous present reports describing the first detections of ISKNV in new hosts and
1465 locations e.g. Girisha et al. (2021) and Sukenda et al. (2020). Evaluation of the complete genome of ISKNV
1466 might also identify factors that determine host and geographical range and influence viral phenotype,
1467 thereby influencing the spectrum of clinical outcomes from subclinical infection to severe disease
1468 (Shinmoto et al., 2009).

1469 The objective of this study was to evaluate a hybrid capture enrichment method to determine the
1470 complete genome sequence of ISKNV directly from clinical specimens and to evaluate genomic diversity
1471 of ISKNV in archived specimens representing a broad range of host, location, and clinical status of fish in

1472 SE Asia. Improved understanding of the genomic diversity of megalocytiviruses is important to understand
1473 disease caused by ISKNV and to inform disease control measures including biosecurity and vaccination.

1474 **4.3 Methods**

1475 **4.3.1 Samples of ISKNV infected fish**

1476 Specimens were recruited into the study to represent the diversity of ISKNV in the laboratory archive
1477 collected from SE Asian locations between 2011 and 2018 (Table 4.1). Samples were selected to maximize
1478 diversity with respect to the country of origin, host species, year of collection, and to compare samples
1479 from related disease outbreaks in grouper aquaculture. Most samples were archived as nucleic acids that
1480 were purified from fish with megalocytivirus infection identified by PCR and stored at -80°C (n=12). These
1481 had been prepared by homogenizing visceral samples by bead beating (Rimmer et al., 2012) and were
1482 extracted using the MagMax-96 Viral Isolation Kit (ThermoFisher) according to the directions of the
1483 manufacturer (Samples 1-11 and 16). An additional 4 samples were prepared from visceral samples
1484 preserved in 80% ethanol (Samples 12-15) using a phenol-chloroform precipitation method for nucleic
1485 acid purification described below (Green and Sambrook, 2012).

1486 **Table 4. 1.** Description of samples used to evaluate ISKNV genomic diversity in Southeast Asian aquaculture.

Sample ID	Collection details		Host		Fish type, habitat	Clinical status	MCV qPCR result		Reference
	Country of origin	Year	Species	Common name			Ct (average)	MCV genome copies / mg	
1	Indonesia	2011	<i>Trichogaster leeri</i>	Pearl gourami	Ornamental, freshwater	Subclinical	20.38	7.81 x 10 ⁷	(Rimmer et al., 2015)
2	Thailand	2011	<i>Trichogaster trichopterus</i>	Blue/gold gourami	Ornamental, freshwater	Subclinical	25.06	2.92 x 10 ⁶	(Rimmer et al., 2015)
3	Indonesia	2015	<i>Pterapogon kauderni</i>	Banggai cardinal fish	Ornamental, Marine	Subclinical	17.9	4.42 x 10 ⁸	(Becker et al., 2017)
4	Indonesia	2014	♀ <i>Epinephelus fuscoguttatus</i> x ♂ <i>E. polyphkadion</i>	Hybrid grouper Cantik	Food fish, Marine	Subclinical	28.57	2.50 x 10 ⁴	(Rimmer et al., 2019)
5	Indonesia	2014	♀ <i>E. fuscoguttatus</i> x ♂ <i>E. polyphkadion</i>	Hybrid grouper Cantik	Food fish, Marine	Subclinical	21.84	2.80 x 10 ⁷	(Rimmer et al., 2019)
6	Thailand	2015	<i>Trichopodus trichopterus</i>	Three spot gourami	Ornamental, freshwater	Subclinical	14.57	4.58 x 10 ⁹	(Becker et al., 2017)
7	Malaysia	2015	<i>Xiphophorus helleri</i>	Green swordtail	Ornamental, freshwater	Subclinical	21.16	4.50 x 10 ⁷	(Becker et al., 2017)
8	Thailand	2015	<i>Trichogaster lalius</i>	Dwarf gourami	Ornamental, freshwater	Subclinical	16.2	1.46 x 10 ⁹	(Becker et al., 2017)
9	Sri Lanka	2015	<i>Xiphophorus maculatus</i>	Southern platyfish	Ornamental, freshwater	Subclinical	19.22	1.76 x 10 ⁸	(Becker et al., 2017)
10	Indonesia	2015	♀ <i>E. fuscoguttatus</i> x ♂ <i>E. polyphkadion</i>	Hybrid grouper	Food fish, Marine	Subclinical	24.49	2.72 x 10 ⁷	(Sah Putra et al., 2020)
11	SE Asia	2010	<i>Trichogaster lalius</i>	Dwarf gourami	Ornamental, freshwater	Clinical	18.52	2.86 x 10 ⁸	(Rimmer et al., 2017)
12	Indonesia	2016	♀ <i>E. fuscoguttatus</i> x ♂ <i>E. lanceolatus</i>	Hybrid grouper Cantang	Food fish, Marine	Clinical	14.71	4.15 x 10 ⁹	(Fusianto et al., 2021)
13	Indonesia	2018	<i>Osphronemus goramy</i>	Giant gourami	Food fish, fresh-water	Clinical	24.65	3.91 x 10 ⁶	This study
14	Indonesia	2018	<i>Osphronemus goramy</i>	Giant gourami	Food fish, fresh-water	Clinical	16.51	1.17 x 10 ⁹	This study
15	Indonesia	2016	♀ <i>E. fuscoguttatus</i> x ♂ <i>E. polyphkadion</i>	Hybrid grouper Cantik	Food fish, Marine	Clinical	19.33	1.63 x 10 ⁸	(Fusianto et al., 2021)
16	Indonesia	2014	♀ <i>E. fuscoguttatus</i> x ♂ <i>E. polyphkadion</i>	Hybrid grouper Cantik	Food fish, Marine	Subclinical	24.49	4.37 x 10 ⁶	(Rimmer et al., 2019)

1487 * The isolate was the 4th passage which used as a positive control in Murray cod by Fusianto et al. (2019)

1488

4.3.2 Purification of nucleic acids and quantification of ISKNV

1489 Nucleic acids were treated to remove RNA using 4 µl DNase-free RNase A (2 µg/mL, Qiagen) with
1490 incubation at 37°C for 1 hour and then purified by ethanol precipitation. Briefly, for each volume of the
1491 nucleic acid preparation, 1/20 volume of 3M Sodium acetate and 3 volumes of absolute ethanol was
1492 added followed by overnight incubation at -20°C. Samples were centrifuged at 12,000 g for 20 min, the
1493 supernatant was discarded and 500 µL of 70% ethanol (at -20°C) was added followed by centrifugation at
1494 12,000 g for 10 min. The ethanol was removed by pipetting followed by air-drying and the DNA pellet was
1495 resuspended in 100 µL of Tris-EDTA buffer (pH 8). For the 4 samples obtained as ethanol preserved organs,
1496 a 0.5 g pool of equal parts liver, spleen, and kidney was air-dried and washed with phosphate buffered
1497 saline (PBS). The pooled organs were homogenised by grinding using plastic pestles in 360 µl RLT lysis
1498 buffer (Qiagen). Proteinase K was added (50 µL of 20 µg/mL; Sigma-Aldrich) with overnight incubation at
1499 56°C for enzymatic digestion before RNase treatment which was performed as previously described.
1500 Phenol:chloroform:isoamyl-alcohol (25:24:1) was added (400 µL) and the samples were incubated at
1501 ambient temperature for 15 min in a fume hood (Conditionaire International). The aqueous layer was
1502 collected after centrifugation at 2,000 g for 10 min and DNA was obtained by ethanol precipitation was
1503 performed as previously described. Evaluation of DNA purification was described in Chapter 2.4.3.
1504 Quantification of ISKNV genome was described in Chapter 2.4.4.

1505

4.3.3 Design of hybrid bait capture sequences

1506 A custom hybrid capture panel (SureSelect, Agilent) was designed for targeted enrichment of the whole
1507 genome of multiple genotypes of ISKNV. The design was based on 12 published ISKNV genomes: ISKNV
1508 (NCBI Acc number: AF371960 and KT781098); RSIV (AB104413, AP017456, AY779031, KT804738,
1509 KC244182, AY894343 and AY532606); and TRBIV (GQ273492, MG570132, and MG570131) and to meet
1510 the limit of the library size of the SureselectXT Custom 1Kb - 499Kb-16 samples. These genomes were

1511 aligned using MUSCLE in MEGA X (Kumar et al., 2018). Regions of the genome alignment in which the
1512 nucleotide similarity was greater than 90% were defined as conserved for the purpose of probe design.
1513 Regions of the alignment with <90% nucleotide sequence similarity in a region of 180 bp or more were
1514 considered a variable region. Hybrid capture probes (120 bases) were designed to tile across the
1515 conserved regions with 2x coverage. Additional probes were designed for each genotype within the
1516 variable regions to achieve 2x coverage of each unique genotype (Supplementary Figure S4.1). The DNA
1517 probes were designed for a melting temperature between 60-65°C. The hybrid capture probe design was
1518 evaluated *in silico* by mapping to the positive strand of each ISKNV reference genome using CLC Genomic
1519 Workbench 12 (Qiagen) with similarity and length fraction 0.9 (Supplementary Table S4.1). The bait library
1520 oligonucleotide probes were manufactured by Agilent Technologies.

1521 **4.3.4 Sequencing library preparation, hybridisation and sequencing**

1522 Sequencing library preparation and hybridization were performed at the Westmead Institute of Medical
1523 Research, Genomics Facility. Libraries were generated using the Sureselect XT HS Target Enrichment
1524 System for Illumina-Paired End Multiplexed Sequencing (Agilent Technologies) according to the
1525 instructions of the manufacturer. In brief, up to 200 ng of DNA for each sample was ultrasonically
1526 fragmented to 150-200 bp in 130 µL microtubes (Covaris) using the Covaris E220 Evolution system. The
1527 following shearing parameters were used: peak incident power = 140W; duty factor = 10%; cycles per
1528 burst = 200; treatment time = 100s. End repair and A-tailing was performed by adding 207 µl ligation
1529 buffer, 18 µl T4 DNA ligase, end repair-A Tailing buffer (144 µL) and enzyme mix (38 µL) were added with
1530 incubation at 20°C for 15 min, then 72°C for 15 min before being held at 4°C. Molecular barcode adapters
1531 were added by ligation at 20°C for 30 min. All incubation and PCR steps were performed using a Miniamp
1532 thermocycler (ThermoFisher). Samples were purified using Ampure XP beads (Beckman Coulter) with a
1533 Dynamag-96 side magnet (Thermo Fisher) according to directions to capture oligonucleotide > 100 bp.
1534 The purified, adapter-ligated libraries were amplified by a pre-capture PCR protocol with the master mix

1535 composition: 180 µL 5× Herculase II reaction buffer, 9 µL 100 mM dNTP Mix, 36 µL forward primer and 18
1536 µL Herculase II fusion DNA polymerase. The thermocycling program depended on the quantity of input
1537 DNA: 98°C for 2 min, 11 cycles of 98 °C for 30 sec, 60 °C for 30 sec and 72 °C for 1 min for samples with
1538 100-200 ng input DNA. For samples with a low input of DNA (50 ng), 12 cycles were used with final
1539 elongation at 72°C for 5 min. Amplified libraries were purified using Ampure XP beads followed by
1540 fragment size and concentration assessment on a Tapestation 4200 (Agilent) using the D1000 tape.

1541 Prepared libraries were hybridized to the target-specific capture library using the Sureselect XT HS Target
1542 Enrichment System for Illumina-Paired End Multiplexed Sequencing (Agilent Technologies) and the
1543 protocol for a target size < 3000 base pairs. Briefly, 5 µL of Sureselect XT HS Blocker Mix was added to
1544 prepared libraries and processed with a thermocycler using the following program: 95°C for 5 min, 65°C
1545 for 10 min, 65°C for 1 min, 60 cycles of 65°C 1 min and 37°C 3 sec, held at 65°C. The thermal cycling was
1546 paused at 65°C before entering the 60 cycles segment for the addition of 18 µL of 25% RNase Block
1547 solution prepared as 4.5 µL SureSelect RNase Block with 13.5 µL Nuclease-free water (NFW), 18 µL Capture
1548 Library for <3 Mb kit, 54 µL SureSelect Hybridisation buffer and 27 µL NFW and the thermal cycling process
1549 was continued. After the thermal cycler reached the 65°C hold step, the samples were transferred at room
1550 temperature to wells containing 200 µL of washed Dynabeads MyOne Streptavidin T1 magnetic beads
1551 (ThermoFisher). These were prepared earlier according to the directions of the manufacturer to capture
1552 the hybridized DNA for purification using a magnetic separator.

1553 Libraries enriched for the ISKNV target were washed using SureSelect Wash Buffers 1 and 2 according to
1554 directions before the post-capture PCR was used for amplification. The protocol for libraries <0.2 Mb
1555 required a reaction mix consisting of 250 µL NFW, 180 µL 5× Herculase II reaction buffer, 18 µL Herculase
1556 II Fusion DNA Polymerase, 9 µL 100 mM dNTP Mix, and 18 µL SureSelect Post-Capture Primer Mix. The
1557 thermocycling conditions were: 98°C for 2 min; 14 cycles of 98°C for 30 sec, 60°C for 30 sec and 72°C for
1558 1 min; 72°C for 5 min. Amplified libraries were purified using Ampure XP beads and final analysis of library

1559 size and concentration was performed on the TapeStation 4200. With the genome size 110 to 112 kb and
1560 expected coverage depth of 1000, sequencing of captured libraries was performed on one lane of an
1561 Illumina Miseq using the 300-cycle V2 kit for 150 bp paired end reads according to the manufacturer's
1562 protocol (Illumina, US).

1563 **4.3.5 Genome assembly and annotation**

1564 Illumina adaptor sequences were removed from raw sequence files and a filter for a minimum Phred score
1565 of 20 for the quality of base calls was applied using Trimmomatic (Bolger et al., 2014). The trimmed FASTQ
1566 files were paired using FASTQ joiner (Blankenberg et al., 2010). *De novo* assembly of contigs from paired
1567 FASTQ files and unpaired reads was performed with SPAdes Genome Assembler Version 3.14.1
1568 (Bankevich et al., 2012). The assembly of contigs was performed with correction on mismatches and short
1569 indels and K-mer values set to 21, 33, and 55, respectively. Genome orientation and the completeness of
1570 coverage was evaluated by mapping to published ISKNV reference genomes. The genomes were
1571 compared according to genome length, read coverage, GC content (%), and pairwise comparison after
1572 progressive alignment using CLC Genomic Workbench 12.

1573 The Genome Annotation Transfer Utility (GATU) was used to annotate assembled genomes (Tcherepanov
1574 et al., 2006). The annotated genes and other predicted ORFs identified by GATU were included using the
1575 following criteria: (1) larger than 120 nucleotides, (2) not overlapping with another ORF by more than
1576 25%, and (3) in the case of overlapping ORFs, only the larger ORF was annotated (Koda et al., 2018). Four
1577 reference genomes were used for annotation references: Banggai cardinal fish iridovirus (BCIV)
1578 (MN432490.1) and Angelfish Iridovirus (AFIV-16) (MK689685.1) for the ISKNV genotype samples and
1579 Pompano iridovirus strain PIV2014a (MK098186.1) and RSIV strain KagYT-96 (MK689686.1) for the RSIV
1580 genotype sample.

1581 **4.3.6 Genetic and phylogenetic analysis**

1582 Assembled and annotated genomes were aligned using progressive MAUVE (Darling et al., 2010) including
1583 BCIV and AFIV-16 for comparison. Dot plots were generated using JDotter (Brodie et al., 2004) with
1584 Angelfish Iridovirus (MK689685), BCIV 2012 (MN432490) on the horizontal axis for ISKNV genotype and
1585 PIV2014a (MK098186) for the RSIV genotype. Gene to gene similarity comparison was conducted using
1586 GATU with AFIV-16 (MK689685.1) as the reference sequence for ISKNV and RSIV strain KagYT-96
1587 (MK689686) for Sample 16 (RSIV). Repeated sequences were identified through the Tandem repeats
1588 finder (<https://tandem.bu.edu/trf/trf.submit.options.html>) (Benson, 1999).

1589 Core genes of ISKNV species were identified by comparing multiple whole genomes for the ISKNV
1590 genotype (AFIV-16 MK689685, ISKNV AF371960, BCIV-2012 MN432490, ISKNV_KU1 MT128666,
1591 ISKNV_KU2 MT128667, ISKNV_RSIV-Ku KT781098, ISKNV_EFIV-2019 MW273354, ISKNV_EFIV-2018
1592 MW273353, BCIV-2017 MT926123), RSIV genotype (RSIV_RIE12-1 AP017456, PIV2014a MK098186, RSIV
1593 strain KagYT-96 MK689686, GSIV-K1 KT804738, RBIV-C1 KC244182, RBIV-KOR-TY1 AY532606, OSGIV
1594 AY894343) and TRBIV genotype (TRBIV GQ273492, TSGIV MG570132, SACIV MG570131). Gene to gene
1595 comparison was performed using GATU which used NEEDLE (Rice et al., 2000) to obtain similarity at the
1596 amino acid level. Genes with a similarity $\geq 95\%$ for the three genotypes were defined as ISKNV core genes.

1597 Each core gene was processed to BLASTp (<https://blast.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov>) to identify the sequence of
1598 corresponding genes in GenBank. The amino acid sequences for core genes were aligned using Clustal-W
1599 and combined into a single alignment using CLC Genomic Workbench 12. IQ-TREE (Nguyen et al., 2015)
1600 was used to construct a phylogenetic tree from this alignment. The analysis used 1000 bootstraps through
1601 ultrafast bootstrap (Minh et al., 2013) after applying the best model finder using ModelFinder
1602 (Kalyaanamoorthy et al., 2017) and excluding gaps on the analysis.

1603 An SNP alignment was build using a CSI Phylogeny 1.4 web tool with default setting
1604 (<https://cge.cbs.dtu.dk/services/CSIPhylogeny/>) (Kaas et al., 2014). IQ-TREE was used for phylogenetic
1605 analysis of this SNP alignment as previously described. Geographic visualisation was conducted using
1606 Mapbox© studio (<https://studio.mapbox.com>).

1607 **4.3.7 Comparison of hybrid capture enrichment with direct sequencing of** 1608 **clinical specimens**

1609 The hybrid capture enrichment method was compared with a direct Illumina MiSeq approach to
1610 sequencing nucleic acids purified from the clinical specimens according to the method described by
1611 Fusianto et al. (2021). Two samples with a higher concentration of ISKNV were able to be used for the
1612 comparison (Sample ID 12 and 15). The number of mapped ISKNV specific reads, depth of coverage,
1613 genome coverage and identification of SNPs were compared for both methods using CLC Genomic
1614 Workbench 12.

1615 **4.4 Results**

1617 **4.4.1 Hybrid bait capture design**

1618 The library design contained probes that targeted conserved regions (589), and the less conserved regions
1619 of each genotype i.e. ISKNV (942), RSIV (946), and TRBIV (244). The number of probes for variable regions
1620 of TRBIV was less than ideal due to the constraints of the library size that was used. *In silico* mapping of
1621 the probe library to 12 reference genomes indicated that the proportion of the genomes targeted by
1622 probes for conserved and variable regions was 42% and 58%, respectively. The average predicted
1623 coverage of reference genomes by the probes was 1.98 to 2.29 times (Supplementary Table S4.1).
1624 Variability in the coverage included up to 70 regions of zero probe coverage for intervals between 1 and
1625 299 bp for TRBIV.

1626 **4.4.2 Evaluation of hybrid capture genome enrichment methods of ISKNV**

1627 Direct sequencing of tissue homogenates and hybrid capture enrichment resulted in identical whole
1628 genome sequences for two samples which were tested using both methods (Table 4.2). Genome
1629 enrichment of the clinical samples increased read coverage more than 10 times compared to direct
1630 sequencing (Table 4.2). Enrichment was necessary to obtain a complete genome from samples with less
1631 than 1.3×10^8 copy virus per mg tissue (data not shown). Mapping the probe library to *de novo* assembled
1632 genomes showed that sequence data were generated with up to 10% mismatch between the target and
1633 probe and for regions up to 481 bp with zero coverage (Supplementary Table S4.1).

1634 **4.4.3 MCV genome assembly and annotation**

1635 The complete MCV genome was determined for all 16 samples after target enrichment using the custom
1636 SureSelect bait library. This included a range of viral genome concentration in visceral organs between 2.5
1637 $\times 10^5$ and 4.2×10^9 copies of the MCV genome per mg of tissue (Table 4.1). The genomes ranged from
1638 110,394 to 111,666 nucleotides in length with 120-122 predicted ORFs (Table 4.3). The average depth of
1639 coverage for all samples was 1144 - 4023 reads across all positions. The genomes were most closely
1640 related to the ISKNV genotype except for a single sample belonging to the RSIV genotype (Table 4.3). The
1641 genomes were complete when compared to the representative genomes for the relevant genotype.

1642

1643 **Table 4. 2.** Comparison of ISKNV genomes determined using the hybrid bait capture enrichment method compared to direct sequencing of tissue
 1644 homogenate for two samples with a high concentration of viral DNA.

Parameter	Enriched		Direct sequencing	
	Sample 15	Sample 12	Sample 15	Sample 12
Total reads after trimming	2,207,566	3,194,072	8,131,798	5,830,384
Percentage of mapped reads	97.67%	98.44%	1.63%	4.04%
Genome length	110,919	110,961	110,919	110,961
GC content (%)	54.75	54.75	54.75	54.75
Depth of coverage - Average	2,508	3,773	163	307
Maximum tr	6,385	7,525	1,822	1,169
Minimum	391	494	13	73
SNPs (Compared to direct sequencing)	0	0		

1645

1646

1647

1648 **Table 4. 3.** Characteristics of the MCV genomes determined using a hybrid capture enrichment method for fish tissue homogenates.

Sample ID	Country of origin	Year of collection	Host species	No. of predicted genes	Length (bp)	Average coverage depth	GC content (%)	GenBank Acc.	Closest published MCV genome		
									Genotype	Percent identity ^a	Acc number
1	Indonesia	2011	Pearl gourami	122	111,309	2682	54.76	MW883593	ISKNV	99.94	AF371960.1
2	Thailand	2011	Blue/gold gourami	122	110,394	2675	54.76	MW883594	ISKNV	99.97	AF371960.1
3	Indonesia	2015	Banggai cardinal fish	120	111,666	3074	54.87	MW883595	ISKNV	99.95	MN432490.1
4	Indonesia	2014	Hybrid grouper, Cantik	122	111,039	1918	54.75	MW883596	ISKNV	99.84	MK689685.1
5	Indonesia	2014	Hybrid grouper, Cantik	122	111,039	2781	54.75	MW883597	ISKNV	99.84	MK689685.1
6	Thailand	2015	Three spot gourami	122	111,351	4023	54.78	MW883599	ISKNV	99.94	AF371960.1
7	Malaysia	2015	Green swordtail	121	110,927	2661	54.68	MW883600	ISKNV	99.94	AF371960.1
8	Thailand	2015	Dwarf gourami	122	111,014	3266	54.75	MW883601	ISKNV	99.88	MK689685.1
9	Sri Lanka	2015	Southern platyfish	122	111,062	2535	54.73	MW883602	ISKNV	99.84	MK689685.1
10	Indonesia	2015	Hybrid grouper	122	111,138	2430	54.75	MW883603	ISKNV	99.89	MK689685.1
11	SE Asia	2010	Dwarf gourami	122	111,092	3301	54.75	MW883604	ISKNV	99.89	AF371960.1
12	Indonesia	2016	Hybrid grouper, Cantang	122	110,961	3773	54.75	MW464172	ISKNV	99.87	AF371960.1
13	Indonesia	2018	Giant gourami	122	111,105	2063	54.77	MW883605	ISKNV	99.94	AF371960.1
14	Indonesia	2018	Giant gourami	122	111,609	3313	54.77	MW883606	ISKNV	99.99	AF371960.1
15	Indonesia	2016	Hybrid grouper, Cantik	122	110,919	2509	54.75	MW557381	ISKNV	99.85	MK689685.1
16	Indonesia	2014	Hybrid grouper, Cantik	120	112,711	2065	53.14	MW883598	RSIV	99.91	MK689686.1

1649 ^a Percent identity derived from whole genome sequence at the nucleotide level

1650

4.4.4 Genome structure and sequence identity

1651 Pairwise comparison identified >98.80% nucleotide similarity between 14/15 of the ISKNV genotypes in
1652 the study which were identified as ISKNV Clade 1. The ISKNV Clade 2 genotype (Sample 3) had 96.83-
1653 97.36% similarity to the other ISKNV genotype samples, whilst the RSIV genotype (Sample 16) had 85.37-
1654 85.91% similarity to other genomes in the study (Table 4.4). A consistent genome structure was observed
1655 for all samples with a single super interval identified by MAUVE compared to a representative genome,
1656 AFIV-16 (MK689685) (Supplementary Figure S4.2). Dot plot analyses demonstrated a high degree of
1657 collinearity between samples and reference genomes (Supplementary Figure S4.3).

1658 Annotation identified the consistent presence of predicted genes from representative ISKNV genomes,
1659 and a high proportion had >95% amino acid sequence identity (Table 4.5). Using BCIV (MN432490.1) and
1660 AFIV (MK689685.1) as reference genomes for annotation, each of the ISKNV genotype samples had 122
1661 ORFs except for 2 samples, with 120 and 121. This was explained by non-sense mutations in ORF 26 and
1662 57 (Sample 3) and ORF 26 (Sample 7). The 14 Clade 1 ISKNV genomes had 92 - 105 of 122 predicted genes
1663 with 100% amino acid identity (Table 4.5). Sample 3 grouped with ISKNV Clade 2 and had 110 ORFs with
1664 100% amino acid identity to BCIV (MN432490.1). The most variable sequence occurred in ORFs 24, 26, 57,
1665 and 58 where pairwise nucleotide identity was below 80%. These ORFs were distinguished by variation in
1666 the frequency and sequence of repeated sequences (Supplementary Table S.2). There were 120 predicted
1667 ORFs for the RSIV genotype (Sample 16) which grouped with RSIV Clade 2 and shared 91 ORFs with 100%
1668 amino acid identity to RSIV strain KagYT-96 (MK689686.1) (Table 4.5). This included ORF 109 from RSIV
1669 strain KagYT-96 (MK689686.1) which was absent in PIV 2014a (MK098186) and did not include ORF 27
1670 and 52 predicted in PIV 2014a which had less than 120 nucleotides. Gene by gene analysis identified 59
1671 core genes (>95% amino acid similarity) for the ISKNV species (Supplementary Table S4.3) with additional
1672 ORFs shared across two genotypes: ISKNV and RSIV (8); ISKNV and TRBIV (1), RSIV and TRBIV (6).

1673 There were 20 and 32 conserved direct repeated sequences in the ISKNV and RSIV genomes, respectively,
1674 with 3 shared repeated sequences. The repeated sequences ranged in size from 9 to 222 nucleotides with
1675 frequency between 1.9 and 30.4 (Supplementary Table S4.2). The repeated sequences differed between
1676 clades in the ISKNV and RSIV with 10 of the ISKNV repeats present in Clades 1 and 2 and 7 from RSIV
1677 present in both Clades of this genotype.

1678

1679 **Table 4. 4.** Pairwise comparison of whole genomes characterized in the present study. The nucleotide sequence identity (%) (upper) and genetic
 1680 distance (lower) were calculated using maximum composite likelihood model that encompassed 115,409 nucleotides including gaps.

Sample ID	Sample ID															
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
1		99.07	97.16	99.72	99.71	99.77	99.60	99.59	99.64	99.78	99.69	99.59	99.68	99.34	99.60	88.14
2	1.11×10^{-3}		96.81	99.27	99.27	99.01	99.25	99.21	99.29	99.14	99.24	99.17	99.12	98.81	99.21	87.50
3	1.80×10^{-2}	1.85×10^{-2}		97.34	97.36	97.14	97.12	97.26	97.23	97.17	97.33	97.29	97.19	96.95	97.28	88.09
4	3.87×10^{-4}	1.20×10^{-3}	1.77×10^{-2}		100	99.63	99.66	99.78	99.76	99.74	99.85	99.86	99.75	99.45	99.86	87.95
5	4.23×10^{-4}	1.20×10^{-3}	1.78×10^{-2}	0		99.63	99.66	99.78	99.76	99.74	99.85	99.86	99.75	99.45	99.86	87.95
6	7.83×10^{-4}	1.13×10^{-3}	1.81×10^{-2}	7.39×10^{-4}	7.39×10^{-4}		99.53	99.55	99.66	99.70	99.66	99.56	99.63	99.43	99.53	88.14
7	5.14×10^{-4}	1.29×10^{-3}	1.79×10^{-2}	5.33×10^{-4}	5.33×10^{-4}	6.40×10^{-4}		99.64	99.72	99.69	99.64	99.53	99.65	99.18	99.60	87.89
8	5.68×10^{-4}	1.29×10^{-3}	1.79×10^{-2}	6.77×10^{-4}	6.77×10^{-4}	6.85×10^{-4}	4.97×10^{-4}		99.70	99.60	99.77	99.70	99.67	99.35	99.72	87.88
9	5.14×10^{-4}	1.20×10^{-3}	1.81×10^{-2}	5.86×10^{-4}	5.86×10^{-4}	3.15×10^{-4}	6.41×10^{-4}	6.59×10^{-4}		99.66	99.75	99.64	99.69	99.37	99.70	87.93
10	4.50×10^{-4}	1.19×10^{-3}	1.80×10^{-2}	4.96×10^{-4}	4.96×10^{-4}	7.29×10^{-4}	6.04×10^{-4}	6.68×10^{-4}	5.77×10^{-4}		99.69	99.62	99.66	99.26	99.64	88.01
11	6.31×10^{-4}	1.16×10^{-3}	1.79×10^{-2}	5.77×10^{-4}	5.77×10^{-4}	7.48×10^{-4}	5.60×10^{-4}	6.31×10^{-4}	5.95×10^{-4}	6.85×10^{-4}		99.75	99.79	99.46	99.77	87.97
12	4.33×10^{-4}	1.21×10^{-3}	1.77×10^{-2}	9.92×10^{-5}	9.92×10^{-5}	7.12×10^{-4}	5.42×10^{-4}	6.50×10^{-4}	5.96×10^{-4}	5.05×10^{-4}	6.31×10^{-4}		99.63	99.38	99.93	87.90
13	8.38×10^{-4}	1.42×10^{-3}	1.82×10^{-2}	8.21×10^{-4}	8.21×10^{-4}	1.13×10^{-3}	7.94×10^{-4}	9.02×10^{-4}	8.84×10^{-4}	1.02×10^{-3}	8.29×10^{-4}	8.03×10^{-4}		99.35	99.66	88.00
14	3.78×10^{-4}	1.04×10^{-3}	1.80×10^{-2}	4.32×10^{-4}	4.32×10^{-4}	8.19×10^{-4}	4.60×10^{-4}	5.23×10^{-4}	4.78×10^{-4}	4.33×10^{-4}	5.58×10^{-4}	4.42×10^{-4}	6.94×10^{-4}		99.34	87.76
15	3.70×10^{-4}	1.18×10^{-3}	1.76×10^{-2}	9.02×10^{-5}	9.02×10^{-5}	6.40×10^{-4}	5.15×10^{-4}	6.23×10^{-4}	5.69×10^{-4}	4.42×10^{-4}	5.41×10^{-4}	4.51×10^{-5}	7.85×10^{-4}	3.97×10^{-4}		87.88
16	7.96×10^{-2}	7.96×10^{-2}	7.89×10^{-2}	7.93×10^{-2}	7.93×10^{-2}	8.00×10^{-2}	7.91×10^{-2}	7.95×10^{-2}	7.95×10^{-2}	7.95×10^{-2}	7.95×10^{-2}	7.93×10^{-2}	7.98×10^{-2}	7.98×10^{-2}	7.92×10^{-2}	

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1683 **Table 4. 5.** Amino acid similarity for gene-by-gene comparison within the predicted ORFs in the samples from the present study and reference
 1684 samples from similar genotypes. Data are the sum of genes within the categories for percentage similarity compared to Angelfish iridovirus AFIV-
 1685 16 (ISKNV genotype Clade 1, MK689685), Banggai cardinal fish iridovirus (ISKNV genotype Clade 2, MN432490 BCIV 2012), Pompano iridovirus
 1686 isolate PIV 2014a (RSIV genotype Clade 1, MK098186 PIV 2014) and RSIV isolate KagYT96 (RSIV genotype Clade 2, MK689686).

Gene similarity (pairwise amino acid %)	Compared with ISKNV Clade 1 (MK689685 Angelfish iridovirus AFIV-16)																Compared with ISKNV Clade 2 (MN432490 BCIV 2012)															
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
	100	103	95	30	105	105	93	98	94	101	104	104	105	92	104	105	2	31	30	110	31	31	30	29	28	30	31	32	32	25	31	32
<100-95	14	20	74	12	12	24	19	22	15	12	12	11	25	13	11	57	74	74	6	74	74	74	76	75	75	72	73	72	80	74	72	59
<95-90	2	3	11	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	4	3	2	3	33	7	7	2	7	7	7	7	7	7	8	7	8	6	8	8	34
<90-85	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	9	0	1	0	0	0	2	0	2	0	0	1	2	0	0	6	
<85-80	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	
<80-75	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
<75-70	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	3	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
<70	0	3	4	0	0	1	2	0	0	3	1	1	0	1	0	10	5	6	1	6	6	5	6	6	6	7	6	5	5	5	6	10

Gene similarity (pairwise amino acid %)	Compared with RSIV Clade 1 (MK098186 PIV 2014)																Compared with RSIV Clade 2 (MK689686 RSIV isolate KagYT 96)															
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
	100	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	23	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	91
<100-95	56	55	57	56	56	56	56	56	56	56	56	56	54	55	56	80	59	59	66	59	59	58	59	59	59	59	59	59	59	59	24	
<95-90	35	34	33	35	35	35	35	34	35	35	35	35	37	36	35	6	30	29	25	30	30	30	30	29	30	29	30	30	30	30	0	
<90-85	7	8	9	7	7	7	7	8	7	7	7	8	7	7	8	2	14	14	13	14	14	14	14	14	14	14	14	13	14	14	0	
<85-80	5	5	6	5	5	5	5	5	5	4	5	4	5	5	4	3	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	0	
<80-75	6	6	5	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	3	4	4	5	4	4	5	4	5	4	3	4	4	4	4	2	
<75-70	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	2	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	0	
<70	9	10	9	9	9	8	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	3	7	8	7	7	7	6	7	7	7	8	7	7	7	7	7	1

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4.4.5 Phylogenetic analysis

1689 The phylogenetic tree of the 59 core genes divided ISKNV species into the three expected genotypes
1690 (ISKNV, RSIV, and TRBIV) and supported the two previously identified clades for each genotype (Figure
1691 4.2). Two recently published genomes referred to as Large yellow croaker iridovirus were identified as
1692 RSIV genotype, without grouping with RSIV Clade 1 or 2. These genomes were assigned to the ISKNV
1693 genotype based on analysis of 26 core iridovirus genes (data not shown). Fourteen of the sixteen study
1694 samples were identified within Clade 1 of the ISKNV genotype (Figure 4.1). Sample 3, which had 99.95%
1695 whole genome similarity to BCIV (MN432490 Banggai Cardinal Iridovirus), grouped with Clade 2 of the
1696 ISKNV genotype (Figures 4.1 and 2). These genomes were both derived from Banggai cardinal fish
1697 (*Pterapogon kauderni*) from Indonesia in 2012 and 2015, respectively. One sample from grouper
1698 aquaculture in Indonesia was identified within Clade 2 of the RSIV genotype, although it did not group as
1699 closely as previously described isolates (Figures 4.1 and 2). Interestingly, two Clade 1 ISKNV genotypes
1700 were obtained from hybrids of the same grouper species in the same Indonesian aquaculture location and
1701 year as the RSIV genotype (Samples 4 and 5).

1702 The use of SNPs for phylogenetic analysis differentiated the ISKNV genomes with high similarity and
1703 identified patterns of association between viral genome sequence and country of origin, host species and
1704 year of the collection (Figure 4.3). For example, Clade 1 ISKNV genotypes from Indonesia (Samples 1, 4, 5
1705 and 12-15) were grouped separately from samples of the same clade and genotype in Thailand (Samples
1706 2, 6 and 8). Further, there were differences between samples from fish farmed in freshwater aquaculture
1707 of giant gourami in Indonesia and examples of the same clade and genotype from farmed marine hybrid
1708 grouper in this country. Samples from freshwater ornamental fish in Sri Lanka (Sample 9) and Singapore
1709 (Sample 7) clustered with ISKNV from the USA, also from freshwater ornamental fish. Additionally,

1710 although Sample 3 was highly similar to the Clade 2 ISKNV also obtained from Banggai cardinal fish three
1711 years earlier, it was clearly differentiated by SNP analysis.

1712

Year	Host species	Origin	Genome length (bp)	Reference	Fish type	ISKNV genotype	Clade
2002	Orange-spotted grouper (<i>Epinephelus coioides</i>)	Guangdong, China	112,636	Lu et al. (2005)	Food fish		
2006	Barramundi (<i>Lates calcarifer</i>)	Kaohsiung, Taiwan	112,565	Wen and Hong (2016)	Food fish		
2018	Barramundi (<i>Lates calcarifer</i>)	Mangalore, India	111,557	Puneeth et al. (2020)	Food fish		
2009	Barred knifejaw (<i>Oplegnathus fasciatus</i>)	Fujian, China	112,333	Zhang et al. (2013)	Food fish		
2000	Barred knifejaw (<i>Oplegnathus fasciatus</i>)	Tongyeong, Korea	112,080	Do et al. (2004)	Food fish	RSIV	Clade 2
2012	Red sea bream (<i>Pagrus major</i>)	Ehime, Japan	112,590	Matsuyama et al. (2017)	Food fish		
1996	Japanese amberjack (<i>Seriola quinqueradiata</i>)	Kagoshima, Japan	112,710	Kawato et al. (2020)	Food fish		
2014	Hybrid grouper (<i>♀E. fuscoguttatus</i> x <i>♂E. polyphkadion</i>)	Bali, Indonesia	112,717	This study	Food fish		
2016	Florida pompano (<i>Trachinotus carolinus</i>)	Dominican Rep	112,052	Koda et al. (2019)	Food fish		
2014	Florida pompano (<i>Trachinotus carolinus</i>)	Dominican Rep	112,377	Koda et al. (2019)	Food fish	RSIV	Clade 1
2010	Florida pompano (<i>Trachinotus carolinus</i>)	Dominican Rep	112,321	Koda et al. (2019)	Food fish		
1991	Red sea bream (<i>Pagrus major</i>)	Ehime, Japan	112,415	Kurita et al. (2002)	Food fish		
2001	Large yellow croaker (<i>Pseudosciaena crocea</i>)	Fujian, China	111,760	Ao and Chen (2006)	Food fish	RSIV	Clade 3
2020	Large yellow croaker (<i>Pseudosciaena crocea</i>)	Zhoushan, China	112,043	Wang et al. (2020)	Food fish		
2012	Banggai cardinal fish (<i>Pterapogon kauderni</i>)	Indonesia	112,618	Koda et al. (2020)	Ornamental	ISKNV	Clade 2
2015	Banggai cardinal fish (<i>Pterapogon kauderni</i>)	Ketapang, Indonesia	111,666	This study	Ornamental		
2017	Banggai cardinal fish (<i>Pterapogon kauderni</i>)	USA	111,920	Koda et al. (2020)	Ornamental		
1998	Mandarin fish (<i>Siniperca chuatsi</i>)	Guangdong, China	111,362	He et al. (2001)	Food fish		
2019	Albino rainbow shark (<i>Epalzeorhynchus frenatus</i>)	USA	111,380	Koda et al. (2020)	Ornamental		
2018	Barramundi (<i>Lates calcarifer</i>)	Thailand	111,487	Kayansamruaj (2021)	Food fish		
2019	Barramundi (<i>Lates calcarifer</i>)	Thailand	111,610	Kayansamruaj (2021)	Food fish	ISKNV	Clade 1
2016	Angelfish (<i>Pterophyllum scalare</i>)	Singapore	111,127	Kawato et al. (2020)	Ornamental		
2007	Red sea bream (<i>Pagrus major</i>)	Penghu, Taiwan	111,154	Shiu et al. (2017)	Food fish		
2018	Albino rainbow shark (<i>Epalzeorhynchus frenatus</i>)	USA	111,369	Koda et al. (2020)	Ornamental		
1989	Three spot gourami (<i>Trichopodus trichopterus</i>)	USA	111,591	Koda et al. (2018)	Ornamental	TRBIV	Clade 2
1989	South American cichlid (<i>Cleithracara maronii</i>)	USA	111,347	Koda et al. (2018)	Ornamental		
2005	Turbot (<i>Scophthalmus maximus</i>)	Shandong, China	110,104	Shi et al. (2010)	Food fish	TRBIV	Clade 1

1722 **Figure 4. 1.** Maximum likelihood phylogenetic cladogram based on 59 ISKNV species core genes and information table for the sequences. Sample
 1723 1,2,4-15 have identic amino acid sequence for the core genes. The cladogram included 17213 amino-acid sites from 28 whole genome sequences
 1724 and constructed using Jones-Taylor-Thornton model with empirical frequencies and invariable sites. The analysis was performed using IQ-Tree
 1725 (Nguyen et al., 2015) with 1000 bootstraps which applied ultrafast bootstrap (Minh et al., 2013) after the best model finding using ModelFinder
 1726 (Kalyaanamoorthy et al., 2017). Bootstrap value of 80 was used as a cut-off point. Alignment using MAFFT with fftns option (Katoh and Standley,
 1727 2013) was performed prior to phylogeny tree construction.

1728

1729 **Figure 4. 2.** Cladogram of the whole genome sequence of the 16 study samples and ISKNV species based on single nucleotide polymorphisms
 1730 (SNPs). The maximum likelihood cladogram was constructed from 40 sequences including 4701 nucleotide sites on IQ-Tree using three
 1731 substitution type model and unequal base frequencies with the application of ascertainment bias correction and discrete gamma distribution
 1732 with four rate categories. Bootstrap value of 1000 was applied using ultrafast bootstrap (Minh et al., 2013) after the best model finding using
 1733 ModelFinder (Kalyaanamoorthy et al., 2017). Bootstrap value of 80 was used as a cut off point. SNP Alignment was generated using CSI

1734 Phylogeny 1.4 web tool (Kaas et al., 2014). The geographic assignment was performed using Mapbox ©. Circle, square, and triangle represent
1735 ISKNV, RSIV, and TRBIV genotypes respectively. The colours represent the country of origin. The numbers on the map indicate the sample
1736 number.

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4.5 Discussion

1739 The present study enhanced knowledge of ISKNV by analysing 16 complete genome sequences. The hybrid
1740 capture enrichment method provided access a broad range of viral genomes directly from fish, including
1741 those with subclinical infections and low viral load which have not previously been accessible to whole
1742 genome analysis. The sequence similarity within the previously described ISKNV genotype and clade
1743 designations was extremely high (>98.8% for ISKNV Clade 1) irrespective of a broad range of hosts,
1744 countries of origin, year of collection and clinical status of the infected fish. Considerable differences in
1745 genomic sequence also added further support for differentiation of sub-groups within the broad ISKNV-
1746 species designation to support functional disease control. For example, increasing availability of sequence
1747 data supports the three distinct genotypes of ISKNV despite each causing a disease with similar pathology
1748 and an increasing overlap in geographical distribution and range of susceptible fish species (Koda et al.,
1749 2018; Kawato et al., 2020; Zhu et al., 2021). An RSIV isolate in this study caused clinically indistinguishable
1750 disease in hybrid grouper in the same year and location within Indonesia as an ISKNV genotype. These
1751 viruses were readily distinguished with 87.96% nucleotide sequence identity and only 30 genes with 100%
1752 predicted amino acid identity. The RSIV and ISKNV genotypes represent pathogenic virus groups which
1753 each has a broad host range but with different viral properties. Therefore, these and TRBIV should be
1754 considered separately for functional disease control, such as validation of diagnostic tests, vaccine
1755 development and retesting for freedom from infection.

1756 The growing number of aquatic pathogens recognized in genus *Megalocytivirus* across diverse locations
1757 requires sequences and associated metadata to be reported according to a standard nomenclature. In
1758 addition to the distinct genotypes within species ISKNV, genomic diversity has been reported in SDDV
1759 causing disease in barramundi (Kayansamruaj et al., 2020). Additional megalocytiviruses have been
1760 described from freshwater European chub, *Squalius cephalus* (Halaly et al., 2019) and euryhaline three-
1761 spine stickleback, *Gasterosteus aculeatus* (Waltzek et al., 2012). There were more than double the number

1762 of core genes (59) within the species ISKNV compared to the 26 for family *Iridoviridae* (Eaton et al., 2007).
1763 Repeated sequence analysis showed the ISKNV genome was consistent at the clade level. The function of
1764 the repeated sequence in megalocytiviruses is unknown, however, some studies revealed that repeated
1765 sequence influenced the protein expression by affecting transcription initiation (Metruccio et al., 2009)
1766 and mRNA stability (Attia and Hansen, 2006). The different repeated sequences in each ISKNV genotypes
1767 may result in different genome regulation at some point which affect the pathogenicity. These will be
1768 important for distinguishing viruses within the genus *Megalocytivirus* as rapid advances in documenting
1769 iridovirus pathogen diversity necessitates updated disease control policy. For example, a regulatory
1770 diagnostic procedure for 'megalocytivirus' refers to an assay has that has been evaluated for the ISKNV
1771 and RSIV genotypes rather than the spectrum of pathogens across this genus (Crane and Moody, 2018),
1772 whilst the OIE definition of red seabream iridoviral disease considers genotypes with little definition
1773 within the species ISKNV (OIE, 2019b).

1774 Important differences between genotypes and further subgroups within the ISKNV species could be
1775 overlooked when the host range, environment, and pathology overlap. The RSIV and ISKNV genotypes
1776 which caused disease in hybrid grouper in Indonesia in the present study were distinguished by the
1777 sequence of the MCP and ATPase genes (95.1% and 96.1% nucleotide identity, respectively). Determining
1778 the genotype is an important distinction as it will indicate the appropriate approach to disease control.
1779 For example, a commercial vaccine against RSIV (Aquavac IridoV, MSD Animal Health) provided only
1780 partial protection against ISKNV (Dong et al., 2017), and cross protection was not identified for TRBIV
1781 (Jung et al., 2016). This is consistent with a report of the highest antigenicity for RSIV related to the major
1782 capsid protein and the products of ORFs 054L, 055L, 101L, 117L, and **125L** (Xiong et al., 2011), of which
1783 includes another gene product that was not an ISKNV core genes (125L). Vaccine development, is an area
1784 of current research and development interest for ISKNV (Zhao et al., 2019). Failure to differentiate
1785 different causative pathogens in diagnosis or surveillance for the ISKNV species will impair efforts for

1786 disease control based on biosecurity and vaccination. Therefore, disease control requires validated
1787 diagnostic tests for high throughput surveillance for ISKNV that can differentiate the genotypes to guide
1788 the appropriate vaccine choice or development. Validation of fit-for-purpose tests for high throughput
1789 screening assays that are pan-ISKNV reactive as well as rapid and convenient tests to differentiate each
1790 genotype is a priority highlighted by the absence of such tests in the Manual of Diagnostic Tests for Aquatic
1791 Animals (OIE, 2019b).

1792 Effective international and regional biosecurity can benefit fish health by excluding ISKNV genotypes, even
1793 if some are already endemic. For example, disease in the economically and sociocultural important species
1794 barramundi has been reported for RSIV (Puneeth et al., 2021), ISKNV (Zhu et al., 2021) and TRBIV (Tsai et
1795 al., 2020), whilst mandarin fish were susceptible to disease caused by RSIV and ISKNV (Liu et al., 2018). In
1796 2017, outbreaks of disease caused by TRBIV occurred in Taiwan in barramundi that were shipped from
1797 Thailand (Tsai et al., 2020). This was the first detection of TRBIV in Taiwan and was spread to 35 farms
1798 across 2 growing regions. Given the current suite of PCR assays, this infection is likely to have gone
1799 undetected in any pre-exporting health assessment (OIE, 2019b). Further, the potential for ISKNV to
1800 undergo recombination presents an additional reason to minimize spread of different isolates (Shiu et al.,
1801 2017). In the related genus *Ranavirus*, natural recombination generated a chimeric pathogen with much
1802 higher virulence (Peace et al., 2019).

1803 The genotype classification with a numbering system provides the most functional approach to ISKNV
1804 nomenclature which overcomes the confusion of a genotype name overlapping with the species i.e.
1805 Genotypes I (RSIV), II (ISKNV) and III (TRBIV) (Kurita and Nakajima, 2012). The International Committee for
1806 Taxonomy of Viruses (ICTV) might also consider classification of 1 or more viruses species within ISKNV
1807 based on the genomic and phenotypic descriptors of different virus species (Chinchar et al., 2017).
1808 Systematic nomenclature will enhance communication for effective regional and international disease

1809 management. For example, a disease report using the virus classification: “The causative agent was
1810 identified as *Megalocytivirus* ISKNV genotype II” (Dong et al., 2017), was more informative compared to
1811 a report with an isolate name: “a new member of megalocytivirus, designated as giant gourami iridovirus”,
1812 when the sequence data indicated that the same genotype was present (Sukenda et al., 2020).

1813 The present study highlighted that there was a high level of conservation within the existing genotype and
1814 clade designations for ISKNV with > 95% amino acid sequence similarity for at least 115 of 122 predicted
1815 genes (ISKNV genotype Clade 1). The nucleic acid target enrichment method demonstrated that this
1816 conservation held across clinical and subclinical infections, freshwater and marine fish and isolates
1817 obtained several years apart. Hybrid probe libraries have enabled detection of viral genomes with 85-90%
1818 sequence mismatches and with sequence gaps up to 500 nucleotides (Kamaraj et al., 2019). In this study,
1819 the suitability of the method for identifying sequence diversity was highlighted by the detection of ISKNV
1820 Clade 2 and an RSIV genotype. Other examples of nucleic acid target enrichment have demonstrated the
1821 value for determining sequence variation in important aquatic pathogens. Hybrid capture probes
1822 successfully enriched a sample limited to 5000 copies of *Cyprinid herpesvirus 3* to determine the 295 kb
1823 genome and identify a mixed genotype infection (Hammoumi et al., 2016). An alternative enrichment
1824 method used oligonucleotide primers with long-range PCR to enrich *Ostreid herpesvirus 1* DNA and
1825 identified viral sequence variants from clinical samples (Bai et al., 2019).

1826 Despite the high similarity within the ISKNV genomes, the present method for high resolution complete
1827 genome sequence determination identified a role for genomic epidemiology. An example of the value of
1828 this technique to understand disease occurrence and transmission pathways in aquaculture and
1829 determine preventative measures is provided by *Salmon pancreas disease virus* (salmon alphavirus, SAV).
1830 The shorter and more variable 12 kb RNA genome was more amenable to such analyses (Gallagher et al.,
1831 2020). However, single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP) and nucleotide repeat region analyses of ISKNV

1832 might inform disease investigations as the samples that shared a common collection location grouped on
1833 phylogenetic analysis. This will be particularly useful in informing the role ISKNV spread through
1834 international trade in ornamental fish, which is a recognized route for the global spread of aquatic disease
1835 agents (Trujillo-González et al., 2018). This was suspected to have contributed to the increasing
1836 distribution of ISKNV, including an incursion into Australia (Go et al., 2006; Rimmer et al., 2015). Sample
1837 11 in the present study was derived from a dwarf gourami imported into Australia from a Southeast Asian
1838 location, with phylogenomic evidence suggesting that this was most likely Indonesia. The high similarity
1839 between a Clade 2 ISKNV from Banggai cardinal fish (Sample 3) with a sample from the same host species
1840 and sampling location (BCIV 2012, MN432490) three years earlier (Weber et al., 2009) suggests that ISKNV
1841 circulated in this environment with a stable genome. The possibility that this reflected host adaptation is
1842 less likely with the recent description of a Clade 1 ISKNV genotype from Banggai cardinal fish (BCIV 2017,
1843 MT926123).

1844 Disease caused by ISKNV in fish is multifactorial with important influence from host and environmental
1845 factors on disease expression. For example, disease expression in infected fish was influenced by water
1846 temperature (Jun et al., 2009), although a controlled experimental setting indicated that additional factors
1847 also influence the disease outcome (Fusianto et al., 2019). Further studies of ISKNV will benefit from
1848 genomic tools to determine viral factors that influence disease. For example, viral genetic markers of
1849 adaptation to freshwater or marine hosts have been suggested (Huang et al., 2021) and pathogenicity of
1850 an ISKNV isolate was reported to be limited to a specific host fish species (Jung et al., 2016). Subclinical
1851 infection has been documented based on PCR positivity without evaluation of the infective potential of
1852 the virus (Rimmer et al., 2015). Access to detailed genomic information directly from hosts with subclinical
1853 infection will be the key to differentiating the role of viral factors.

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1855 **4.6 Conclusion**

1856 Detailed genomic characterization of ISKNV is important to inform disease control for this emerging
1857 pathogen in aquaculture. The broad ISKNV species designation includes readily distinguished genotypes
1858 which cause a similar disease with non-specific clinical signs and overlap in the large number of susceptible
1859 fish species. Comparison of complete genomes will identify genomic features associated with distinct viral
1860 phenotypes, including virulence factors that contribute to variable disease outcomes in different hosts
1861 and environments. A clear nomenclature that supports individual consideration of the sub-species
1862 designations of ISKNV is needed to manage fish health. The ISKNV genotypes are sufficiently different to
1863 require individual consideration in development of vaccines and validation of diagnostic tests. Control of
1864 ISKNV remains a high priority in endemic regions where it is important to limit viral amplification within
1865 high density populations fish in aquaculture. Whole genome sequences of ISKNV provide sufficient
1866 resolution for genomic epidemiology which can evaluate transmission pathways and inform the measures
1867 needed to limit the spread of this pathogen.

1868

1878 **Supplementary Figure S4. 1.** Hybrid probe design for ISKNV genome enrichment from fish samples. The design used a nucleotide alignment of 12
 1879 ISKNV genomes representing the 2 Clades within each of three genotypes to identify conserved regions (A) where nucleotide similarity was $>90\%$
 1880 in regions of 200 bases, or variable regions (B) with $<90\%$ similarity within 200 base regions. The 120 bp hybrid capture probes were tiled for 2x
 1881 coverage across the conserved regions and unique probes were designed for each unique sequence within the variable regions to ensure >2
 1882 coverage.

1883 **Supplementary Table S4. 1.** *In-silico* evaluation of probe design by mapping to ISKNV reference genomes
1884 and comparison with the genomes derived from the hybrid probe enrichment study. A similarity and
1885 length fraction of 0.9 were applied and global alignment was performed to map the probes using CLC
1886 Genomic workbench 12.

Sample/Reference ID	Mapped probes	Unmapped probes	Coverage (exclude zero coverage)				Zero coverage region			
			Max	Average	Min	St dev	Total Number	min	max	Total size (bp)
1	2062	659	7	2.22	1	0.95	5	1	70	100
2	2035	686	6	2.22	1	0.94	6	1	92	192
3	2050	671	7	2.24	1	0.97	25	1	158	1613
4	2053	668	6	2.22	1	0.95	7	1	95	206
5	2053	668	6	2.22	1	0.95	7	1	95	206
6	2051	670	6	2.21	1	0.94	7	1	104	227
7	2044	677	6	2.21	1	0.95	6	1	205	305
8	2050	671	6	2.22	1	0.94	6	1	70	126
9	2046	675	6	2.22	1	0.94	7	1	70	122
10	2048	673	6	2.21	1	0.94	6	1	86	186
11	2048	673	6	2.22	1	0.94	7	1	165	266
12	2054	667	6	2.23	1	0.95	6	1	95	205
13	2054	667	8	2.22	1	0.95	6	1	70	164
14	2052	669	6	2.21	1	0.95	8	1	481	661
15	2050	671	6	2.22	1	0.94	7	1	95	206
16	2150	597	6	2.22	1	0.94	10	1	98	168
AF371960 ISKNV	2059	662	7	2.22	1	0.95	6	1	70	104
KT781098 ISKNV RSIV-Ku	2062	659	7	2.23	1	0.94	5	1	18	34
AY532606 RBIV-KOR-TY1	2120	601	6	2.28	1	0.93	26	1	111	353
AB104413 RSIV	2103	618	6	2.25	1	0.94	15	1	73	442
AP017456 RSIV-RIE 12-1	2143	578	6	2.29	1	0.93	11	1	98	253
KT804738 GSIV-K1	2,143	578	6	2.29	1	0.93	10	1	98	188
AY779031 LYCIV	2,068	653	6	2.24	1	0.93	23	1	127	1023
AY894343 OSGIV	2,143	578	6	2.28	1	0.93	10	1	98	253
KC244182 RBIV C1	2,139	582	6	2.29	1	0.93	9	1	98	187
GQ273492 TRBIV	1842	879	6	2.05	1	0.91	42	1	203	2296
MG570132 TSGIV	1762	959	6	1.98	1	0.88	76	1	299	4761
MG570131 SACIV	1765	956	6	1.97	1	0.89	70	1	184	4067

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1894 **Supplementary Figure S4. 2.** Genome structure view developed after progressive alignment in MAUVE
 1905 indicating consistent genome structure across all samples from this study and two ISKNV reference
 1906 genome, Angelfish iridovirus AFIV-16 (MK689685) and Banggai cardinal fish iridovirus BCIV-2012
 1907 (MN432490)

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Supplementary Figure S4.3. Dot plots for pairwise comparison between samples: A. Sample 1 (representing the ISKNV Clade 1 samples in this study) with MK689685 Angelfish iridovirus AFIV-16 , B. Sample 3 (ISKNV Clade 2) and MN432490 Banggai cardinal fish iridovirus (BCIV), C. Sample 16 (RSIV genotype clade 2) and MK098186.1 Pompano iridovirus isolate PIV 2014a, D. Sample 5 (ISKNV genotype Clade 1) and Sample 16 (RSIV genotype) which were the amongst the most dissimilar genomes detected in this study and obtained from the same aquaculture site showed high collinearity.

1927 **Supplementary Table S4. 2.** Conserved repeated sequence regions identified in ISKNV and RSIV clade 1 and 2. ISKNV genomes mentioned in Figure
 1928 2 excluding TRBIV were analyzed using tandem repeats finder (Benson, 1999). The location of repeated sequences was based on annotation of
 1929 Angelfish iridovirus (MK689685).

Consensus pattern	Length (bp)	Location	ISKNV				RSIV			
			Clade 1		Clade 2		Clade 1		Clade 2	
			Match identity (%)	Frequency						
GACCGGCGCTTGGCGGGC	18	Orf 20	86-95	4.6-5.7	97	3.6	86-90	4.9-5.9	86	4.6
GACCGGCGCTTGGCGGGCGACCTGCGCTTGGCGGGC	36	Orf 20	87	2.7	-	-	-	-	85	2.3
CGGGCGACCTGCGCTTGG	18	Orf 20	92	4.7	-	-	-	-	89	2.6
TGGTCAATATGATGTTACTACCACTGAACCATGAGTGCTAAT...	47	Orf 24	100	2	100	2	-	-	-	-
GGCGCTGGT	9	Orf 23	-	-	88	8	-	-	-	-
GGCGCTGGTGGCGCTGGTGGCGCCGGT	27	Orf 23	-	-	93	2.7	-	-	-	-
ACAGGCCTGACAGGCCTGACGCGCACC	27	Orf 26	65-85	8.9-30.4	65-66	15-37	-	-	-	-
GACGCGCACCACAGGCCTGACGCGCACCACAGGCCTGACAC...	45	Orf 26	-	-	77-89	5.5-18.5	-	-	-	-
ACAGGCCTG	9	Orf 26	-	-	100	3.3	-	-	-	-
ACGACGCGCACCACAGGCCTGACAGGCCTGACACGC	36	Orf 26	72-100	3.6-18.7	87	4.7	-	-	-	-
ACAGGCCTGACACGACCC	18	Orf 26	95-100	1.9-3.4	94	2	-	-	-	-
AAGACGGCAGTTTATTGAGTTGTTACACATATAATATTAGCCA...	88	Orf 32	-	-	98	2.3	-	-	-	-
AGGGTCGCCACGTCGCAGAGGAACACGAGCCTCCCTTG...	75	Orf 57	97	1.9	-	-	-	-	-	-
GCTGCGTAGTGGATGTCATGGACCATCGTGGCTACG	36	Orf 58	97	2	97	2	-	-	-	-
AGTGGATGTCATGGACCATCGTGGCTACGGCTGCAC	36	Orf 58	88	2.1	88	2.1	-	-	-	-
TTGGTCCATGTCGCGCGGGTCTCCGGTTCAGGCAGGCGTCTG...	183	Orf 60	-	-	96	2	-	-	-	-
TTAATCATACACAGCACACCACAAAGTATGTACAC	35	Orf 64-65	94	2	97	2	-	-	-	-
GGTGCCCGAAGAGGTACGCC	21	Orf 87	86	2	86	2	-	-	-	-
GATGGCAGCGGTGCGTCGGTTC AACGGTA	30	Orf 92	96	1.9	96	1.9	-	-	-	-
GACGTGCCCACTCCCGCAAGGACAACATATGTGGTGCCTC...	96	Orf 114	94	2.2	-	-	-	-	-	-
GGCACCGGAGATGGTGGTCGCGCTGGCACCGGAACCTGGTACC	42	Orf 23	-	-	-	-	-	-	97	1.9
CCTGAGGAACCGGAGGAAGAAGAGGACGAGTACGACTGTCC...	174	Orf 24	-	-	-	-	-	-	75	3.6
ACCACCACCACTGTGGCACCTACAACA	27	Orf 24	-	-	-	-	-	-	95	2.7
ACAGGCCCGACGCGCACC	18	Orf 26	-	-	-	-	-	-	82	8.4-30.4
GGTGCTGGCACC	12	Orf 23	-	-	-	-	84	4.2	-	-
GCACCGGTGCTGGCA	15	Orf 23	-	-	-	-	86	3	-	-

GCTGGCACCGGAGATGGTGGTCGC	24	Orf 23	-	-	-	-	100	2.5	-	-
GAGCCTGAAGAACCAGAGGAAGAAGAGGACGAGTACGACT...	171	Orf 24	-	-	-	-	86	1.9	-	-
ACCACCACCACTGTGGCACACACA	27	Orf 26	-	-	-	-	90	3.5	-	-
CAACCACCACCACCACTGTGGCACCTACAA	27	Orf 26	-	-	-	-	89	2.8	-	-
ACCACCACCACTGTGGCACCTACAACAACCACCACCACTGTG...	222	Orf 24	-	-	-	-	92	2	-	-
ACCACCACCTGTGCCACCTACAACAACCACCACCACTGTGGCAC...	168	Orf 24	-	-	-	-	93	1.9-2	92-93	1.9-2
CACACCACAGGCCTGACAGGCCCGACG	27	Orf 26	-	-	-	-	71-76	11.5-13.5	-	-
ACAGGCCCGACGCACACCACAGGCCTGACAGGCCCGACGCA...	45	Orf 26	-	-	-	-	73-96	4.2-7.6	-	-
ACAGGCCCGACGCACGCCACAGGCCCGACGCACGACGACG...	72	Orf 26	-	-	-	-	85	3-3.5	-	-
ACAGGCCCGACGCACGCC	18	Orf 26	-	-	-	-	68-100	4.4-11.4	-	-
ACCCCGCCTGTTAGGCTAAGAAGGGTCGCCACGTTGCAGAG...	76	Between orf 56-57	-	-	-	-	99	2.6	-	-
GACCCCGCCTGTTAGGCTAAGAAGGGTCGCCACGTTGCAGA...	55	Between orf 56-57	-	-	-	-	90	3.8-4.8	-	-
GGCACATGCGTCGACCCGGCGT	22	Orf 54	-	-	-	-	100	2.4-3.4	85	1.9
TAGCGGCACCCCGCCTGTTAGGCTAAGAAGGGTCGCCACG...	69	Between orf 56-57	-	-	-	-	-	-	97	2.5
GCCACCGTCATCTGGCCATATTCAAATATTTCCAATATCAC...	66	Between orf 56-57	-	-	-	-	83	2.5	-	-
CACATATATCAATATACCCAGCCACCGATCATCTGGCCATAT...	66	Between orf 56-57	-	-	-	-	88	1.9	-	-
GCGTCTGAAGGGGCTGTCACTTGGCTCGTCCTGCAGG...	57	Orf 60	-	-	-	-	-	-	82	2
TGCAGGGGCGCTCAGGCAAGTCATCT	27	Orf 60	-	-	-	-	73	5.3	97	2.3
GTGCGACACCGTGCATAGACGACAGTCCCCAGCACATGGG...	57	Orf 65	-	-	-	-	82	2.2	82	2.2
GGTCAGGCTTTGGTG	15	Orf 88	-	-	-	-	88	6.9	88	7.9
CACCTGTACAATGCATGTGTGAGAATCAAAATGTGCAACT...	94	Orf 114	-	-	-	-	-	-	100	2
CAATTTGCATCAAGTGACTTTATTTCTACATTGTATTG	38	Between orf 103- 104	-	-	-	-	-	-	100	2
CACCACCTTACCAGCCGCTGCTATTCCACCCA	33	Orf 114	-	-	-	-	92	22	96	1.9

1931 **Supplementary Table S4. 3.** Core genes of members of the species ISKNV after a cut-off point of 95%
 1932 amino acid identity across ISKNV genotypes.

ORF ^a	Putative function	Position		Strand +/-
		Start	Stop	
1	Transmembrane amino acid transporter protein	134	1270	-
2	DNA dependent RNA polymerase subunit H-like protein	1240	1695	-
7	Major capsid protein	3794	5155	-
8	Myristylated membrane protein	5174	6631	-
10	Unknown	8342	8503	+
11	Unknown	8662	9054	-
12	Unknown	9051	9311	-
13	RING-finger-containing E3 ubiquitin ligase	9330	9662	+
ORF15 ^b	Unknown	11017	11394	-
15	Unknown	11309	12268	+
16	Unknown	12278	13069	+
17	Unknown	13129	13716	-
20	DNA polymerase	14579	17425	+
21	Unknown	17467	18006	+
24	Ribonucleotide diphosphate reductase small subunit	22300	23238	+
27	DNA repair protein RAD2	23942	24838	-
28	DNA dependent RNA polymerase largest subunit	24855	28361	-
29	Transcription factor S-II	28368	28589	-
33	DNA dependent RNA polymerase second largest subunit	30919	34053	+
42	Thiol oxidoreductase	43255	43617	-
45	Cytosine DNA methyltransferase	45333	46016	-
46	Unknown	46176	46439	+
48	Unknown	46796	46966	+
49	Unknown	47025	47453	-
54	Unknown	50294	50941	-
55	Unknown	50948	51208	-
58	Replication factor	52134	52937	-
60	Unknown	56620	56988	-
61	SNF2 family helicase	57002	59650	-
62	mRNA capping enzyme	59693	61168	-
66	Unknown	63671	65104	-
69	Unknown	66207	67817	-
74	Unknown	70820	73792	-
75	Ankyrin repeat containing protein	73810	75144	+
76	Unknown	75141	75605	+
78	Unknown	76142	76639	+
79	Unknown	76676	77782	-
80	Unknown	77834	78193	+
84	Ribonuclease III	80715	81485	+
85	SAP domain-containing protein	81482	81895	-
ORF88 ^b	Unknown	81939	83495	+
91	Putative RNA binding protein	84635	85561	-
92	Unknown	85571	86071	-
94	Unknown	87264	88073	-
95	Unknown	88007	88498	-
98	Unknown	89511	90026	-

101	Unknown	91990	92766	+
102	Unknown	92768	93133	+
105	D5 family NTPase	94949	97714	-
106	Unknown	97761	97916	+
108	Proliferating cell nuclear antigen-like protein	98823	99566	+
109	Unknown	99556	100059	-
111	FV3 immediate-early protein ICP46-like protein	102968	103978	+
114	FV3 31KDa-like protein	105486	106160	-
116	RING-finger-containing E3 ubiquitin ligase	107870	108157	+
117	Unknown	108189	108698	+
119	ATPase	109359	110078	+
120	Unknown	110050	110421	-
121	Ankyrin repeat-containing protein	110430	111116	-

1933 ^a ORF designations were based on the positions within the genome of Angelfish iridovirus strain AFIV-16 (MK689685) except two ORFs

1934 ^b ORF from Pompano iridovirus PIV2014a (MK098186)

1935

1936 5. **Chapter 5: Stability of *Infectious spleen and kidney necrosis virus* and susceptibility to**
1937 **physical and chemical disinfectants**

1938 **5.1 Abstract**

1939 The genus *Megalocytivirus* (MCV) includes *Infectious spleen and kidney necrosis virus* (ISKNV) and red
1940 seabream iridovirus (RSIV) which are listed by the World Organization for Animal Health (OIE). MCV has a
1941 broad host range and can be present as a persistent subclinical infection in some fish. Australia is
1942 considered free from MCV, and important aquaculture and wild fisheries are at risk. Consequently,
1943 biosecurity measures are implemented to ameliorate transmission pathways through imported
1944 ornamental fish which include certification of freedom from infection with MCV. Evaluation of practical
1945 and cost-effective disinfection protocols suitable for recirculating aquaculture facilities is an important
1946 aspect of the biosecurity plan to facilitate eradication in the event of early detection of an outbreak. An
1947 authentic sample matrix was prepared by *in vivo* amplification of ISKNV in Murray cod (*Maccullochella*
1948 *peelii*) and the biological load of a clarified tissue homogenate was standardized by addition of 10% v/v
1949 foetal bovine serum. In the absence of a cell culture system for ISKNV, a bioassay was used to assess
1950 infectivity after disinfection. A cellulose membrane buffer exchange device was used to remove residual
1951 disinfectants before intraperitoneal injection of juvenile Murray cod. Fish were maintained in 100 L
1952 aquaria at 23°C and observed for clinical signs over 14 days. Each bioassay was conducted in duplicate
1953 tanks with 6 to 19 fish per tank. A positive assay was defined by an increase in ISKNV DNA quantified by
1954 qPCR in any fish from a subsample of challenged fish collected at 7 d or those remaining at 14 d. Negative
1955 bioassays were defined by the absence of ISKNV DNA in all fish at both sampling times. Clinical disease
1956 and amplified viral DNA was detected after injection of a dilute positive control, indicating greater
1957 analytical sensitivity compared to qPCR (with a detection limit of 100 copies per reaction). Further, the
1958 system was used to demonstrate that ISKNV can remain infectious in aquaria without fish for at least 48

1959 h at 25°C. Effective disinfection measures included: heating to 65°C for 20 min; pH 3; pH 11; 1% Virkon™;
1960 1000 ppm sodium hypochlorite and benzalkonium chloride at the recommended concentration and
1961 contact time. These data can be interpreted to provide effective disinfection protocols for MCV in a wide
1962 variety of disease control scenarios.

1963 **5.2 Introduction**

1964 The ornamental fish industry presents a high risk to Australia for introducing exotic pathogens and alien
1965 fish species with many documented occurrences (Lintermans 2004; Padilla and Williams 2004; Rixon et al.
1966 2005; Cohen et al. 2007; Cobo et al. 2010; Duggan 2010; Rimmer et al., 2015). Annually, Australia imports
1967 approximately 14 million ornamental fish predominantly from Indonesia, Singapore and Thailand (Trujillo-
1968 González and Militz, 2019). Australia is considered to have a highly regulated quarantine system with
1969 stringent controls compared to global standards for importing live fish (Whittington and Chong, 2007).
1970 However, despite these controls, there have been several incursions of exotic aquatic pathogens of
1971 international significance, including *Infectious spleen, and kidney necrosis virus* (ISKNV) (Rimmer et al.,
1972 2015), *Cyprinid herpesvirus 2* (Stephens et al., 2004; Becker et al., 2014), and *Edwardsiella ictaluri*
1973 (Humphrey et al., 1986, Kelly et al., 2018), with the latter two now considered endemic in wild fish
1974 populations.

1975 Megalocytiviruses have a wide host range and have caused epidemics at marine and freshwater food fish
1976 aquaculture (Subramaniam et al., 2012). Recently, natural infections with ISKNV have been documented
1977 in hybrid groupers (*Epinephelus* spp.) in marine farms (Fusianto et al., 2021) and in giant gourami
1978 (*Osphronemus goramy*) from freshwater farms (Sukenda et al., 2020). The megalocytiviruses, ISKNV and
1979 a closely related but distinct virus, red sea bream iridovirus (RSIV) are notifiable to the World Organization
1980 for Animal Health (OIE, 2018) and are subject to regulation and notification in many countries (Hick et al.,
1981 2016a).

1982 ISKNV is considered exotic to Australia and infection with this virus and related viruses is listed on the
1983 Australian Government, Department of Agriculture and Water Resources national list of reportable
1984 diseases of aquatic animals. Given the prior outbreak of ISKNV resulting in over 90% of Murray cod dying
1985 at a hatchery in Victoria (Lancaster et al., 2003), there is a real risk to domestic aquaculture if ISKNV was
1986 to become established. Prior research has shown that several Australian native fish, including Golden
1987 perch (*Macquaria ambigua*) and the endangered Macquarie perch (*Macquaria australasica*) are
1988 susceptible to infection with ISKNV through cohabitation exposure at 23°C (Rimmer et al., 2017). Based
1989 on an import risk analysis (Australian Department of Agriculture, 2014), from March 2016, imported
1990 ornamental fish belonging to cichlid, gourami and poeciliid families require health certification indicating
1991 freedom from infection with *Megalocytivirus*.

1992 Effective disinfection procedures are important components of disease control and general guidelines for
1993 aquatic animal health are available from the OIE (2017). Efficient post-entry detection and containment
1994 incursions to prevent establishment of MCV are critical components of Australia's biosecurity in addition
1995 to health certification. However, interpretation and implementation by industry and regulatory
1996 authorities require pathogen-specific information. The survival of MCV outside a host is unknown and
1997 data describing disinfection with ether, formalin and chloroform are impractical, particularly without
1998 detailed application instructions (OIE, 2019b).

1999 The objective of the study was to identify effective disinfection measures to support biosecurity for ISKNV
2000 at aquaculture facilities and to determine the stability of ISKNV in aquarium water. Practical and
2001 efficacious disinfection protocols were identified for field relevant samples. Preparations of ISKNV in
2002 tissue samples provided authentic, complex biological matrices for testing. Due to the absence of a cell
2003 culture system for ISKNV, the evaluation of the infectivity of tissue samples before and after disinfection
2004 required a bioassay. Precedents for such studies with large, enveloped DNA viruses are available using a
2005 marine mollusk model (Corbeil et al. 2012, Hick et al. 2016b).

2006

2007

5.3 Materials and methods

2008

5.3.1 Fish and Experimental Conditions

2009 Murray cod fingerlings were obtained from a commercial farm in New South Wales and held in
2010 aquaculture tanks (300 to 500 L) with constant aeration and biological filtration. Water temperature was
2011 held at $23 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ through the use of an aquarium heater and recorded daily with a glass thermometer.
2012 Water changes were completed as needed to ensure nitrogenous wastes remained below 0.5 mg/L. pH
2013 was held between 7.0-7.2 and adjusted daily as needed using sodium bicarbonate. Fish were fed at 2% of
2014 the tank biomass once daily with crushed native fish sinking pellets (Skretting). Fish were acclimated to
2015 the 100 L Perspex experimental tanks for 48 hours prior to experimentation. Prior to handling and the
2016 intraperitoneal injection (IP), fish were anaesthetized by immersion in benzocaine (50–60 mg/L). Fish were
2017 euthanized as required with an overdose of benzocaine at 120 mg/L. Animal ethics approval was obtained
2018 from the University of Sydney Animal Ethics Committee (approval number: 2016/979).

2019

2020

5.3.2 Source of infective ISKNV

2021 From archival stocks, the well-characterized ISKNV isolate DGIV_2010 (Rimmer et al., 2017) was amplified
2022 twice in Murray cod. This work was the essential first step as the evaluation of disinfectants requires virus
2023 that has not been subject to freeze-thaw cycles. The DGIV_2010 isolate was obtained from a single dwarf
2024 gourami (*Trichogaster lalius* – see Sample 11 in Chapter 4) obtained from an aquarium shop in Sydney,
2025 Australia that had a natural acquired subclinical infection (Rimmer et al., 2017). The disinfection trials
2026 were conducted on freshly amplified virus stock at *in-vivo* passage level three or four rather than a
2027 cryopreserved virus stock which was shown previously to have diminished infectivity (unpublished data).

2028

2029

5.3.2.1 Trial 1

2030 A group of 19 Murray cod (total length 128 ± 8 mm mean \pm SD) were IP injected with 50 μ L of archived
2031 ISKNV inoculum (1/10 of the preserved clarified tissue homogenate stored in 2010 from Rimmer et al.
2032 (2017)). Fish were held in two aerated tanks (100 L habitable volume) at 23°C and maintained with an
2033 established canister biofilter. Fish were observed twice daily and euthanized in the event of morbidity or
2034 at 28 days and tested by qPCR for ISKNV. The kidney, liver and spleen from all qPCRs positive fish was
2035 pooled, homogenized with a mortar and pestle and filtered at 0.22 μ m to produce a 1/10 w/v tissue
2036 homogenate in phosphate buffered saline (PBS) that was cryopreserved with 10% foetal bovine serum
2037 (FBS, Bovogen Biologicals) and 10% glycerol at -80°C. This was used as the challenge inoculum in a second
2038 amplification trial (Trial 2). This first passage *in vivo* virus stock contained 9.74×10^6 ISKNV genome
2039 equivalents per μ L.

2040

2041

5.3.2.2 Trial 2

2042 Twenty Murray cod (total length 128 ± 8 mm) held in triplicate tanks at 25°C were injected with 50 μ L of
2043 1/10 dilution of the cryopreserved clarified tissue homogenate generated from Trial 1 in PBS. The kidney,
2044 liver and spleen from these fish were pooled, homogenized with a mortar and pestle, filtered, and
2045 cryopreserved as above. The clarified tissue homogenate inoculum from Trial 2 was used for the bioassays
2046 to generate fresh virus. The concentration of ISKNV was 7.43×10^3 genome equivalents per μ L

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5.3.3 ISKNV preparation for assessment of disinfection treatments

For Trial 3, freshly amplified third passage virus was obtained by injecting 20 donor Murray cod with 50 µL of a 1/10 dilution of the cryopreserved ISKNV-infected clarified tissue homogenate generated from Trial 2. For Trial 4, 10 Murray cod were injected with 50 µL of a 1/10 dilution of the cryopreserved ISKNV-infected clarified tissue homogenate generated from Trial 3 (thus at 4th passage).

The donor Murray cod were held at 25°C in aerated aquariums fitted with a canister biofilter. On Day 7, fish were euthanized, and kidney, liver, and spleen were dissected and pooled. A tissue homogenate was prepared using a mortar and pestle with PBS at 1/10 (w/v) and filtered at 0.22 µm. The clarified tissue homogenate was diluted at 1/10 and heat inactivated FBS (10% v/v) was added to the homogenate to create a standardized, authentic biological matrix. This was referred to as the “ISKNV virus preparation” and was subjected to the disinfectant treatments described below and kept on ice between steps. A qPCR was performed on clarified pooled tissue homogenate and the ISKNV virus preparation.

Two positive controls were used in each bioassay with one being no treatment other than incubation on ice (Trial 3) or buffer exchange only (Trial 4) of the virus preparation. The second positive control preparation was a 1/100 dilution with PBS (w/v) of the virus preparation for each trial and was referred to as the diluted positive control. Effectively, the positive control and the diluted positive control groups were injected with virus preparations derived from 4.5 µg and 0.045 µg of ISKNV-infected tissue, respectively. Negative control challenge inoculum was prepared using kidney, liver, and spleen from Golden perch (*Macquaria ambigua*) previously tested negative for MCV that were homogenized with PBS (1:10 w/v) and then combined with 10% FBS (v/v).

The disinfection treatments in 5 mL aliquots detailed in Table 5.1 were:
a) heating in a hybridization oven followed by rapid cooling on ice,
b) changes in pH by addition of HCl or NaOH and neutralized to pH 7, or

2073 c) chemical treatment with Virkon S™ (DuPont), sodium hypochlorite (1000 ppm) or quaternary
2074 ammonium compound (Accent, 26 g/L benzalkonium chloride tested at 650 ppm).

2075

2076 The ISKNV virus preparation was subjected to heat treatment in a hybridization oven (Thermoscientific)
2077 and temperature monitored using a calibrated digital thermometer (KS-T-10S Digital Thermometer).

2078 For pH treatments, 11.65 M hydrochloric acid (HCl) or 0.1 M sodium hydroxide (NaOH) was added to
2079 the ISKNV virus preparation to adjust the pH to 3 or 11, respectively using digital pH meter (LAQUA F-
2080 74BW, Horiba scientific). After 30 minutes at the desired pH, HCl or NaOH was added to adjust the pH
2081 to 7.3.

2082 Buffer exchange was performed for the chemical treatments to remove any residual disinfectants prior
2083 to injection. A regenerated cellulose 30 000 molecular weight cut-off membrane centrifuge device was
2084 prepared by pre-rinsing the membrane with ultrapure water (Amicon Ultra-15 Ultracel, Merck
2085 Millipore). The buffer exchange device was loaded with the treated challenge inoculum and
2086 centrifuged at 4000 x *g* for 5 minutes at 4°C (Hick et al., 2016b). The same chemical and pH disinfection
2087 procedures were applied to the negative control sample preparation. The quantity of ISKNV DNA was
2088 assessed by qPCR before (amount of ISKNV in the positive control injection) and after each disinfection
2089 procedure. All of the challenge inoculums were held on ice until time of use and were injected into fish
2090 within 1 hour of preparation.

2091

2092 **Table 5. 1.** Summary of disinfection treatments tested for inactivating ISKNV. The challenge inoculum
 2093 was freshly amplified, high titre ISKNV that was partially purified from fish organs (kidney, liver,
 2094 spleen) and added to a standardized biological matrix with 10% foetal bovine serum (v/v).

Treatment	Contact Time (minutes)	Outcome	
		qPCR assay following treatment ^{1,2,3}	Bioassay
Disinfection treatment (Trial Number)			
Heating to 40°C (3)	20	5.58 x 10 ³	Positive
Heating to 60°C (3)	5	9.58 x 10 ³	Positive
Heating to 65°C (4)	20	3.5 x 10 ⁴	Negative
pH 3 (4)	30	7.4 x 10 ⁴	Negative
pH 11 (4)	30	2.0 x 10 ⁴	Negative
Virkon™ 1% (4)	10	BLOD	Negative
Chlorine at 1000 ppm (4)	30	BLOD	Negative
Quaternary ammonium compound at 650 ppm (4)	10	5.0 x 10 ⁴	Negative
Positive Controls (Trial Number)			
No treatment (3)	0	2.81 x 10 ⁴	Positive
1/100 dilution with PBS (3)	0	BLOQ	Positive
Buffer exchange (4)	0	1.6 x 10 ⁵	Positive
1/100 dilution with PBS (4)	0	BLOQ	Positive
Negative Controls (Trial Number)			
No treatment (3)	0	BLOD	Negative
pH 3 (4)	30	BLOD	Negative
pH 11 (4)	30	BLOD	Negative
Virkon™ 1% (4)	10	BLOD	Negative
Chlorine at 1000 ppm (4)	30	BLOD	Negative
Quaternary ammonium compound at 650 ppm (4)	10	BLOD	Negative

2095 ¹ ISKNV genome copies per injection

2096 ² BLOQ: Below the level of quantification of the qPCR assay, a high Ct value was obtained outside of
 2097 the quantitative range.

2098 ³ BLOD: Below the limit of detection: a negative result was obtained using an assay with a limit of
 2099 detection of 100 copies of template per reaction.

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5.3.4 Bioassays

Two bioassay trials were completed with Trial 3 testing the effect of heating the sample preparation (Table 5.2) and Trial 4 testing heat, pH, and chemical disinfectants (Table 5.3). A bioassay outcome was considered negative when all fish from a treatment group were qPCR negative at the time of morbidity, at the 7 days post injection sampling and on the final day of observation.

For Trial 4, 3 positive control fish were dissected for qPCR testing and sample collection for histopathology at time of morbidity or at Day 12. Gill, posterior kidney, heart, liver, spleen, and gut were fixed in 10% neutral buffered formalin for 24 hours, demineralized in a 12.5% ethylene diamine tetra acetic acid solution (pH 7.0) and subject to routine processing for histopathology with hematoxylin and eosin staining. Sections were examined by an experienced pathologist (Professor Richard Whittington, University of Sydney) for up to 10 minutes per section at up to 400 x magnification.

Treatments and fish were randomly assigned to the experimental tanks (using www.random.org). Water quality was managed as described above (Section 5.3.1) and temperatures were maintained at 23°C (±1). All wastewater was disinfected with >1000 ppm chlorine for 60 minutes prior to disposal. Fish were fed once daily five times per week to a maximum of 2% tank weight. Feeding was halted if fish did not show interest or feed was left remaining on tank bottom.

Disinfecting treatments were tested in duplicate tanks with 6 to 19 fish per tank. On Day 0, fish were given a 50 µL IP injection with the virus preparation that underwent a disinfecting treatment described above. Positive controls were run in duplicate tanks with six to 20 fish in a tank and negative controls were run in single tanks. Fish were monitored twice daily for signs of morbidity. Moribund or dead fish were collected and frozen whole at -80°C for qPCR testing. On Day 7, one third of the fish were randomly selected, euthanized, and frozen at -80°C for qPCR testing. All surviving fish were sampled on Day 14 for Trial 3 and Day 12 for Trial 4.

2126 **Table 5. 2.** The disinfection of ISKNV using heat as assessed by bioassay and qPCR (Trial 3). The challenge inoculum was freshly amplified, high
 2127 titre ISKNV that was partially purified from Murray cod tissue and added to a standardized biological matrix of 10% foetal bovine serum (v/v).

Treatment	Amount of ISKNV in injection ^{1,2,3}	n	Days post injection	No. of moribund fish	No. positive/total no. tested	Median virus copy number (per mg of tissue) ^{3,4}	Bioassay outcome
40°C for 20 min	5.58 x 10 ³	36	1-6	3	1/3	1.8 x 10 ²	Positive
			7	0	9/11	3.4 x 10 ⁴	Positive
			14	0	21/22	9.5 x 10 ⁴	Positive
60°C for 5 min	9.58 x 10 ³	36	4	1	1/1	7.2 x 10 ²	Positive
			7	0	11/12	1.4 x 10 ⁴	Positive
			14	0	23/23	9.4 x 10 ⁵	Positive
Positive control	2.81 x 10 ⁴	37	3-7	7	4/7	2.8 x 10 ⁴	Positive
			14	0	30/30	3.2 x 10 ⁷	Positive
Diluted positive control	BLOQ	30	14	0	27/30	6.3 x 10 ⁴	Positive
Negative control	BLOD	30	14	0	0/30	BLOD	Negative

2128
 2129 ¹ Virus preparation was tested by qPCR following treatment.
 2130 ² BLOQ: Below the level of quantification of the qPCR assay, a high Ct value was obtained outside of the quantitative range.
 2131 ³ BLOD: Below the limit of detection: a negative result was obtained using an assay with a limit of detection of 100 copies of template per
 2132 reaction.
 2133 ⁴ Statistic only included qPCR positive fish.
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2136 **Table 5. 3.** The disinfection of ISKNV as assessed by bioassay and qPCR. The challenge inoculum was freshly amplified, high titre ISKNV that was
 2137 partially purified from Murray cod tissue and added to a standardized biological matrix with 10% foetal bovine serum (v/v) (Trial 4).

Treatment	Replicate	Amount of ISKNV in injection ^{1,2,3}	Proportion of moribund fish	No. positive/ total no. tested	Median virus copy number (per mg of tissue) ^{3,4}	Bioassay outcome
Positive control ⁵	1	1.6 x 10 ⁵	5/6	6/6	3.8 x 10 ⁷	Positive
	2		3/6	6/6	4.7 x 10 ⁸	Positive
Diluted positive control ⁶	1	BLOQ	0/9	3/9	2.5 x 10 ⁵	Positive
	2		1/9	7/9	3.5 x 10 ⁷	Positive
Chlorine 1000 ppm for 30 min	1	0	1/9	0/9	BLOD	Negative
	2		7/9	0/9	BLOD	Negative
65°C for 20 min	1	3.5 x 10 ⁴	0/8	0/8	BLOD	Negative
	2		4/9	0/9	BLOD	Negative
pH 3 for 30 min	1	7.4 x 10 ⁴	2/8	0/8	BLOD	Negative
	2		0/9	0/9	BLOD	Negative
pH 11 for 30 min	1	2.0 x 10 ⁴	4/9	0/9	BLOD	Negative
	2		0/9	0/9	BLOD	Negative
Quaternary ammonium compound 650 ppm for 10 min	1	5.0 x 10 ⁴	3/9	0/9	BLOD	Negative
	2		3/10	0/10	BLOD	Negative
Virkon™ 1% for 10 min	1	BLOD	6/9	0/9	BLOD	Negative
	2		1/8	0/8	BLOD	Negative

2138 ¹ Virus preparation was tested by qPCR following treatment

2139 ² BLOQ: Below the level of quantification of the qPCR assay, a high Ct value was obtained outside of the quantitative range.

2140 ³ BLOD: Below the limit of detection: a negative result was obtained using an assay with a limit of detection of 100 copies of template per
 2141 reaction.

2142 ⁴Statistic only included qPCR positive fish

2143 ⁵ Virus preparation was subjected to the buffer exchange procedure and then tested by qPCR

2144 ⁶ Virus preparation was not subjected to the buffer exchange procedure prior to being tested by qPCR

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2147 **5.3.5 Stability of ISKNV in water**

2148 To test the stability of the ISKNV in an appropriate biological matrix, naïve Murray cod were added to
2149 aquariums previously containing positive control bioassay fish with a clinical infection with the virus (Trial
2150 5). Once the infected fish were removed, the aquarium was maintained at 25°C with the same biofilter
2151 and without water change. The naïve fish were added to tanks 1 h, 24 h or 48 h following the removal of
2152 the infected fish. This represented 9, 7 and 7 days after injection for the naïve Murray cod added at 1, 24
2153 and 48 h after the removal of clinically affected fish. A 5 mL sample of aquarium water was obtained
2154 immediately prior to adding the naïve fish and frozen at -80°C until a sample of 200 µL was tested for
2155 ISKNV by qPCR (see below). Fish were fed as above and monitored daily for signs of morbidity. All fish
2156 were euthanized and tested for ISKNV by qPCR on Day 14.

2157 **5.3.6 Quantitative PCR for ISKNV**

2158 Sample preparation was performed as described in Chapter 2.3.4. Nucleic acid purification and qPCR
2159 testing was completed as described previously in Chapter 2.4.2.2 and 2.4.4.

2160

2161 **5.4 Results**

2162 **5.4.1 Trial 1 and Trial 2**

2163 From Trial 1, 9 of 19 Murray cod died and were qPCR positive. The peak mortality period was between
2164 Day 20 and 25 post injection. A further 3 survivors at Day 28 were positive for ISKNV. Target organs from
2165 all 12 positive fish were pooled in a homogenate with 9.74×10^8 ISKNV DNA copies per mg of fish tissue.
2166 From Trial 2, all 20 Murray cod injected with ISKNV-infected material (from Trial 1) died by Day 7. All fish
2167 were qPCR positive and the mean copy number for the pooled clarified tissue homogenate was 7.43×10^5

2168 DNA copies per mg of fish tissue. The ISKNV-infected material generated from Trial 2 was used to inject
2169 the donor Murray cod to generate the ISKNV virus preparations evaluated for disinfection using bioassays.
2170

2171 **5.4.2 Donor Murray cod for Trial 3 and Trial 4**

2172 For Trial 3, target organs were pooled from 12 Murray cod that were euthanized on Day 7 post injection.
2173 The pooled tissue homogenate (1/10) contained 3.62×10^6 ISKNV DNA copies per mL. The mean copy
2174 number for the virus preparation prior to disinfection was 5.7×10^5 per mL. Therefore, the amount of
2175 ISKNV in the injection dose (50 μ L) for the positive control fish was 2.81×10^4 copies. The remaining eight
2176 Murray cod were euthanized on Day 16, whereby most fish were showing signs of morbidity. The target
2177 organs were pooled and cryopreserved as a clarified tissue homogenate for use in Trial 4. The mean copy
2178 number for the clarified tissue homogenate was 1.3×10^6 per mg of fish tissue.
2179 Similarly, for Trial 4, target organs were pooled from 10 Murray cod that were euthanized on Day 7 post
2180 injection. The mean copy number for the virus preparation prior to the buffer exchange procedure was
2181 5.29×10^6 copies per mL and after buffer exchange was 3.2×10^6 copies per mL for the positive control.
2182 Therefore, the amount of ISKNV DNA in the injection dose for the positive control with buffer exchange
2183 was 1.6×10^5 copies.

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2185 **5.4.3 Trial 3 and 4: Bioassays testing disinfectant treatments**

2186 **5.4.3.1 Heating**

2187 Heating the virus preparation in the standardised sample matrix to less than 60°C was not effective to
2188 inactivate ISKNV, with both bioassays being positive (Table 5.2). However, heating at 65°C for 20 minutes
2189 effectively inactivated the ISKNV despite the detection of viral DNA by qPCR in the inoculum after

2190 treatment (Table 5.3). The detected ISKNV DNA was not infectious as none of the 17 fish injected had
2191 detectable viral DNA at 7 or 14 days post-injection (Table 5.3).

2192 **5.4.3.2 Chemical disinfectants and pH disruption**

2193 From Trial 4, all of the chemicals tested at the stated concentration and contact time were effective to
2194 disinfect ISKNV. Further, adjusting the pH to 3 and 11 was effective to disinfect ISKNV. The challenge
2195 inoculum for both the pH groups and the quaternary ammonium compound retained viral DNA that could
2196 be detected by qPCR, but it was non-functional as there was no amplification (Table 5.3). There was no
2197 detectable viral DNA in the challenge inoculum after the chlorine or Virkon™ treatments.

2198 **5.4.3.3 Positive Control Groups**

2199 All of the positive control groups produced a positive bioassay outcome. Clinically affected Murray cod
2200 were observed in the positive control groups for Trials 3 and 4. Histologically, megalocytic inclusion bodies
2201 were observed posterior kidney and spleen in two fish from the positive control group (Trial 4, data not
2202 shown). From Trial 3, 7 fish died between Day 3 to 7 with 4 of these being ISKNV positive (Table 5.2). All
2203 of the fish sampled on the final observation day (Day 14) were positive with a median copy number of 3.2
2204 $\times 10^7$ per mg of tissue (Table 5.2). Similar results were observed in Trial 4 with all 12 Murray cod being
2205 positive for ISKNV at Day 12 (Table 5.3). The median copy number of the virus was between 3.8×10^7 and
2206 4.7×10^8 (Table 5.3).

2207 The diluted positive control groups were used to show the effects of a very low ISKNV challenge as would
2208 occur with partial disinfection of the sample preparation. Despite having an initial injection dose below
2209 the level of quantification of qPCR, the diluted positive control groups resulted in a positive bioassay
2210 (Table 5.2 and 5.3). Trial 3 results showed that 90% of the Murray cod injected with the diluted positive
2211 control were positive with a median copy number of 6.3×10^4 (Table 5.2). From Trial 4, 10 of 18 fish

2212 injected with the diluted positive control were positive for ISKNV at Day 12 with a median copy number
2213 greater than 2.5×10^5 (Table 5.3).

2214 **5.4.3.1 Negative Controls**

2215 All fish in the negative control tanks were negative for ISKNV by qPCR at the end of the observation period
2216 for both Trial 3 (Table 5.2) and Trial 4 (Table 5.4). One fish died in Trial 4 and it was attributed to non-
2217 specific cause, otherwise the disinfected virus preparations did not cause any clinical signs of disease.

2218

2219 **Table 5. 4.** The negative control groups tested with ISKNV-negative challenge material (Trial 4).

Treatment ¹	Amount of ISKNV in injection ^{2,3}	n	Proportion of moribund fish	Days post injection	No. positive/total no tested	Virus copy number (per mg of tissue) ³	Bioassay outcome
Chlorine	BLOD	6	0/6	14	0/6	BLOD	Negative
pH 3	BLOD	5	0/5	14	0/5	BLOD	Negative
pH 11	BLOD	6	0/6	14	0/6	BLOD	Negative
Quaternary ammonium compound	BLOD	6	1/6	14	0/6	BLOD	Negative
Virkon™	BLOD	6	0/6	14	0/6	BLOD	Negative

2220 ¹ Treatment time and concentration was the same indicated in Table 3.3

2221 ² Challenge inoculum was tested by qPCR following treatment.

2222 ³ BLOD: Below the limit of detection: a negative result was obtained using an assay with a limit of detection of 100

2223 copies of template per reaction.

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5.4.4 Trial 5 Stability of ISKNV in water

ISKNV was able to remain infective in aquarium water alone (i.e. void of fish) for at least 48 hours (Table 5.5). From Trial 5, infection occurred when naïve Murray cod were added to aquariums at 1, 24 and 48 hours after the last ISKNV-infected fish were removed. When added at 1 h, all of the fish died between Day 4 and 7 post exposure. All fish were positive for ISKNV and had a median copy number of at least 6.8×10^5 (Table 5.5). When fish were added after 24 or 48 h, 1/6 (16.7%) was infected with ISKNV in all replicate tanks (Table 5.5). Two fish added after 48 hours died on Day 4 with clinical signs and both had very high copy numbers ($2.7 - 4.0 \times 10^8$ ISKNV DNA copies per mg).

2235 **Table 5. 5.** Stability of ISKNV in water as assessed by bioassay and qPCR (Trial 5). Naïve Murray cod were added to an aquarium previously
 2236 holding fish with clinical disease after 1 hour, 24 hours, or 48 hours from the infected fish being removed.

Description of aquarium prior to naïve fish being added ¹	Time added (h)	Replicate	n	Virus copy number per µL aquarium water ^{2,3}	Proportion of fish died	No. positive/total no tested	Median of virus copy number per mg of tissue ⁴	Bioassay outcome
6 Murray cod with clinical disease and high copy number	1	1	6	5.5 x 10 ²	6/6	6/6	6.8 x 10 ⁵	Positive
		2	6	3.8 x 10 ²	6/6	6/6	1.7 x 10 ⁶	Positive
5 Murray cod with clinical disease and high copy number	24	1	6	Not tested	0/6	1/6	8.6 x 10 ²	Positive
6 Murray cod with clinical disease and high copy number	48	1	6	BLOQ ³	1/6	1/6	2.7 x 10 ⁸	Positive
		2	6	BLOQ ³	1/6	1/6	4.0 x 10 ⁸	Positive

2237 ¹ Aquarium (100 L) was held at 25°C with the existing biological filterer and no water change during the time the tank was void of fish

2238 ² BLOQ: Below the level of quantification of the qPCR assay, a high Ct value was obtained outside of the quantitative range.

2239 ³ Water sample collected immediately prior to adding naïve fish

2240 ⁴ Statistic only included qPCR positive fish.

2241 **5.5 Discussion**

2242 For this study, the challenge inoculum used to test disinfection procedures was freshly harvested ISKNV-
2243 infected tissues that were partially purified with a standardized with a biological matrix. Foetal bovine
2244 serum (10%) was added to ensure the disinfectants were being tested under a high level of soiling. This
2245 was conducted in alignment with the guidelines for data to support the efficacy of disinfectants for
2246 veterinary use from the Australian Pesticides and Veterinary Medicines Authority website
2247 (<https://apvma.gov.au/node/1026>) and the ASTM International standard (ASTM 2018). High soiling
2248 conditions would be particularly relevant under circumstances of disinfection in an emergency response
2249 to an exotic disease outbreak. It was shown that at 15°C, 20°C and 25°C, RSIV remained infectious after 7
2250 days in autoclaved artificial seawater but not in environmental seawater (Ito et al., 2013). The addition of
2251 plasma has shown to interfere with heat and chemical inactivation of African swine fever virus, similar to
2252 MCV as a large enveloped DNA virus which replicates in the cytoplasm (Kalmar et al., 2018). In cell culture,
2253 African swine fever virus showed a ten-fold higher tolerance to a combined heat and alkalinity treatment
2254 in the presence porcine plasma compared to minimum essential medium (Kalmar et al., 2018). Further,
2255 the high soiling conditions are relevant to disinfectants that are inactivated by organic matter (such as
2256 sodium hypochlorite). This was demonstrated for *Ostreid herpesvirus 1* where measurement of the
2257 effective concentration of sodium hypochlorite in the sample matrix was shown to be required (Hick et al
2258 2017). The presence of high soiling condition also reported to reduce the efficacy of sodium hypochlorite
2259 against *Tilapia lake virus* (TiLV) (Jaemwimol et al., 2019) and benzalkonium chloride against *Streptococcus*
2260 *agalactiae* (Mon-on et al., 2018). This present study demonstrated effective disinfection could be
2261 achieved for ISKNV under standardised soiling conditions using heating at 65°C, chlorine, pH 3, pH 11,
2262 Virkon™ and quaternary ammonium compound at the tested concentrations and contact times shown in
2263 Table 5.1.

2264 The current study showed that heat inactivation was achieved in organ filtrates with high organic load
2265 when treated at 65°C for 20 minutes. Previously, bioassays were used to test organ filtrates with ISKNV
2266 isolated from naturally infected mandarin fish (*Siniperca chuatsi*) (He et al., 2002). Results showed similar
2267 heat resistance characteristics with the current study with inactivation after 30 minutes at 50°C and 60°C,
2268 but ISKNV organ filtrates were still infectious at 30°C and 40°C for 30 minutes (He et al., 2002). *Bohle*
2269 *iridovirus*, a *Ranavirus* in the same family as ISKNV, was inactivated in cell culture medium at 52°C for 60
2270 minutes and 60°C for 30 minutes (La Fauce et al., 2012).

2271 ISKNV has three protective layers covering the core double stranded DNA, being the envelope, capsid, and
2272 internal lipid membrane (Kurita and Nakajima, 2012). These structures could protect the core viral DNA
2273 and any disturbance could interfere with the ability of the virus to attach and enter a host cell (Williams
2274 et al., 2005; La Fauce et al., 2012). This study demonstrated that the accumulated amount of ISKNV
2275 remained infectious in freshwater aquaria at 25°C for at least 48 hours after the removal of clinically
2276 infected fish. Previously, it was shown that the titre of RSIV incubated at 25°C in environmental seawater
2277 quickly decreased to below the detection limit within 24 hours (Ito et al., 2013). There is no known
2278 information regarding the persistence of RSIV outside the host (OIE, 2018).

2279 Previous research has shown ISKNV to be susceptible to chemical treatments and heating for disinfection.
2280 Chemical disinfection was shown effective using formaldehyde (2000 ppm), potassium permanganate
2281 (100 ppm) and sodium hypochlorite (200 ppm) with 15 minutes of contact time using ISKNV-infected
2282 spleen and kidney tissue filtrates in PBS (i.e. low soiling conditions) (He et al., 2002). Further, it was shown
2283 that heating at 50°C for 30 minutes and applying a pH of 11 for 30 minutes at 30°C was able to disinfect
2284 ISKNV filtrates (He et al., 2002). However, using the same testing conditions, iodine, and pH 3 for 30
2285 minutes at 30°C were ineffective at disinfecting ISKNV filtrates (He et al., 2002). Using cell culture (i.e. low
2286 soiling conditions), RSIV has been shown to be sensitive to pH 3 and heat treatment at 56°C for 30 minutes
2287 (Kurita and Nakajima, 2012, Nakajima and Sorimachi, 1994). Similar to ISKNV, *Epizootic hematopoietic*

2288 *necrosis virus* (EHNV) is a large DNA virus belonging to the Family *Iridoviridae*. Using cell culture testing
2289 methods, Langdon (1989) reported that EHNV was non-infectious following exposure to pH 4 or 12 for 1
2290 h, chlorine at 200 ppm for 2 h and heating to 60°C for 15 min or to 40°C for 24 h. Changes to increase the
2291 soiling conditions in the above studies may affect the efficacy of the disinfection procedures.

2292 Imported ornamental fish are a pathway for *Megalocytivirus* to enter Australia. ISKNV was detected in
2293 numerous domestic populations of ornamental fish at wholesalers and retailers and at one aquaculture
2294 facility (Rimmer et al., 2015). The diluted positive control groups were used to show the effects of a low
2295 viral challenge and to allow for potential comparisons with suboptimal disinfection procedures. The
2296 diluted positive control groups demonstrated that the bioassay was more sensitive than the qPCR assay
2297 used in this study. Despite having an initial injection dose below the level of quantification, the diluted
2298 positive control resulted in a positive bioassay (Table 5.2 and 5.3).

2299 From this study, aquarium water contaminated with ISKNV remained infectious for at least 48 hours. This
2300 result highlights the importance of strict biosecurity measures with active pathogen surveillance in high
2301 volume aquarium facilities, such as zebrafish colonies for medical research and ornamental fish premises.

2302 Recently, the first description of a natural ISKNV infection in zebrafish occurred in a Spanish research
2303 facility in 2015 (Bermudez et al., 2018). Previously, only experimental infections with ISKNV were known
2304 in zebrafish (Xu et al., 2008). In 2013, several ornamental fish retailers in Germany experienced high losses
2305 of angelfish (*Pterophyllum* spp.) due to ISKNV (Jung-Schroers et al., 2016). The angelfish were originally
2306 imported from Colombia and at the time the virus was not known to occur in South America (Jung-
2307 Schroers et al., 2016). Moribund platy (*Xiphophorus maculatus*) that were being held within the same
2308 recirculating system as the angelfish were infected and showed pathology consistent with disease caused
2309 ISKNV infection (Jung-Schroers et al., 2016). Further research is needed to determine the window of
2310 infectivity for ISKNV-contaminated water.

2311 Traditionally, megalocytiviruses including ISKNV and RSIV are known to widely infect marine and
2312 freshwater fish species in Southeast Asia with the host boundary between the two viruses being
2313 considered unclear (Kurita and Nakajima, 2012). Current evidence indicates that we must consider the
2314 three genotypes of ISKNV as globally distributed pathogens, each able to infect fish in a variety of
2315 environments. Recently, it was shown that archival samples from epidemics in ornamental fish in
2316 California, USA from 1991 were due to the turbot reddish body iridovirus (TRBIV) genotype of MCV (Koda
2317 et al., 2018). Dong et al. (2017) confirmed natural epidemics of ISKNV infections in barramundi (*Lates
2318 calcarifer*) in marine farms from Vietnam. Between 2012 and 2014, annual outbreaks of ISKNV infections
2319 resulted in 40% to 46% mortality with younger barramundi (e.g. 3 to 15 g) being most susceptible (Dong
2320 et al., 2017). ISKNV distributes systemically via the circulatory system and ISKNV-infected cells have been
2321 identified in hematopoietic organs and most tissues, including muscle, skin, and eyes (Xu et al., 2008,
2322 2010). The importation of frozen aquaculture products with ISKNV-infected tissues could present a
2323 biosecurity risk to Australia. Recently, it was shown that RSIV-Ku isolated from diseased red seabream
2324 (*Pagrus major*) in Taiwan was a natural recombinant megalocytivirus of ISKNV and RSIV (Shiu et al., 2018).
2325 Given the opportunity for co-infection with ISKNV and RSIV, recombination events are possible. Continued
2326 research is needed to study the pathobiology, evolution, and host range of megalocytiviruses. Practical
2327 and efficacious disinfection protocols were identified for ISKNV which included: heating to 65°C for 20
2328 min; pH 3; pH 11; 1% Virkon™; 1000 ppm sodium hypochlorite and benzalkonium chloride at the
2329 recommended concentration and contact time.

2330 **6. General discussion**

2331 **6.1 Introduction**

2332 The emergence of ISKNV has become a serious constraint for aquaculture with the infection reported in
2333 new hosts and locations almost every year since 1990. Recently, ISKNV genotype has been reported in
2334 Indonesia infecting giant gourami (*Osphronemus goramy*) (Sukenda et al., 2020) with 90% mortality, TRBIV
2335 genotype was reported in cultured barramundi (*Lates calcarifer*) in Taiwan with up to 90% mortality (Tsai
2336 et al., 2020), and RSIV genotype was identified in cultured barramundi in India with 80-90% mortality
2337 (Girisha et al., 2021). ISKNV has a broad range of marine and freshwater host species and with the
2338 potential for subclinical infection, can be easily translocated through the trading of fish to new hosts and
2339 locations (Go et al., 2006; Rimmer et al., 2015; Jung-Schroers et al., 2016; Koda et al., 2018). Disease
2340 caused by ISKNV infection causes generic clinical signs in addition to the potential for subclinical infection.
2341 These characteristics highlight the importance of effective diagnostic methods and tests for use in
2342 surveillance for ISKNV which will support functional biosecurity at aquaculture farms.

2343 The research described in this thesis aimed to narrow knowledge gaps in ISKNV disease control and to
2344 strengthen functional biosecurity. The research presented in Chapter 3 demonstrated the importance of
2345 a multi-modal diagnostic approach and a sampling framework that considered a suitable sample size with
2346 fish at all stages of disease (e.g. mild clinical signs and moribund). This was suitable to identify a primary
2347 pathogenic aetiology in a complex polymicrobial and multifactorial disease. Chapter 4 presented research
2348 evaluating the distribution and diversity of ISKNV genotypes in food fish aquaculture and internationally
2349 traded ornamental fish. This utilised a technique to obtain complete genomes from preserved clinical
2350 samples to provide the resolution required to evaluate transmission pathways and for detailed genomic
2351 characterization of ISKNV. Chapter 5 evaluated practical disinfection protocols for ISKNV under high soiling
2352 conditions using Murray cod (*Maccullochella peelii*) as a bioassay.

2353 **6.2 Multi-modal diagnostic approach to investigate epidemics at sea cage farms**

2354 Fish in aquaculture are susceptible to a wide range of infectious pathogens including parasites, bacteria,
2355 and viruses. These pathogens transmit horizontally from fish to fish and or vertically from parents to their
2356 offspring. An accurate diagnostic method, which is part of aquaculture biosecurity, is vital to stop the
2357 spread of pathogens and reduce the burden of disease on aquatic farming systems. The design of a
2358 diagnostic process should encompass sample collection in the field through to processing in the laboratory
2359 using a multi-modal diagnostic approach for a definitive result. The variety of pathogens and their role in
2360 disease pathogenesis needs to be identified to create an appropriate disease control response. Chapter 3
2361 demonstrated the importance of the multi-modal diagnostic approach combining classical and
2362 contemporary methods for laboratory assays as well as prospective and targeted sample collection in the
2363 field. As aquaculture diseases are increasingly being recognised as multifactorial it will be important to
2364 collect data regarding the host and environment to help interpret the diagnostic investigations.

2365 A suitable sample size that is representative of the disease process is critical to obtaining a valid diagnosis
2366 of disease in aquaculture. The analytical and diagnostic specificity and sensitivity of a diagnostic test
2367 should be considered when calculating the number of fish required for sampling. The range of clinical
2368 signs of the fish sampled was also important to provide information regarding the stage of the
2369 pathogenesis of the disease. Recommendations from OIE (2019b) regarding fish sampling for disease
2370 diagnostics is to only sample the moribund fish. This approach may overlook the opportunity to capture
2371 the early stage of the disease process and possibly makes it difficult to differentiate primary from
2372 secondary pathogens. Additional data regarding water quality, farm management, fish nutrition and
2373 production will enable non-infectious risk factors for disease to be included for consideration of diseases
2374 with multifactorial aetiology. Chapter 3 demonstrated how the sample size and the collection of
2375 individuals with wide range of clinical signs was critical to determine the most likely cause of the epidemic

2376 and direct future efforts for disease control. For example, the sample size was 36 for each population and
2377 this was determined by an estimated 70% sensitivity and 90% specificity for the combined series of
2378 diagnostic steps. Furthermore, the sample size also designed to be 95% certain of detecting a disease
2379 process with a minimum expected prevalence of 90% which was realistic under the targeted sampling
2380 strategy. The study identified two ectoparasites *Benedenia epinepheli* and *Zeylanicobdela arugamensis*
2381 which most likely made a minor contribution to the disease process with the evidence on fin erosion. Five
2382 potentially pathogenic bacteria were identified in some samples. However, the bacteria were not
2383 considered to be relevant to the disease process as no histopathology consistent with bacterial
2384 pathogenesis was observed. Two viruses NNV and ISKNV were identified using qPCR assays that were
2385 selected based on the known risk. These virus infections are common in grouper aquaculture with NNV
2386 predominantly a cause mortality in very young fish, although infections can persist in apparently healthy
2387 fish (Sah Putra et al., 2020). The study in Chapter 3 used histopathological observation to confirm that
2388 only lesions attributed to ISKNV were present and that these were evident early in the course of disease,
2389 suggestive of a role as the primary pathogen. By sampling different stages of infection, it was found that
2390 fish identified with clinical signs were likely to be in the later stages of pathogenesis and had evidence of
2391 necrosis associated with megalocytes. Fish without clinical signs were in many cases found to have
2392 evidence of the beginning stages of disease.

2393 The OIE (2019b) recommends PCR for accurate detection of both ISKNV and RSIV genotypes without
2394 differentiating them. Diagnosis at the nucleic acid level has higher sensitivity compared to protein-based
2395 diagnosis which requires a certain amount of antigen protein for a positive result (Adams and Thompson,
2396 2011). However, the analytical sensitivity of the conventional PCR assay described by OIE was in the order
2397 of 1000 times lower compared to the qPCR assay developed by Rimmer et al. (2012). This, and other qPCR
2398 assays could detect as little as 100 copies of the ISKNV as genome were approved for ISKNV detection in
2399 Australia, despite the absence of diagnostic validation data (Australian Department of and Water, 2020).

2400 Using qPCR, pooling samples with 10 fish is acceptable under circumstances that the prevalence is >10%
2401 with high viral load samples, usually during an outbreak (Johnson et al., 2019). Furthermore, the pooling
2402 strategy may not be applicable for countries with an eradication strategy including Australia as the
2403 method will not meet the required sensitivity for surveillance considering that ISKNV infection can be
2404 subclinical, at low prevalence and low viral load (Johnson et al., 2019). The current OIE (2019b) protocols
2405 allows for pooling of no more than five juvenile fish (<3 cm) prior to PCR assay without consideration of
2406 the prevalence or viral load. It is suggested that this protocol to be revised where qPCR is being used in
2407 surveillance to limit spread of ISKNV.

2408 Despite the accuracy and sensitivity of pathogen detection using qPCR, this method alone may not reveal
2409 the cause of fish mortality, particularly with the examples of NNV and ISKNV which can be a persistent
2410 infection in apparently healthy fish. Combining histopathology from a targeted sampling strategy with the
2411 results of the molecular examination is essential to identify relevant disease processes. Acute mass
2412 mortality of farmed hybrid grouper investigation in Chapter 3 identified two key viruses in grouper
2413 aquaculture, NNV and MCV, and two ectoparasites that cause disease or mortality. The histopathology
2414 did not identify any vacuolation in the brains and retinas and observed megalocytes in multiple organs
2415 which was the key lesion for ISKNV.

2416 A combination of methods is often needed for a definitive diagnosis of a disease that is accompanied by
2417 histopathology (Adams and Thompson, 2011). Unbiased sequencing can identify a pathogen when it
2418 cannot be cultured, and a specific test is not available or used. For example, this method identified the
2419 pathogen responsible for heart and skeletal muscle inflammation in Atlantic salmon (Palacios et al., 2010).
2420 After a decade without pathogen identification, unbiased high throughput sequencing revealed that
2421 *Piscine orthoreovirus* was the main pathogen (Palacios et al., 2010). The cost associated with unbiased
2422 sequencing is acceptably low and is now a complementary tool accessible for pathogen identification

2423 during a disease investigation and will assist in the timely identification of appropriate biosecurity
2424 measures. This method benefits from investigating disease events with mixed or coinfections and for
2425 identifying novel or emerging pathogens for which PCR assays are non-existent or suboptimal. In Chapter
2426 3, unbiased sequencing identified that ISKNV was the genotype responsible for the mortality event after
2427 using a qPCR assay that does not differentiate between ISKNV and RSIV. Unbiased sequencing for
2428 pathogen detection can also be considered for outbreak investigations in remote areas or areas with
2429 limited access to veterinary diagnostic laboratories as samples can be preserved at the farm.

2430 **6.3 Characteristic of *Infectious spleen and kidney necrosis virus***

2431 Functional biosecurity requires adequate knowledge of the characteristics of the pathogen. The
2432 characteristics of ISKNV have been studied in some aspects such as virion morphology (He et al., 2000; Go
2433 et al., 2016; Koda et al., 2018), genome structure (He et al., 2000; Shiu et al., 2017), replication strategy
2434 (He et al., 2002), potential hosts (He et al., 2002; Rimmer et al., 2017; Go and Whittington, 2019)
2435 retrospective study with ornamental fish (Go and Whittington, 2006), and transmission (Suebsing et al.,
2436 2016). Important aspects including the stability of ISKNV in water and epidemiological studies of disease
2437 remain limited. No studies have investigated the stability of ISKNV outside the host.

2438 Regarding the stability of ISKNV in water, Chapter 5 revealed that ISKNV was transmissible by contact only
2439 with contaminated water (Fusianto et al., 2019). ISKNV can remain infectious in aquarium water in the
2440 absence of fish for at least 48 hours at 25°C even when the virus copy number in the water was below the
2441 level of quantification (i.e. <100 copies) of a qPCR assay (Fusianto et al., 2019). Water-borne transmission
2442 of ISKNV has been demonstrated in mandarin fish after immersion in water containing 10 ml ISKNV
2443 filtrates in 10 L for two hours at 28°C (He et al., 2002). This information highlights the importance of water
2444 disinfection in aquaculture facilities to prevent ISKNV infection in particular closed recirculating
2445 aquaculture systems.

2446 Genomic epidemiology using whole-genome sequences has provided sufficient resolution to evaluate
2447 transmission pathways which is essential to limit the spread of aquatic pathogens. This approach has also
2448 been successful with *Salmon pancreas disease virus* (salmon alphavirus, SAV) (Gallagher et al., 2020). For
2449 example, whole-genome sequence analysis revealed multiple subtypes of SAV infecting fish at farms and
2450 deciphered transmission dynamics at a country-wide level (Gallagher et al., 2020). In Chapter 4,
2451 information on the essential ISKNV genomic characteristics were obtained by analysing 16 whole genomes
2452 from this study and 12 published complete genome sequences. With limited options for viral culture, the
2453 hybrid capture enrichment method successfully accessed a broad range of viral genomes directly from
2454 fish tissues, including those with subclinical infections and low viral load which have not previously been
2455 available to whole-genome analysis. This method will benefit the studies of ISKNV from difficult samples
2456 in which cell culture is not achievable.

2457 The genomic characterisation of ISKNV in Chapter 4 identified 59 predicted ORFs with amino acid similarity
2458 at least 95% among three ISKNV genotypes. Despite this level of similarity there were considerable
2459 differences between the genotypes for the other genes, representing approximately half of the genome.
2460 This study included an RSIV isolate in hybrid grouper that caused disease of hybrid grouper at the same
2461 location and year as a similar disease was caused by an ISKNV genotype. The similarity of these pathogens
2462 was limited to 88% nucleotide identity across the whole genome. Despite the similar clinical signs of
2463 disease reported for the three genotypes of ISKNV, genomic analysis of predicted ORFs provided further
2464 support for differentiation of sub-groups within the broad ISKNV-species designation. Repeated sequence
2465 analysis in ISKNV genomes which revealed conserved repeated sequence patterns at clade level, also
2466 strengthens the separation of the three genotypes of ISKNV. There are important practical implications
2467 for considering the genotypes as different pathogens. For example, a commercial formalin-killed vaccine
2468 designed for RSIV provides limited protection to ISKNV in farmed barramundi (Dong et al., 2017).

2469 The ISKNV genotype has a stable genome with DNA sequence similarity. In the present study, multiple
2470 ISKNV Clade 1 genotypes from a broad range of hosts, countries of origin, year of collection and clinical
2471 status of the infected fish all had very high similarity (>98.8%) with each other and previously published
2472 genomes. Similar evidence of ISKNV genome stability was observed in ISKNV isolates from Banggai
2473 cardinalfish (*Pterapogon kauderni*) which were sampled from the same location three years apart. An
2474 ISKNV isolate (BCIV 2012, MN432490) had high similarity with a sample that clustered as ISKNV genotype,
2475 Clade 2. The possibility that this result reflected host adaptation is unlikely with the recent description of
2476 a Clade 1 ISKNV genotype from Banggai cardinalfish (BCIV 2017, MT926123).

2477 The high resolution of whole-genome analysis identified single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNP) which
2478 were able to differentiate ISKNV genomes with different country of origin on phylogenetic analysis. This
2479 will be a useful tool to understand pathways of spread for ISKNV including through international trade in
2480 ornamental fish. This is documented as a pathway for the global spread of aquatic disease agents
2481 (Trujillo-González et al., 2018). Phylogenetic analyses have been used to speculate about the country of
2482 origin for infected ornamental fish imported to Australia (Go et al., 2006; Rimmer et al., 2015). With whole
2483 genome SNP analysis, a sample that was derived from a dwarf gourami imported into Australia from an
2484 unknown South-East Asian location and purchased at a pet shop in Sydney was grouped with confidence
2485 among isolates of Indonesian origin (Chapter 4).

2486 Whole genome analysis is also informative for resolving current confusion arising in the nomenclature for
2487 ISKNV. When new isolates of ISKNV are reported in a new host, frequently the host name will be used to
2488 define the virus name, such as giant gourami iridovirus (Sukenda et al., 2020) and angelfish iridovirus
2489 (Kawato et al., 2020). This adds confusion when applying prevention measures including vaccination,
2490 detection, and disinfection. The genotype classification with a numbering system presents the most
2491 functional approach to ISKNV nomenclature and can remove ambiguity of a genotype name that overlaps

2492 with the species i.e. Genotypes I (RSIV), II (ISKNV) and III (TRBIV) (Kurita and Nakajima, 2012). Each of
2493 which can be divided into Clades 1 and 2 with sufficient genetic information. Whole genome analysis in
2494 Chapter 4 indicated that both giant gourami iridovirus (Sukenda et al., 2020) and angelfish iridovirus
2495 (Kawato et al., 2020) grouped in ISKNV Clade 1 and could be referred to as isolates of ISKNV, Genotype II
2496 Clade 1. Systematic nomenclature will benefit communication for effective regional and international
2497 disease management.

2498 **6.4 Subclinical infection of *Infectious spleen and kidney necrosis virus***

2499 Subclinical infection with ISKNV has the potential to spread the virus undetected through the trade of
2500 food (Jeong et al., 2008; Suebsing et al., 2016) and ornamental fish (Go and Whittington, 2006; Rimmer
2501 et al., 2015). Under experimental conditions, in Chapter 5, subclinical infection of ISKNV was observed
2502 both in positive control and treatment groups which had low copy number of virus. The current
2503 recommendation for fish sampling from OIE (2019b) may not be appropriate as this thesis confirms
2504 previous reports of ISKNV subclinical infections (Wang et al., 2003; Oh et al., 2006; Rimmer et al., 2015;
2505 Girisha et al., 2021). Therefore, fish in any condition of health should be considered for ISKNV testing. In
2506 Australia, ISKNV is considered an exotic disease that impacts the biosecurity measures which aim for
2507 eradication. For the importation of ornamental fish to Australia that are susceptible to ISKNV, health
2508 certification requires them to free of MCV (meaning infection with the ISKNV species) and must undergo
2509 further precautions such as 14 days of quarantine in the exporting country and then 7 days quarantine
2510 upon arrival quarantine before being released to the Australian market (Australian Department of
2511 Agriculture, Water, and the Environment, 2021).

2512 **6.5 Disinfection measures of *Infectious spleen and kidney necrosis virus***

2513 Effective disinfection procedures are essential components of disease management in aquaculture
2514 facilities as a part of a biosecurity plan (OIE, 2017). The purpose of disinfection is to prevent the

2515 translocation of pathogens at the entry and exit of aquaculture facilities (OIE, 2017). Disinfection studies
2516 of ISKNV are limited and conducted only under low soiling condition (He et al., 2002; Kurita and Nakajima,
2517 2012). Chapter 5 in this thesis demonstrated effective disinfection measures for ISKNV under a high soiling
2518 condition which reflects that which generally occurs in aquaculture facilities. High soiling conditions are
2519 needed to meet the requirements for evaluation of disinfectants for veterinary use from the Australian
2520 Pesticides and Veterinary Medicines Authority website (<https://apvma.gov.au/node/1026>) and the ASTM
2521 International standard (ASTM, 2018). High soiling conditions would be applicable under circumstances of
2522 disinfection in an emergency response to a disease outbreak. Furthermore, the high soiling conditions are
2523 appropriate to disinfectants that are deactivated by organic matter (such as sodium hypochlorite). Under
2524 low soiling condition, *Ostreid herpesvirus 1* was inactivated using sodium hypochlorite 50 ppm available
2525 chlorine for 15 min but remain infectious after sodium hypochlorite 200 ppm available chlorine for 15 min
2526 treatment under high soiling condition (Hick et al., 2016b). Under standardized high soiling conditions,
2527 effective disinfection for ISKNV could be accomplished by heating at 65°C for 20 minutes, chlorine 1000
2528 ppm, pH 3 and pH 11 for 30 minutes, Virkon™ 1% and quaternary ammonium compound 650 ppm for 10
2529 minutes. The results are essential to inform functional disinfection measures for ISKNV.

2530 This thesis revealed that ISKNV is infectious in aquaria water for at least 48 hours. The disinfection
2531 protocols in this thesis are applicable to inactivate ISKNV in recirculating water or wastewater in an
2532 aquaculture facility. There is a need to study the risk factors for ISKNV transmission which is critical for
2533 disease control. ISKNV can be transmitted through infected water (Chapter 5), cohabitation with infected
2534 fish (Go and Whittington, 2006; Rimmer et al., 2017), and trash fish (Lajimin et al., 2015) which become
2535 the main feed for grouper aquaculture in SE Asia (Rimmer and Glamuzina, 2019). The effective disinfection
2536 protocols described in Chapter 5 can be applied for an eradication approach in the circumstance in which
2537 ISKNV is exotic and disease control in aquaculture facility where ISKNV is endemic. Ensuring aquaculture
2538 facilities are disinfected can reduce the risk pathway for ISKNV transmission through the trade-in

2539 ornamental fish. Current guidelines for ISKNV disinfection protocols described by OIE (2019b) are lacking
2540 details and impractical.

2541 The current biosecurity measures to control ISKNV are insufficient in some respects. The findings in this
2542 thesis have filled knowledge gaps in controlling ISKNV with regards to a diagnostic method for multiple
2543 pathogens, epidemiology study informing the stability of ISKNV genome and supporting separation for
2544 each ISKNV genotypes and effective and applicable disinfection measures for aquaculture. These could
2545 become essential input to complement current guidelines for controlling ISKNV.

2546 **6.6 Recommendations**

2547 Based on the findings in this thesis the following recommendations are made to inform functional
2548 biosecurity in aquaculture associated with ISKNV.

2549 1. Multi-modal diagnostic approaches should be applied to investigate disease outbreaks. These
2550 should use a proper sample size for pathogen identification should be applied to identify the key
2551 and other contributing pathogens and non-infectious risk factors for a definitive diagnosis that
2552 can guide to appropriate biosecurity response. In situations where multiple pathogens are
2553 identified, histopathology is critical to assess the relative importance of each detection.

2554 2. The three genotypes of ISKNV including ISKNV, RSIV, and TRBIV should be considered functionally
2555 as different pathogens. Validation is required for methods that differentiate these pathogens
2556 including qPCR and IFAT are urgently needed for surveillance and diagnosis. Vaccine development
2557 should consider the efficacy against each genotype.

2558 3. Standardisation of ISKNV nomenclature is essential and needs to be resolved. A numbering system
2559 with the addition of two clade groups for each of the three genotypes is suggested for
2560 unambiguous descriptions of isolates within the broad ISKNV species classification.

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6.7 Conclusion

In summary, this thesis has achieved the objective of addressing key knowledge gaps required to build functional biosecurity measures for ISKNV. Multi-modal diagnostic approaches including histopathology and high throughput sequencing demonstrated a successful approach to identify the main pathogen for disease epidemics in farmed hybrid grouper in Bali, Indonesia. Molecular epidemiology using whole genomes revealed the stability of the ISKNV genome and provided additional evidence for the separation of ISKNV genotypes as pathogens worthy of individual consideration in disease diagnosis and control. The whole genome analyses were identified as a tool for evaluating ISKNV transmission pathways. Effective disinfection measures for ISKNV were evaluated and identified measures that are suitable to be applied in land-based aquaculture facilities. These findings are essential to inform effective biosecurity measures for ISKNV which is the key to control ISKNV in the growing aquaculture industry. Importantly, it is evident that ISKNV and other megalocytiviruses are an emerging threat to aquaculture production that require focused research and extension efforts to minimise the negative impacts on the health, welfare, and production of fish in a very broad range of aquaculture settings.

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